

University of the West of Scotland

THE IMPACT OF PUBLIC PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP'S PROJECTS ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN RWANDA - A CASE OF RWANDA SPACE AGENCY (RSA)

**Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the Business School,
School of Business and Enterprise, University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Business Administration**

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that, to the best of my knowledge, the content of this thesis is the product of my work and has not been submitted for any other equivalent academic award. I can confirm that the intellectual content of this thesis is my own and that any other information brought from other sources for the preparation of this thesis have been acknowledged. This Thesis has been undertaken in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of Scotland towards the degree of Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) under the supervision of Dr Nasir Kolade.

Signed: *A Mutamuliza*

Date :08th December 2024

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DEDICATION

I wish to dedicate this piece of research to God almighty, my incredible husband, Hillary Kamanzi, our beautiful princess Isimbi Lisa Ornella, son Kylian Lior Kamanzi, my siblings and their families and finally to my mother Oda Umubyeyi Gashagaza for their love, care, patience, and tremendous support. Although this research signifies an individual achievement, it is an encouragement for the rest of my friends, family, and colleagues, who encouraged me daily and reminded me that with God everything is possible.

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ABSTRACT

Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) have become a common practice by multilateral organizations, international financial institutions (IFIs), governments, and companies across the globe. The enthusiasm for PPPs is driven by their ability to assist developing countries attain sustainable development goals (SDGs). They help countries to mobilize capital for sustainable development, to reduce the risk of investments in the public sector (Ferlie, Lynn and Pollitt, 2005; Sharma,2016) and reduce the timelines of projects.

The purpose of the study is to investigate the impact of PPPs on sustainable development in Rwanda, specifically through the RSA. The study is motivated by the global trend in leveraging PPPs to overcome debt, reduce poverty and support the financing of infrastructural development. The study examines if PPPs contribute to agricultural productivity, if agricultural productivity contributes to economic growth and if agricultural production is sustainable.

The research employed quantitative methods using the Rwanda Space Agency (RSA) as a Case study. The case selection criteria are based on its ability to provide the necessary information on the variables that contribute to answering the research question. The research relies on quantitative agricultural data obtained from RSA and to obtain a larger picture, it employs a quantitative methodology to analyse quarterly data for a period of 6 years (from 2015 to 2020). For data analysis, the research employs Inzight statistical software that intelligently analyses the data and creates appropriate graphs of data and variable type. Data analysis is complemented by use of p-Value and the regression analysis.

The results show a positive probability of consistency in the growth of agricultural sector which is complemented by the International Monetary Fund data statistics report (2021) data on Rwanda's GDP. It indicates an increase of real GDP growth of 10.2% compared to 6.1% in 2020. Furthermore, the current statistics show that Rwanda's economy has been growing steadily between 6% and 7% annually with majority of the country's growth resulting from agricultural activities (Heinen, 2021).

The outcome of the analysis, though not exhaustive in nature provides opportunities for future research. This should ascertain if Rwanda's collaboration with the Public Private Partnership (PPP) in the development of the country's economy is sustainable. The overall percentage (%) impact of public private partnership projects in Rwanda's sustainable development based on sample data of the agricultural sector was 81.2% probability. Broadly, the findings from the positive coefficients at 95% significance confirm that there is a positive impact of PPPs on agricultural productivity in Rwanda. However, future research should aim to apply mixed methods and an expanded data set.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ADB	African Development Bank
AFC	Africa Finance Cooperation
APMG	Association of Project Managers Group
BBO	Buy -Build-Operate
BOT	Build Operate Transfer
BOO	Build -Own -Operate
BTO	Build to Order sometimes referred to as MTO Make to Order or Made to Order
BO	Business Object
CSTD	The United Nations Commission on Science and Technology for Development
DBO	Design -Build -Operate
DBOM	Design-Build- Operate -Maintain
DBFO	Design -Build -Finance -Operate
DBFOM	Design-Build-Finance-Operate-Maintain
DBFOMT	Design-Build-Finance -Operate-Maintain-Transfer
DBB	Design -Bid-Build
EDPRS	Economic Development and Poverty Reduction Strategy (in Rwanda)
EIB	European Investment Bank
EU	European Union
FAO	Food Agriculture Organisation
FDIs	Foreign Direct Investments
G20	Group of Twenty (19 Countries and the European Union)
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GoR	Government of Rwanda
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GPS	Global Positioning System

HIV Human immunodeficiency Virus

IBRD International Monetary Fund

ICT Information Communication Technology

ICP Innovative Cooperation Programme

IFC International Finance Corporation

ISS International Space Station

IMF International Monetary Fund

MINICOM Ministry of Trade and Industry (in Rwanda)

MINECOFIN Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning (in Rwanda)

NHAI National Highways Authority in India

NISR National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda

NPIP National Public Investment Policy

NPM New Public Management (Theory)

NPS New Public Service (Theory)

NPG New Public Governance (Theory)

PESTLIED Political- Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, International, Environmental, Demographic

PESTLE Political, Economic, Social, Technology Legal and Environment

STEEPLE Social, Technological, Economic, Environmental, Politics, Legal and Ethical

PPP Public Private Partnership

PPIAF Public Private Infrastructure Advisory Facility

PPA Public Procurement Act

PPI Public Private Initiative

PSC Public Sector comparator

PVT Public Value Theory

KPIs Key Performance Indicators

SD Sustainable Development

RDB Rwanda development board

RSA Rwanda Space Agency

RWASATI Rwanda Satellite

RWASAT-1 Rwanda Satellite 1

RURA Rwanda Utilities Regulatory Authority

TPP Traditional Procurement Practice

TPA Traditional Public Administration Theory (TPA)

UN United Nations

UN-Space United Nation Space

UNOOSA United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs

UNCHS United Nation Centre for Human settlements also known as UN-Habitat

UNSDG United Nation Sustainable Development Goals

UNCTAD United Nations Conference on Trade and Development

UNDP United Nations Development Programme

UK (United Kingdom)

USD United State Dollar

VFM Value for money

WB World Bank

WBI World Bank Institute

CHAPTER 1

1.0 Introduction

In very recent years, Private Public Partnerships (PPPs) have become a common practice by multilateral organizations, international financial institutions (IFIs), governments, and companies across the globe. The enthusiasm for PPPs is driven by their ability as mechanisms that assist developing countries to attain sustainable development goals (SDGs) rather than merely as procurement mechanisms (Mohieldin, 2018 and World Bank, 2018).

PPPs has been described by the World Bank as “a long-term contract between a private party and a government entity, for providing a public asset or service, in which the private party bears significant risk and management responsibility, and remuneration is linked to performance” (World Bank, 1988), PPPs are adopted to fill-in the public sector funding gap that developing countries face. Besides, being used as a strategy to mobilize capital for sustainable development, they help to reduce the risk of investments to the public sector (Ferlie, Lynn and Pollitt, 2005 and Sharma,2016). Public Private Partnerships (PPPs), if implemented well they can help overcome inadequate infrastructure that constrains economic growth, particularly in developing countries. Thus, reduce the timelines projects take and improve the quality of the projects (Argaw et al, 2016).

PPPs can help overcome some of these challenges by mobilizing private sector sources, helping improve project selection and on-time and on-budget implementation, and ensuring adequate maintenance. Although initially restricted to public infrastructure in the form of roads, railways, power generation, or water and waste treatment facilities, PPPs have increasingly moved into the provision of so-called “social infrastructure,” such as schools, hospitals, and health services. According to (Boardman, Siemiatycki and Vinig ,2016) PPPs enable governments to obtain private sector capital and expertise. Moreover, (Boardman, Siemiatycki and Vinig 2016) also indicated that occasionally, private sector provides the service that use the infrastructure such as clinical services and correctional services. Additionally, (Hashmi and Sanni ,2014) in Canada noted that provincial, federal, and municipal governments all employed PPPs for their infrastructural developments. This affirms that PPPs

are favoured as a quick means of acquiring infrastructure assets and public services indicating a major shift in the association between the government and private companies.

PPPs help governments including Rwanda to achieve sustainable development goals of their countries through increasing economic growth and provision of employment. This helps to reduce levels of poverty while at the same time providing domestic workers with expertise (Gidado, 2010). It is through such initiative, that governments have become so creative to improve service delivery and ensure better value for money from the projects undertaken (Ibando & Ndandiko, 2010).

Globally, PPPs are attractive to many governments out of the necessity for new infrastructure (Boardman, Siemiatycki, & Vinig, 2016). Nevertheless, (Luanda ,2013) states that governments have different perceptions towards PPPs with results that only developed countries are said to be fully exercising the PPP approach. Moreover, (Rosenau ,2000) has criticised Western European countries for shifting the role of social welfare responsibility to the private sector through the PPP approach. At the same time, in countries like New Zealand, Scandinavia and Australia PPPs are observed as an approach that has disorganized the traditional way of the public social welfare benefit system (Sharma, 2012).

Broadly, PPPs provide knowledge, resources, expertise, legitimacy, confidence and implementation. It is through these contributions that they are able to make significant impacts in achieving sustainable development goals (Marx, 2019). Despite these known contributions by PPPs, Powell (2016) and Leigland (2018) have also argued that they are at times very expensive. They also tilt powers in favour of the private sector, expand governments' costs, have no known socio-economic benefit and any positive impact on achieving sustainable development results. Given these misgivings, it is necessary to examine if PPPs contribute to sustainable development outcomes in Rwanda and how they do it.

Whereas several studies (Baporikar, 2020; Liu et al., 2014; Boardman, Siemiatycki and Vinig, 2016) observe that the interaction between government and private companies is motivated by the need to fill-in the funding gap, our understanding of PPPs contribution to sustainable development remains very inadequate.

In the view of the above observations, the main motivation for this research is to investigate the impact of PPPs on sustainable development projects focusing on Rwanda. Thus, this research aims to identify and measure the impacts of public private partnerships on sustainable development and whether they have any contribution towards sustainable development outcomes using Rwanda Space Agency as a case study.

1.1 Background of the study

PPPs are major elements that help in driving innovation and guidance in the national setting. The idea of PPPs provides new and innovative possibilities that were inaccessible and solved when countries adopt public and private investments (Wojewnik-Filipkowska and Wegrzn, 2019). The private sector has the ability to perform a key role in promoting improved distribution of deliberate national investments through PPPs. This benefits the general economy through provision of suitable and excellent infrastructure services and assist in the achievement of company objectives. Such kind of arrangements with the private sector improve the delivery of services through public capital influence to attract private capital to implement large ventures/projects.

PPPs benefit the public sector with its expertise via cost reduction strategies and technologies including efficiency in general project operations as well as maintenance. A well organised PPP has the capability to assign the tasks, risks, and responsibilities between the parties in the best way (Wang and Ma, 2021). Public stakeholders include the government and its departments, ministries, and municipalities while the private partners entail for instance local or international agencies with businesses or stakeholders with technical and financial expertise pertinent to the project.

PPPs contribute to sustainable development, which has been defined as a development that meets people's needs without compromising future generations' ability to meet their own individual needs. Furthermore, sustainable development emphasises various aspects influencing on the improvement of the quality of life of the present generation without using natural resources excessively in order to preserve them for the future generations. It is mandatory for companies to address challenges of economic development and

environmental degradation (Esposito and Dicorato, 2020). In general, sustainable development perception is dependent on principles that incorporate economic, shared responsibility, environment decisions, decision-making, prevention and mitigation, and waste minimisation. Hence, there are three basic elements of sustainable development and include social, economic, and environmental aspects.

The social component entails workers' health and safety, project effects or impacts over local communities, the quality of life and benefits of disadvantaged groups. The economic component entails creation of opportunities and new markets for growth in sales, cost reduction via developments and creation of additional inputs. The environmental component emphasises the status of waste reduction, less impacts on human health, application of renewable materials, removal of toxic substances among others (Anopchenko et.al., 2019). Environmental issues are the major causes of the current development crisis due to the growing population and its implications on the environment.

Rwanda Space Agency presents a good example of PPPs that contribute to sustainable development goals. Set up in 2020, its mandate is to control and coordinate various space activities in Rwanda while creating an environment which promotes entrepreneurial as well as industrial development. This facilitates creation of internationally competitive products that are good for local consumption plus export markets. In addition, Rwanda space agency is considered active in the African Union Space Science and Technology working group. This prepared the African space policy and launched their first satellite in 2019 in partnership with the Japanese Aerospace Exploration Agency. However, because of limited resources, Rwanda launched satellites based on PPPs. Rwanda space agency aims at increasing country's adoption of space technologies through long-term space programs.

This will stimulate the need for research and innovation development into space science technologies. Rwanda government active participation in international cooperation and partnership in the global space arena is essential in the achievement of their development goals and objectives. Space technology is recognized as one of the major initiatives for achieving sustainable development goals enacted by the government. Different

countries/governments continue to increasingly invest in space innovations to meet the primary purpose of addressing challenges of climatic changes.

Collaborations among PPP for sustainable development has existed for several decades at both local and international levels and has influenced change in the public policy formulation. The private partners participate in policy making agenda for instance setting of agenda, negotiation, resource provision and implementation, as well as monitoring. Fundamentally, PPP acts as a tool for attainment of the sustainable development goals aiming at increasing scientific and technical capacity besides formation of competitive industry for smooth running and operations of the local and the global markets (Zheng and et.al. 2018).

New and advanced technological development reduce the cost of space-based applications and collaboration between different stakeholders such as the local partners, national, regional as well as global stakeholders, which enhance the uptake of SDGs. According to the United Nations (2019), there is need to realize the economic and social transformation which are part and parcel of 2030 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

Effectiveness, availability and adequate PPP infrastructure are of importance in Rwanda to facilitate public services as prerequisite for economic development. These act as key indicators of competitiveness of the country (Petrov and Geraskina, 2017; Judyta, 2016; Olaseni & Alade, 2012; Price, 2011; Pitt et al, 2011). Under PPP structure, the private sector might shape and operate effectively while sustaining public infrastructure facilities. It also offers services traditionally delivered by the government for instance, roads, hospitals, schools, airports, bridges, prisons, water and sanitation ventures. PPP competence determines the country's success or failure in product diversification. It enables countries to cope with population growth, poverty reduction, and improvement on the environmental conditions among others (Carbonara & Pellegrino, 2014; Umar et al, 2013; Kokkaew, 2010).

Broadly, PPPs allow mobilisation of highly skilled and well organised private investors to promote the country's growth and capacity development in terms of operation and maintenance (Yang et al, 2017; Ameyaw and Chan, 2015; Kateja, 2012; Afolabi, 2011).

Through PPP collaboration, knowledge sharing via infrastructure, ICT and innovation the country is able to gain the state influence in the economy (Rwanda PPP handbook, 2016). Embracing PPP, SD and space technologies in Rwanda assists in addressing development challenges.

1.1.1 PPP, SD, & Space Collaborations

UN-Space technologies continue to expand their activities in the participation of PPP (public private partnership) to increase the use of space science and technology for economic growth and sustainable development (United Nations, 2019). In September 2018, the Secretary-General launched a strategy on new technologies to define how the United Nations system will support the use of new technologies to accelerate the achievement of the 2030 UN-Agenda. Furthermore, sustainable development has remained intangible for many African countries with poverty challenges (United Nations, 2019). However, Africa has been one of the priority areas targeted by the United Nations activities and the Plan for Implementation of the World Summit on Sustainable Development refers to Africa's sustainable development as a cross-cutting issue (United Nation, 2017). Space technology and its usage such as, drones, earth observation systems, meteorological satellites, global navigation systems, and communication satellites provide strong support for the implementation of the actions called for at the World Summit on Sustainable Development. These have made a considerable influence in attaining sustainable development in Africa. Africa benefits from the use of space technologies in different ways since space applications provide effective systems for connecting people worldwide and monitoring. They also conduct environmental assessments, natural resource management and utilisation, natural disaster response management and providing education and health services in remote areas.

Space technology is vital to agricultural innovation, modern agriculture, and precision agriculture. Earth observation technologies enable quick responses through offering timely data to foresee expected production based on the agricultural season (United Nations, 2019). Space technology is important to the farmers, food producers, agronomists, and agricultural legislators interested in increasing yield and profitability. Remote control satellites are main providers of accurate data in the agriculture sector, and they are used in monitoring soil, snow, drought and crop growth. For instance, satellite rainfall estimates can help farmers plan

about the timing and amount of irrigation. Correct information and analysis can also help to predict the agricultural production of the area, which is essential in predicting and reducing the impact of food shortages and hunger (United Nation, 2019).

Rwanda demonstrates promising progress in the process of establishing and reinforcing infrastructure developments and institutions including policies that promote innovation. However, challenges associated with the low research capacity, low level of interactions among stakeholders, inadequate financial resources as well as deficiency of coordinated framework, continue to hinder establishment of sustainable innovations (Yongabo and Göransson, 2020). The government of Rwanda has released the benefits of using PPP in Rwanda as well as the success achieved overseas. Public private partnerships (PPPs) are believed to be powerful forces for driving innovation, technologies, and critical thinking. Moreover, the incredible resources and trust the PPP share with the infrastructure, ICT and innovation sector will facilitate the process of achieving the state influence in the economy and desired SDGs.

The government of Rwanda frequently explore the benefits for expanding services and capacity improvement as well as global competition through implementation of innovative technologies across all sectors. In additional, the technologies in place enable decision makers to assess current and also predict/observe future market forces on local manufacturing industries (MINCOM, 2008). Therefore, this study is very important because it will be of great important to different stakeholders, including the government (policy makers), private investors and academics since it aims to assess the contribution of PPPs to sustainable development using Rwanda Space Agency as a case study.

1.2 The Research Problem

Although the application of PPPs in infrastructural development systems are big as they are and are becoming ever more critical, different opinions exist on how they are used as procurement approaches for providing public infrastructure internationally (Boardman, Greve and Hodge, 2015, p.442; Osei-Kyei and Chan, 2017, p.113). A number of studies have recommended them because they are carried out appropriately within the budget and they

are affordable than conventional ventures (Babatunde, 2015, p.4; Osei-Kyei and Chan, 2016, p.174-179).

However, contrary other authors have suggested that PPP ventures fail compared to conventional ones, since they are frequently delivered beyond the budget and completion period and intensify public debt plus taxes paid by the citizens (Hodge and Greve, 2009,p.35; Hodge and Greve, 2010,p.12; Romero, 2015,p.6; Babatunde, 2015,p.4; Osei-Kyei and Chan, 2016,p.174-179). These studies admit an existence of a divergence between their performance and understanding of PPPs. With regard to the study findings above, it is hard to predict the trend likely to be followed by Rwanda as it implements PPP strategies to achieve its sustainable development goals. According to Villanueva (2015, p.133) and associates, there are doubts, which are linked to PPP performance.

These entail broad PPP venture issues and agreements, roles adopted by the government in PPP activities. The reality is that PPPs are among decisions to select from for service provision alternatives, different PPP programs by the private and public allies and the long-term agreements (“incomplete arrangements” problem). There are also, democratic deficit issues, transparency, responsibility and regulation that have not been addressed institutionally.

Furthermore, through the literature reviewed, it has been found that a research gap exists. Thus, this study, seeks to examine how PPPs can best contribute to sustainable development goals of achieving full employment and reducing poverty in Rwanda.

Although most of the studies above, have looked at the challenges faced by PPPs, there is a dearth of studies that examine the contribution of PPPs to sustainable development type that contribute and how they do it. It is always assumed that governments focus on infrastructural development because it plays both political and social roles to achieve economic development. As a result, governments rely on PPPs for scarce financial resources to implement infrastructural projects, which ultimately contribute to poverty eradication through provision of employment to people. According to Maria Jose and Mathieu (2021), PPPs are progressively being encouraged as one of the ways for securing funds to deliver development schemes.

The PPPs promoters contend that PPPs are an effective means for bridging the gap in infrastructure and essential service provision to attain the Sustainable Development Goals

(SDGs) as highlighted in the UN's Agenda 2030. However, the mechanisms how PPPs through the establishment of the space technologies (RSA) contribute to the country's revenue and sustainability of development goals is not well known.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of PPPs on sustainable development in Rwanda using Rwanda Space Agency as a case study by assessing whether PPPs have contributed to economic achievements in the country.

1.4 Research Questions

This research attempt to deliver a systematic review of sustainability-oriented PPP studies, with the following research question being raised.

1. What are the roles of PPPs in Rwanda?
2. How and why PPPs become successful in different countries?
3. Which risks need to be considered while preparing projects related to public private partnership?
4. How have PPPs contributed to development sustainability outcomes in Rwanda?

1.5 Research Objectives

Thus, the dissertation is interested in exploring the connection between PPPs and economic development in Rwanda through highlighting the origin of public private partnership. This is done with the help of models that help to elaborate the economic impact, role and responsibilities of PPPs. How do PPPs impact sustainable development in Rwanda through the Rwanda Space Agency?

In addition to this, the investigation also discusses the risks that are associated with PPP models along with the concept of sustainable development. How does the Rwanda Space Agency support sustainable development and what is its relationship with the private sector? Hence, the objectives of the research are as follows:

- To discuss concepts of public private partnership.
- To identify roles and responsibilities of PPP institutions.
- To discuss impacts of private sector's components on economic condition.
- To analyse /review the relationship between PPP and RSA in attaining the SD in Rwanda.
- To evaluate or measure success of PPP in different countries.
- To identify risks associated with PPP's projects.
- To discuss roles of PPP in Rwanda.
- To discuss concept of sustainability.

1.6 Hypotheses

The research hypotheses to be tested to achieve each of the above objectives are listed below:

Hypothesis 1: *Impact of PPPs on Agricultural Productivity.*

- **HO** = Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) involving the Rwanda Space Agency do not significantly increase the productivity in Rwanda's agricultural sector.
- **H1** =Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) involving the Rwanda Space Agency significantly increase the productivity in Rwanda's agricultural sector.

Hypothesis 2: *Influence of PPPs on Economic Growth.* Tests whether there is a direct link between PPPs and economic growth indicators.

- **HO** =The involvement of PPPs in Rwanda's agricultural sector does not positively correlate with an increase in Rwanda's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).
- **H2** =The involvement of PPPs in Rwanda's agricultural sector positively correlates with an increase in Rwanda's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Hypothesis 3: *Effectiveness of PPP Models (types) in Long-term Sustainability.* This Hypothesis focuses on the long-term aspect of PPPs.

- **HO** =Current PPP models employed in Rwanda are ineffective in ensuring long-term sustainable development in the agricultural sector.
- **H3** = Current PPP (types)models employed in Rwanda are effective in ensuring long-term sustainable development in the agricultural sector.

1.7 Research Design and Methodology Introduced

A detailed methodology is explained in the methodology section in Chapter 3. However, this research follows a honeycomb research methodology as defined by (Wilson, 2014). It involves a step-by-step process, collection, analysis and interpretation of data, the honeycomb will serve as an appropriate pathway to conduct this study. The research employs a mix of qualitative through review of the literature and quantitative methods using the Rwanda Space Agency as a Case study. The case selection criteria are based on its ability to provide the necessary information on the variables that contribute to answering the research question. Despite the choice of one case, the quantitative method provides a larger picture by analysing quarterly data for a period of 6 years (from 2015 to 2020). It employs Inzight statistical software which is known to intelligently create appropriate graphs of data, automatically detects the variables type as either categorical or numeric and draws a dot plot, scatter plot or bar chart depending on the researcher choice of presentation.

This is complemented by the p-Value analysis, regression analysis using Inzight statistical software was employed to analyse data for its in-depth decision-making and separating important data from a pool of data. Moving further, the research highlights the data collection through secondary sources. It is important to emphasise that the research does not rely on primary data collected through a questionnaire.

The data was collected from 10 important and credible sources namely: Rwanda Ministry of Finance (MINECOFIN,) National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda (NISR), Rwanda Space Agency (RSA), Rwanda Geoportal (Spatial Data), Private Sector Federation (PSF), African Development Bank (ADB), Rwanda Development Board (RDB), International Monetary Fund (IMF), Esri Rwanda and World Bank (WB).

Thus, research uses the deductive approach as it starts with hypothesis and then gather the relevant data which is used to identify the evidence to support the hypothesis. The positivism philosophy is going to be utilized in this research as it focuses on the scientific testing of hypothesis and enables to identify the evidence.

Moreover, there is a wide range of literature that guides research methodology, especially the structure or architecture of the methodology. For example, (Creswell ,2009; Bryman and Bell ,2007 & 2011) propose a research structure in the form of a linear diagram while

(Saunders,2012) suggests a series of layers ,(Grix ,2002) proposes building blocks and (Wilson, 2014) has also proposed a more comprehensive structure, the honeycomb, comprising of six elements (research philosophy, research approach, research strategy, research design, data collection and data analysis and interpretation techniques) that interconnect to make up the research methodology.

One major advantage of the honeycomb over other suggested structures is that it does show the methodology and its elements in a logical manner while addressing key issues. This research work began with an in-depth review of relevant literature on the effectiveness of the PPP projects on sustainable development in Rwanda using RSA as case study. This research will look at the research onion approach and the honeycomb research model methodology based on the 'Research Onion' as defined by (Saunders et al., 2016) “containing six layers from research philosophy, to research approach, followed by research strategies, research choices, time horizon, and finally research techniques and procedure”.

Figure 1.1: Research Onion by (Saunders et al., 2016)

According to (Wilson, 2014), “The honeycomb research method is almost the same as the research onion as it is also composed of 6 main elements combined with the aim to make up the centre segment”

Figure 1. 2: The Honeycomb Research Methodology by (Wilson, 2014, p. 8)

However, this research intends to use the honeycomb research methodology as defined by (Wilson, 2014). Given that research is a step-by-step process that involves collection, analysis and interpretation of data, the honeycomb will serve as an appropriate pathway to conduct this study. The research has adopted the quantitative method to analyse quarterly data for a period of 6 years (from 2015 to 2020) using Inzight statistical software.

The diagram below describes the predicted best practice model adopted for this research project.

Figure 1.3: Predicted best practice framework model

The First Phase

The research aims to analyse existing PPP and their connection, contribution to sustainable development. As a consequence, the research will look at how the space sector contributes to sustainable development by improving the Agricultural sector. An understanding how PPPs effect on sustainable development using space technologies in other developed countries would be used as a benchmark and the outcome will then be adjusted to incorporate some aspects that are peculiar to developing countries in the same category and situation as Rwanda.

Generally, information, implementation and any potential outcomes of the PPP projects in Rwanda would be assessed based on what is available from local government’s legal framework, the private sector, of the economy and the space technologies as the basis for

analysis. This information will be complemented by data from a pilot study of a few selected PPP projects. The stages will focus on gathering information on the following issues:

- **First Assessment:** This would be done on the relationship between Rwanda Space Agency (RSA) and the Public Private Sector in regard to the Agricultural produce as the major source of Rwanda's export economy with the capacities of the actors, financing structure, risk sharing, resources control, and the cost implication.
- **The Follow-up Assessment:** This would be focusing on the expected management levels of governance and the implementation of legal, regulatory and governance framework with emphasis on stakeholders' involvement, accountability transparency, the process, and the procedures.
- **The Last Assessment:** This would focus mainly on the evaluation of the outcome based on the issue of service improvement, increased stakeholders' participation, improved cost reduction of PPP in order to sustain the development and encourage coverage expansion.

The expected outcome of this phase would be an improved general knowledge database on PPP in developing countries and more specifically in Rwanda. This would be relevant in addressing various categorised issues and ultimately develop the preliminary frameworks or models for validation.

1.8 Definitions of terms

1.8.1 Public Private Partnerships

Public Private Partnership (PPP) refer to a long-term agreement between the public and private agent/party for the development as well as administration of the public service or asset, whereby a private party bears a substantial risk and management accountability via the project life contract and payment is significantly connected to performance or based on the utilisation and the demand for the service or asset (World Bank, 2014). Public-private partnership projects are generally recognised to have a huge influence on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). For instance, PPPs influence not only on financial cost implications but also the effectiveness/efficiency gains through delivering the project plus

following up with its long-term fiscal associations like community's benefit (i.e. jobs creation, poverty reduction, skills and transfer of knowledge), risk and responsibilities (Sharma, 2016).

1.8.2 Sustainable Development

Sustainable Development is defined as development that fulfils today's needs without compromising the ability of the future generation to achieve or meet their own needs (United Nations General Assembly, 1987, p. 43). Such activities in the mutual cause have made sustainable development to be part of every person's vocabulary and agenda (Rogers, et.al, 2012).

The international community and the UN explicitly acknowledge that without the contribution of the private sector, sustainable development may not be attained (United Nations, 2015). For instance, the public and private sectors have more than 4,000 coalitions recognized and connected to one or different sustainable development goals (Marx, 2019). The efficiency of the public-private partnership is significant in the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and the institutional framework play a key role for the success of public-private partnership (Panayides, Parola, and Lam, 2015).

Successful countries provide the economy or society with infrastructure services to enhance the flow of Foreign Direct Investments (FDIs) needed to maintain economic growth. Development experience suggests that 7% of GDP investment in infrastructure is the right order of magnitude for sustainable growth and development. Infrastructure can be classified into physical (often referred to as economic infrastructure in some regions) and social categories.

Physical infrastructure includes public utilities such as power, telecommunications, piped water supply, sanitation and sewage, solid waste collection and disposal, and piped gas. Also included are public works such as roads, major dams and canal works (for irrigation and drainage), as well as several transport projects like urban and inter-urban railways, urban transport, seaports, waterways, and airports (Olaseni and Alade, 2012; Odedairo et al., 2011).

Public policy making is a key driver for the collaboration between public and private sectors towards sustainable development goals (UNSDG, 2018). To achieve the SDGs, the United Nations called all states and governments to incorporate the SDG goals into their national

sustainability and development plans (United Nations, 2015). By providing knowledge, resources, expertise, legitimacy, confidence and implementation, PPPs can make a significant contribution in achieving the sustainable development goals (Marx, 2019).

The international community and UN have clearly recognized that without the participation of the private sector, sustainable development cannot be achieved (United Nations, 2015). The public and private sectors now have more than 4,000 alliances recognized and linked to one or more sustainable development goals (Marx, 2019). The effectiveness of these public-private partnership is critical in achieving the sustainable development goals. The institutional framework is a decisive factor for the effectiveness of public-private partnership (Panayides, Parola, and Lam, 2015).

1.8.3 Space Technologies

Space technologies entail technologies used to permit activities carried out in outer space, for example Earth observation, satellite navigation, satellite communication, and human space study beyond the Earth's orbits (Baumgart et al., 2021). Space technologies are regularly established by governments, private firms, and space agencies with various motives. Baumgart et al., (2021) highlights an aggregate map for space-based technology projects' arrangement with the Sustainable Development Goals including their targets. The utilization of space technologies of Outer Space Activities (UN- Space) to attain sustainable development has acted as the focal point for management and collaboration in space associated activities since 1975 (United Nations, 2019).

It was established that PPPs alone cannot achieve sustainable development without the use of new and innovative technologies. Thus, a need for creative solutions to influence each partner's comparative advantage and mobilize the private sector investment and innovations in support of the SDGs (Mohieldin, 2018). And one of the examples of a cross-cutting goal is the SDG 9, "*Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.*" Therefore, it is both an explicit and implicit component of the SDGs.

According to the United Nations (2019), the use of space technologies of Outer Space Activities (UN- Space) for sustainable development has served as the focal point for the coordination and cooperation in space related activities since 1975 with the aim of promoting interactions and collaboration related to the use of space technology and its

applications in supporting the sustainable development goals. Previous studies discussed the benefit of space in general, whereby spaces or places have been highlighted as key drivers of innovation (Asheim 2000, Porter 2000, 1990) following the seminal insight by Marshall (1920) that “there is something in the air”, and the idea that knowledge spill overs are geographically bounded (Feldman, 1994). Innovation is spatially concentrated, and geography is “a platform to organize economic activity” (Feldman and Kogler 2010, 381). The essence of these arguments is that “geography and place-specific interactions shape industries” (Feldman and Kogler 2010, p. 383).

In addition, the UN General Assembly on international cooperation in the peaceful use of the outer space, urged UN-Space, under the leadership of the Office for Outer Space Affairs of the Secretariat, to continue to examine how space science and technology and their applications could contribute to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. It also encouraged entities of the United Nations system to participate in the UN-Space coordinated efforts to use space related activities within the United Nations System which serves as a strategic tool for the United Nations in the field of space science and technology to address climate change issues, space for global health, space for agriculture development and food security (United Nations, 2019).

The UN-Space technologies continue to expand their activities by considering the participation of the PPP (Public Private Partnership) models and cooperation with the private sector to increase the use of space science and technology applications for economic growth and sustainable development (United Nations, 2019). In September 2018, the Secretary-General launched a strategy on new technologies to define how the United Nations system will support the use of new technologies to accelerate the achievement of the 2030 UN-Agenda and to facilitate the alignment of those technologies with the values preserved in the Charter of the United Nations. According to United Nations (2019), UN-Space organized in form of a workshop the Office for Outer Space Affairs in its capacity as the secretariat of UN-Space and co-hosted by the United Nations Office for Partnerships and conducted a session held at the United Nations Headquarters on 29th October 2018. The objectives were to share experiences in forming partnerships to undertake space-related activities for the implementation of specific mandates of individual entities of the United Nations system, to identify challenges in building successful partnerships with partners outside the United

Nations system in support of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, and to share practices to overcome those challenges.

Moreover, the United Nations (2019) highlighted that sustainable development has remained impalpable for many African countries where poverty is still a main challenge. Approximately 300 million people, equal to 41% of the population in sub-Saharan Africa were living on one dollar per day or less in 2004 and thanks to the collaboration between private and public sector, this has significantly changed since then as many developing countries have experienced problems of limitation to achieve sustainable development which are often linked to conflicts and wars, inadequate access to education and extensive pandemics such as the recent covid 19, malaria and HIV. Furthermore, African continent continues to experience serious environmental challenges including deforestation and climate change. Africa has been a priority area for the United Nations activities, and the Plan of Implementation of the World Summit on Sustainable Development referring to Africa's sustainable development as a cross-cutting issue (United Nations, 2017).

Space technology and its applications, such as, drones, earth observation systems, meteorological satellites, global navigation systems, and communication satellites which provide strong support for the implementation of the actions called for at the World Summit on Sustainable Development and make a substantial influence in achieving sustainable development in Africa. Whereas Africans are benefiting in the use of space technologies in various ways. Space applications offer effective tools for connecting people around the world, monitoring, and conducting assessments of the environment, managing the use of natural resources, managing responses to natural disasters, and providing education and health services in remote areas.

For instance, space technology is essential to agricultural innovation, modern agriculture, and precision agriculture. In that regard, Earth observation technology enables quick responses using timely information to predict the production expected in an agricultural season (United Nations, 2019). Space technology is valuable to farmers, agronomists, food producers, and agricultural legislators who want to increase yield and profitability at the same time. In agriculture, remote control satellites are key providers of accurate data used in monitoring

soil, snow, and drought and crop growth. For example, satellite rainfall estimates can help farmers plan the timing and amount of irrigation.

Accurate information and analysis can also help to predict the agricultural production of an area in advance, which is essential for predicting and reducing the impact of food shortages and hunger. According to the UN report (United Nation, 2019) it is obvious that more is needed to be done and faster, moreover further striving response are in need to release the economic and social transformation which are required to achieve the 2030 United Nation Sustainable Development Goals. In addition, the report continues to highlight areas that can contribute and increase progress across all the 17 SDGs: financial growth; resilience; sustainable and inclusive economies; effective institutions/organisations; local action; better use of data; and connecting science, technology, and innovation with a greater focus on digital transformation (United Nation, 2019).

Furthermore, (Yongabo and Göransson, 2020) have highlighted that the building of sustainable innovations competences in Africa requires innovation system capable of distributing, producing, and using new knowledge. Rwanda shows promising progress in the process of establishing and reinforcing infrastructure and institutional development as well as policies to promote innovation. However, (Yongabo and Göransson, 2020) continue to highlight that there are few challenges associated with the low research capacity, low level of interactions among stakeholders, inadequate financial resources as well as deficiency of coordinated framework, all of which obstructing the building-up of sustainable innovation capabilities. The government of Rwanda has released the benefits of using PPP in Rwanda as well as the success achieved overseas. Public private partnerships (PPPs) are believed to be powerful forces for driving innovation, technologies, and critical thinking. Moreover, the incredible resources and trust the PPP share with the infrastructure, ICT and innovation sector will facilitate the process of achieving the state influence in the economy and desired SDGs.

The government of Rwanda continues to explore the benefits for expanding national services and sectors to improve their capacities and global competition in the implementation of innovative technologies across all sectors. In addition, those technologies in place helps decision makers to evaluate current and predict/observe future market pressures on

traditional manufacturing industries (MINCOM, 2008). The concept of this project is to enhance private participation in sustainable development of Rwanda using available data provided by the public sector (in this case Rwanda Space Agency). More so, this drive for SD have made the government of Rwanda to institute policies that will encourage the PPP. Therefore, Rwanda Space Agency is an integral aspect of this research work.

1.9 Scope and Delimitations

It is vital for the researcher to avoid restrictions as well as lack of validity since they pose crucial threats to the accuracy of the results (Leung, 2015). I managed to avoid and reduce bias in this study by recognizing natural prejudices and applying measures to dodge them. Disregarding biases can affect the foundation of individual's research development and practicality of the research results or findings. Failure to address the bias in one's study research can affect the efficiency of the study findings and also compromise the investigator's integrity.

In most cases, this may impact on how the academic world accepts or admits the general research. As a consequence, I considered it necessary to apply a quantitative research methodology by putting into consideration how the data had been gathered. The application of such design method assisted in exploring the issue at hand in order to develop a general understanding of the study area.

The research design has been utilised by various investigators to assess the phenomenon as it relates to the proposed research questions to respond to how institutions, organizations, departments, groups, or individuals fit into their arguments. It is vital to note that, the investigator may focus at a single-time occurrence/event, or they can study something over a specified timeframe, and I chose to focus on quarterly data for a six-year period.

1.10 Significance of Study

First, this study helps to fill-in the research gap in understanding the contributions of PPPs to sustainable development and how the state of Rwanda can utilize them to achieve sustainable development goals.

Secondly, this project is exceptional in that it examines the manner how PPPs can contribute to sustainable development and how these arguments can be used to develop a deeper

understanding of how they may be used to help promote a better understanding of the atmosphere in which PPPs may thrive globally and in Rwanda.

Thirdly, the research bridges the knowledge gap in the existing PPP literature in Rwanda. This is because little has been written about PPP in Rwanda, the little that has been done focuses on procurement not on its contributions to sustainable development. Hence, the provision of commendations out of a comprehensive analysis of Rwanda's PPP environment with a better framework model will become a major contribution of this research.

Fourthly, the debate on PPPs has mainly focused on them as sources of finance, which neglects a broader picture of their contributions and their overall governance role (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development-OECD, 2015, p.1). Beyond provision of scarce finances, this study broadens the role of PPPs to include how they collaborate with states in providing services to the public.

1.11 Structure of the thesis

Chapters: The Brief Argument

This thesis has been organised into five chapters, including references and appendices.

Details of the thesis structure are as follows:

- **Chapter 1: Introduction**

In introduction, provides the general description regarding topic. The chapter also presents the aim and objectives, rationale of selecting topic, scope of study, and the approach followed.

- **Chapter 2: Literature review**

It is the second chapter that focuses on the analysis of private public partnerships in different countries. It discusses the success of PPPs in two major countries where they have impacted on sustainable development. The chapter presents the theoretical foundations of the study.

- **Chapter 3: Research methodology**

This chapter presents the research methodology followed. It specifically discusses the research type, data collection, sampling, and analysis. This chapter presents the specific approach followed by the study.

- **Chapter 4: Findings and Data analysis**

This chapter presents and analyses the data in which researcher prepares the data, carry out analysis and interpret the result of the analysis outcome based on sample of data used from targeted survey.

- **Chapter 5: Conclusion, Limitations and Recommendations**

This chapter presents the conclusion of the study. It also discusses the limitations of the research work and recommendations for future research work.

- **References**

Details of the literature sources are provided under references.

- **Appendices**

Diverse appendices are provided herein.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter reviews the literature on the subject being studied and presents the analytical framework which guides this dissertation. Through examining the existing literature, we are able to construct the relevant framework on PPPs. To do this, our research like any normal science builds on research efforts of our forefathers through duplicating and refining their propositions (Kuhn, 1970, p.10-35). Although the literature on the subject is immense, the researcher shall only glean through the prominent works lines of inquiry on the subject matter. While going through the literature, it readily becomes apparent that achieving sustainable development requires access to financial resources, including appropriate policies. These financial resources are obtained through PPPs and together with public policymaking there is collaboration between public and private sectors to achieve sustainability (Marx, 2019).

The review of the literature aims to answer the main research question of the study the contribution of PPPs on sustainable development in Rwanda especially through RSA. Thus, the review provides a general overview and an understanding of issues affecting space technologies. This is done by using case studies of where it has been a success and exploring how Rwanda Space Agency (RSA) relies on PPPs to provide solutions to agriculture and environmental problems to reduce poverty in Rwanda. Broadly, the review critiques PPPs and presents appropriate theories on how PPPs contribute to sustainable development in the development of Rwanda and reduction of poverty.

To achieve the aims and objectives of the research, the chapter is organised in three different sections which supplement one another under the following themes: understanding PPPs from definitions, from the origins and current use, theories of PPPs, types of PPPs, their roles and responsibilities of PPP institutions. The concept of sustainable development, sustainable development and space, Impacts of the private sector economy, Success of PPP in different

Countries, PPPs as a mechanism of financing sustainable development, Rwanda Space agency. These main themes of the chapter are unpacked as follows.

2.1 SECTION I - Understanding PPPs, from Definitions and Origins

2.1.1 Understanding PPPs from Definitions

Despite existence of a vast literature on PPPs, still there is a lot of uncertainty regarding its definition. The definitions of PPPs are always slanted in favor of the different research being investigated hence, there are different definitions of PPPs. As one of the proverbs goes, “no one size fits all”, the recommended common aspects for describing PPP may not exclusively apply to every kind of PPP but offer a benchmarking average. This leads to wrong definitions of PPPs that could have been avoided both in studies and in policy actions. This also results in flawed practical applications of the term and the results of the wrong applications conflict with the intended aims of PPPs.

According to Farquharson *et al.* (2011, p.11) PPPs are described as “long-term contracts between the public entity and the private firm, where the private sector party usually agrees to design and build, expand, or upgrade the public sector infrastructure; assume substantial financial, technical, and operational risks; receive a financial return through payments over the life of the contract from users or the public sector, or from a combination of the two; and usually return the infrastructure to public sector ownership at the end of the contract”. Such a definition implies that: Project activities must be hustled into one or larger contracts to enable the private company to bear considerable project risks as well as administration responsibilities; Projects and their contracts should have a lengthy life span; compensation to the private company should directly come to the users of the services or, where possible, by the responsible government itself. Project agreements need to clearly mention how the provision of infrastructure ownership and tasks must be managed at the completion of the project contract. As already mentioned, this definition falls short and does not cover all aspects of PPPs or take into consideration the type or models of PPPs and is skewed in favor of the construction industry.

Conversely, Koppenjan (2005, p. 137) has defined PPPs as a form of cooperation between the public and private agencies in development planning, construction and/or infrastructural facilities in where they share and reallocate resources, benefits, responsibilities, costs, and risks in a particular project. However, this definition presents a number of shortcomings such as being function-based and precludes the informal and long-term relations. It also fails to take into consideration administrative and inter-administrative objectives, principles and visions in the PPP strategies (Brinkerhoff and Brinkerhoff, 2011, p. 3).

Complementing Koppenjan's explanation Zhang, Gao, Feng and Sun (2015, p. 499) stated that PPPs are "a long-term contractual arrangement for the cooperation and coordination of government, investors, contractors, end users and all other stakeholders that are involved in both the institutional environment and organizational processes throughout the whole development and operation cycle". This means that effective coordination cannot occur in short-term contracts, and "rules for decent order" and both macro plus micro levels is a precondition for PPP activities.

The second definitions of PPPs stresses cooperation and collaboration aspects of PPPs, which does not also consider the different models of PPPs and how they operate. It is also in favor of the construction and infrastructural development yet PPPs, can be used for different aims.

Additionally, Grant (1996, as cited in Alinaitwe and Ayesiga, 2013, p. 2) has stated that collaboration or cooperation depends on different partners' best expertise to provide specific public needs explicitly. Expanding the same point, Roberts and Siemiatycki (2015, p .781) and Kalpana (2014a, p. 17) points out that any partnership lies in the concept of "collaborative benefit", where persons from various institutions and disciplines support each other through work to attain outcomes, which may not be achieved without combined efforts. Successively, PPPs allow accessibility to important hard resources for example money, materials. They also contribute to soft managerial resources and technical skills, information, interactions, integrity, validity and political backing. These are at times missing or inadequate within a performer's reserves to attain public service goals (Brinkerhoff and Brinkerhoff, 2011, p. 4).

Nevertheless, PPPs' have been criticized for making governments fail to acknowledge the necessity for mutual obligation and collaboration. Subsequently, this turns PPP strategies into

“contracting out projects” as private partners not permitted to innovate outside the explicit agreement provisions (Roberts and Siemiatycki, 2015, p. 781-782).

Furthermore, the interdependence among the partners beyond the official agreement is minimal (Hodge and Greve, 2010). This results into loss of flexibility even when PPPs are expected to respect and adjust changes in the environment, they operate in to improve negative vital impacts on how public services should be distributed periodically (Boardman *et al.*, 2015). Building on their long-term characteristics and future ambiguity, PPP agreements remain partial. Hence, this necessitates effective partnership conduct between the partners to ease continuous commitment. This is in line with Williamson (1985), and Hodge and Greve’s (2007) argument that, “not everything can be taken into account in the detailed agreement or contract under long-term operational obligations. Maintaining such partnership conduct permits better provision of public services and infrastructure via mutual objectives, creating ways of dispute resolution via team approach. In addition, it allows for procuring the support of the participating parties for continual development, measuring growth and sharing benefits. From the conversation above, this study agrees with the deduction by Zhang *et al.* (2015, p. 498) that PPPs should be considered from a function-specific perspective, which stresses collaborative efforts with other parties.

The contractual view concentrates largely on the formal as well as legal relationship aspects, which brings both the private sector and the government together. The partnership view emphasizes the social element of the relationship that is associated with mutuality, obligation and trust. The function-specific view is based on tasks and applies the project lifespan approach in implementing and shifting (completely or partly) various project activities for instance, designing, financing, constructing, operation plus maintenance from public to private allies. In brief, common aspects that explain PPPs include public and private sector (inter-organizational) connections, risk and accountability distribution or shifting, competitive negotiation, hustling of construction plus operation, long-term partnership agreements in the project context, output and result based provisions that attract innovation, organizational systems and institutional processes, service provision objectives and purpose, compensation mechanism (via consumers and government), and usage of private investment in the expansion of public infrastructure or service delivery.

Given, the different definitions we have examined, Zhang's definition captures all aspects of PPPs, the model type by being function specific despite emphasizing coordination and collaboration.

2.1.2 Understanding of PPPs from Origins and Contemporary Applications

Local Government association UK (2022) has defined "a PPP is any form of partnership whether contractual, corporate, or collaborative, between public and private sector organisations. The role played by public and private sector organisations in PPPs are flexible to meet the requirements of specific projects and to harness the skills, resources, and preferences of the respective parties" (LG UK ,2022). Public Private Partnership is a procurement approach where the public and private sector join forces to deliver a public service or facilities. In this arrangement normally both the public and the private sector will contribute their expertise and resources to the project and share the risks involved (Cheung, 2009).

Furthermore, Liu, Love, Smith, Irani *et.al*, (2018) use the term PPP to refer to public-private partnerships as an arrangement between two or more public sectors. However, the origin of partnerships between the public and private sectors is traced to thousands of years ago in Europe. What is called PPP today has been used as a method for project delivery for centuries especially, in the transport sector. The involvement of the private parties in the highway projects were the first to turn things around one with the turnpike charter. The first private charter was granted for construction of the bridge where the American court cases started to get involved in the public private partnership.

In 1640, the Massachusetts granted Harvard College a power to run and manage the ship through which they managed to profit for over 100 years. Subsequently, in 1785 the company named Charles River Bridge requested the state to grant and give them a right to build a bridge across the river using a PPP method. However, the requirements were granted to the Charles Company to build the bridge and collect the tolls for 40 years. In the entire arrangement, the Harvard College had lost their ownership and Charles Company had to pay it pounds annually.

Following the collection of the tolls for over 40 years made Charles Company to turn ownership of the bridge back in 1972. This forced the state legislature to extend the Charter to 70 years from the initial stage of the opening of the bridge. Le, Kirytopoulos, Chileshe and Rameezdeen (2019) have stated that getting the charter for seventy years enabled the Charles company to operate the bridge successfully making the public sector to provide profit for the private owners. The Charter company slowly increased its level of efficiency and in the first forty years, the Charles River Bridge was able to approximately make \$1 million only in tolls. Due to the increasing productivity the Charles Company started to raise the prices of the tolls subsequently resulting into issues. Eventually, the bridge became successful and conveniently for the public and quite profitable for the private owners. In the first forty years of its charter, the Charles River Bridge had collected almost \$1 million in tolls.

Accordingly, PPPs originated by evaluating the benefits the public obtain from collaborating with private entities. Although Public Private Partnerships have no broadly acknowledged definition, it has been often referred to as PPP, 3P or P3 and increasingly promoted to finance development of projects globally (APMG, 2016). However, PPP knowledge lab define PPP as a long-term contract between a private party and a government entity, for providing a public asset or service, in which the private party bears significant risk and management responsibility to finance development projects worldwide (APMG, 2016).

As a consequence, the historical origins of PPPs led to differing definitions with other other various definitions of PPP slanted in the type of partnership that was entered into. However, the most notorious one is that of the National Council for Public Private Partnerships of the US which states that public- private partnerships are; “Contracts between a private sector entity and a government body that call for the private partner to deliver a desired service and assume the associated risks. The government is relieved of the financial and administrative burden of providing the service but retains an important role in regulating and monitoring the performance of the private partner” (National Council for Public Private Partnerships, 2012).

Nevertheless, in many other countries, this definition remains inadequate. For example, in the Canadian context, the term ‘public-private partnership’ carries a specific meaning because first it relates to the provision of public services or public infrastructure, but secondly, it necessitates the transfer of risk between partners. For the Canadian Council for Public-Private

Partnerships, the arrangements that do not include these two concepts are not technically 'public-private partnerships'. In this sense, a PPP is defined as a: "Cooperative venture between the public and private sectors, built on the expertise of each partner, that best meets clearly defined public needs through the appropriate allocation of resources, risks and rewards" (Canadian Council for Public- Private Partnerships, 2012). This Canadian definition more closely resembles the terminology used in countries other than the USA.

However, in academic circles, the scope of the term 'public private partnership' (PPP) is subject to considerable debate, however it emphasizes a cooperative approach and risk sharing. Van Ham & Koppenjan (2001) state that PPP are a: "Cooperation of some sort of durability between public and private actors in which they jointly develop products and services and share risks, costs, and resources which are connected with these products". Furthermore, the term "public-private partnership" is often misused and interchanged with traditional private-sector procurement contracts, confusing many people in the private and public sectors. When PPP was initiated by UNDP back in 1999, the idea was that local governments, business and civil society would work together and pool their resources, expertise and problem-solving methods combined to tackle urban challenges in a comprehensive approach.

Hence, the Program kept support to local governments and private actors in building innovative, mutually beneficial, and sustainable partnerships in urban service delivery. In support of such initiative, (Berthelemy,2004) declares that in theory PPP may have the potential to solve problems of developing countries, particularly sub-Saharan Africa's, profound infrastructure, health, education and service backlogs. Donor governments and financial institutions, such as the World Bank, have set up multiple donor initiatives to promote changes in national regulatory frameworks to allow PPP as well as provide advice and finance to PPP projects. According to (World Bank, 2019) when governments choose to use Public-Private Partnerships (PPP), the World Bank Group helps ensure they're designed well, benefit from a balanced regulatory environment and good governance, and are fiscally sustainable as it aims to foster better and efficient public services.

PPP also feature prominently in the discussions around the post-2015 and the financing for development agendas. Currently, there is a strong push to increase the involvement of the private sector in the development arena and to promote PPP as key tool to reach the soon to be agreed sustainable development goals (SDGs). It is believed that infrastructure investment helps raise economic growth rates, offers new economic opportunities, and facilitates investment in human capital (World Bank, 2019).

According to (World Bank ,2019) the numbers are stark: about 800 million people live without electricity; 2.2 billion people lack safely managed drinking water service. Congested and inadequate ports, airports, and roadways are a drag on growth and trade. Public-Private Partnerships (PPP) can be a tool to get more quality infrastructure services to more people. When designed well and implemented in a balanced regulatory environment, PPP can bring greater efficiency and sustainability to the provision of public services such as energy, transport, telecommunications, water, healthcare, and education. PPP can also allow for better allocation of risk between public and private entities. Yet, much work is needed to make projects "investor-ready" and to develop innovative frameworks to leverage private investment (World Bank, 2019).

The World Bank Group is committed to helping governments make informed decisions about improving access and quality of infrastructure services, including where appropriate using PPP as one delivery option. This approach is further enabled by working on supporting strong institutions, strengthening data, building capacity, developing, and testing tools, promoting transparency, and encouraging engagement with all relevant stakeholders (World Ban, 2019).

Having laid the definitional, historical origins and contemporary uses of PPPs, the next section presents theoretical perspectives of PPPs which helps us to understand them better. This section looks at the different uses and how they can be described as well as their contributions to society.

2.2 SECTION II- Theoretical foundations

2.2.0 Introduction to Theoretical Perspectives of PPPs

There are different theoretical perspectives that interpret how PPPs contribute to economic growth and sustainable development goals. These theories entail institutional, game, stakeholder, principal-agent, networking, market failure and transaction cost economics. Although these theories demonstrate a more general interpretation of PPPs, they do not have consistency or the desirable emphasis of the public sector view of service delivery or contributions to agriculture or any other sector. Consequently, this study presents five theories namely: the traditional public administration (TPA), the new public service (NPS), the new public governance (NPG), and the public value (PV) theories as the most appropriate in understanding PPPs, how they operate and contribute to service delivery, economic growth and sustainable development goals.

2.2.1 Traditional Public Administration Theory (TPA)

The TPA theory concentrates on policy making efficiency of the development and the level at which public policy execution addresses goals of the current public policies (Osborne, 2010, p. 415). Xu, Sun and Si (2015, p. 15) noted that, in nations with ineffective market mechanisms plus undeveloped third sector, the régime acts as the complete leader of the political structure arrangement and provision of the public goods. Regrettably, the government is anticipated to provide numerous economic and social needs of the people without considering the “real” needs of the public.

However, TPA seems inappropriate in interpreting PPPs contribution to economic growth, governance and sustainable development goals. This is because the public sector isolates itself from partnership relations with the provider and the receiver of the service. The involvement of the citizens or the private sector in the delivery of public services is typically transactional. The presence of collaboration between the government, people and the private companies is almost not there, in that, apart from the period of real transaction or service delivery, there is no connection to be sustained. Thus, TPA objective is to foster top-down management structures, whereby the public service delivery is a complete responsibility of the public leaders who are only answerable to politicians via constitutional guidelines for

oversight, selection, budgeting and lawmaking. According to Willems and Van Dooren (2016, p. 202) stated, TPA creates short-sighted plus unstable public strategies planned to satisfy the self-centered concerns of influential and disciplined interest groups/persons (of course in crime), officials inclusive.

2.2.2 New Public Management Theory (NPM)

NPM as a theory, is credited for bringing the enterprise or business management methods to the government (Xu et al., 2015, p. 15). As stated by Peters (2010, p. 40), public service provision via bureaucratic procedures is not only “clumsy, unsuccessful but also insensitive”. Nevertheless, developing nations have not yet considerably substituted TPA with NPM theory practices since most government roles continue to be vertically implemented (Mongkol, 2011, p. 39; Xu et al., 2015, p. 12). NPM reforms largely aim at refining public facilities through a two-fold “government - market” structure (Mongkol, 2011, p. 35) whereby the government provides capital to outsource the public goods or services from other firms particularly the private sector.

NPM practices focuses the connection between the government plus the market (Bonina and Cordella, 2009, p. 2; Bao, Wang, Larsen and Morgan, 2012, p. 445; Xu et al., 2015), therefore, “favoring the private over the government or public sector, a person over the community, the client over the citizen, rivalry over collaboration, inert product consumption over active social involvement, and individual choice over public accountability” (Benington, 2007, p. 2-5).

What is the relevance of NPM theory to PPPs in contributing to economic growth?

The public sector creates policies and regulates how public services are delivered by the private sector organizations through performance indicators, monitoring and market-oriented mechanisms. PPPs are morally based on profitable lines aiming at attaining value for money through incorporating some or various public infrastructure scheme tasks into one long-term agreement endorsed via a competitive tendering procedure. This helps to save money for the governments enabling it to have more resources to invest in the economy contribution to economic growth. Due to the transparent and competitive methods of procurement utilized, PPPs allow service users especially mainly direct users to contribute both in the course of defining public policy and influencing category and quality of the service provided. The effectiveness of NPM to Public-Private Partnerships is dual.

Firstly, due of the PPP contracts' longevity, the private sector agency is able to generate reasonable earnings as the primary heavy investment expenditures are remunerated by the reduced forthcoming maintenance as well as operational costs.

Secondly, the public sector has the ability to transfer the tasks and risks to a more capable, skilled and expert private companies whose payment is reliant on ensuring that the physical infrastructure accessible and running the similar facility to deliver the required service.

2.2.3 New Public Service Theory (NPS)

This NPS theor is based on the norms or practices which highlight democracy as well as citizenship (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2015, p. 664), and places the people or citizens at the center of handling public affairs (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2000, p. 550). The Government is anticipated to "perform an active role of creating arenas where citizens, via discourse, can clarify shared values and advance a shared sense of the community/public interest" (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2007, p. 66) than the government "struggling to control or steer the society in new guidelines" (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2015, p. 669).

This theory provides problems solving methods by working with people to address society challenges, fairness (services are delivered in an equitable manner to everyone), fiscal accountability (usage of money sensibly), and citizen impact (citizens influencing on the quality of the service they get from the public sector/government) (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2007, p. 61).

Through the process NPS is able to explain how PPPs contribute to economic growth and sustainable development goals by benefiting majority.

Denhardt and Denhardt (2007, p. 4) contend that, the NPS movement "is being demonstrated in a way we relate with political leaders, how we participate with citizens, and how we cause positive impacts in our institutions and communities". Nevertheless, "for the public servants to behave as if their form of public interest is one way or another greater than the citizens' perspectives and values, elected representatives, interest groups, plus political parties is autocratic and unethical" (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2007, p. 80). Instead, the public managers need to "concentrate on creating opportunities for the citizenship by forging trusting relationships with the public members" (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2015, p. 665), while evading

“quick solutions to the problems resulting from personal choices” (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2015, p. 668).

During the process, citizens study more about the government and the government also learns more about the citizens (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2007, p. 155). As a result, this increases trust and willingness of the citizens to pay for public investments, and the public/government getting eager to safeguard that contractors uphold effective processes, best quality, competitive charges, and citizen gratification (Denhardt and Denhardt, 2015, p. 669).

How does NPS contribute to PPPs

NPS focuses on compliance of the public interests via collective relationships, shared tasks and joint understanding of public matters, and active contribution of citizens in government events (Robinson, 2015, p. 11). The New public service practices safeguard PPPs by fulfilling the cooperative public interests, as public servants have the mandate to promote innovative ways of establishing citizen involvement in discovering solutions to the societal issues. Through the process, governments promote economic growth and drive their sustainable development goals ahead. This is done by public directors follow up on the execution of PPP policy via brokering, negotiation as well as resolving broad service provision problems through collaboration with the citizens.

Additionally, the responsibility of public servants goes beyond elected representatives to integrate a wider set of responsibility relationships with the citizens and communities (Robinson, 2015, p. 10). The key government’s role is to offer an environment where PPPs can respond to the society’s service provision needs via dialogue, responsible, open, flexible, available, and transparent ways and structures.

2.2.4 Public Value Theory (PVT)

Public value is the value, which is “consumed” jointly by the citizenry rather than individually by customers (Alford and Hughes, 2008, p. 2). Spano (2009, p. 330) argues that “everything contains a value when anybody is prepared to experience a sacrifice to achieve it, since he/she accepts that the possible benefits surpass the sacrifices”. At the society level, the public values offer “normative consensus on: (a) the human rights, benefits and privileges to which citizens

must (and must not) be entitled; (b) the citizens' obligations to society, the state, and one another; and (c) the values or principles on which governments and their policies should be grounded" (Bozeman, 2007, p. 13).

Thus, public value involves a rigorous way of handling democratic discrepancies, judging the feasibility of projects, decision-making, and of explaining, measuring and improving on performance (Rutgers, 2015, p. 29; Sufna and Fernand, 2015, p. 1-3). As a result, Public Value (PV) carries both democratic standards (equity, honesty plus fairness), and the administrative values (efficacy and efficiency) while performing responsibilities (Bonina and Cordella, 2009, p. 2). Basing on the above conclusions, PV practices improve citizen welfare by addressing market failures of undesirable externalities, natural monopolies and damaged information, and rises trust for and the government's legitimacy (Alford and Hughes, 2008, p. 2-3; Talbot, 2008. P. 18). These translate into:

(a) creation of employment and economic activities,

(b) enhanced social capital, social unity, societal relationships, social meaning and social identity, personal and community welfare,

(c) improved democratic discussion, active involvement and citizen participation, and

(d) better sustainable development as well as reduced public "bads" for example pollution, waste plus global warming (Benington, 2007, p. 11-12). Nevertheless, the above-mentioned benefits, PV is criticized for concentrating on attaining and measuring intermediate to long-term objectives, yet governments, which are dictated by electoral systems tend to concentrate on the short-term goals.

However, such can be controlled given that the public employees or servants have a duty to focus on the long-standing public value (Benington, 2007, p. 17), but on terms and conditions that they (or the public servants) do not participate in partisan politics instead restrict themselves to "program politics" since the actual political environment may limit their independence in service provision (Alford and Hughes, 2008, p. 5).

Relevance of PVT on PPPs

It promotes accountability and responsibility among public institutions, including both political leaders and citizens. It goes beyond political democracy, which restricts itself to the

election box, to the level where public leaders have the ability to satisfy citizens' interests via administrative systems, which are more sensitive to traditional conditions (Blaug, Horner & Lekhi, 2006, p. 6). For the PPPs to contribute to economic growth and sustainable development goals on service provision, public organizations need to attend to, shape and notify the public preferences through deliberative participation, improved information and educational interventions that are clearer and visionary. This is likely, only if public bosses have the ability to apply innovative ways that inspire institutions, politicians plus citizens to respond to the innovative public preferences positively.

According to Coats' (2006, p. 40) recommendations, public leaders can ensure that PPPs increase both quality and quantity of public actions for the resources used. Among the significant tools for advancing the public value model in the real PPP setting is named the "Public Value Scorecard" established by Meynhardt (2012, p. 23-24). This is an effective administrative tool for measuring the viability of planned PPP projects and assessing the suitability of project execution decisions utilizing the approach of chance and risk. Since the tool evaluates and assesses several PPP working structures and system settings while creating a trade off amongst five aspects or dimensions of , including, effectiveness, utility, decency, positive understanding and political acceptance/realism, the tool confirms that PPPs' strategies and management policies are valid, operationally viable, sustainable and valuable to the citizens as well as the private actors.

In summary , PV paradigm offers tools to prove why public money would be or way in which it was expended on PPPs; enhances on the quality of making choices via bringing out evidence based answers; contests a morally technocratic and expert-led performance technique; ensures full application of the information and knowledge of service for consumers and citizens; teaches the public on the difficulties confronting politicians as well public managers and the restrictions of what can probably be provided; and ensures efficient administration of various political risks (Coyle and Woolard, 2010, p. 11).

2.2.5 New Public Governance Theory (NPG)

NPG Theory is a method of practice, which is more embraced or adapted to the modern administration of public activities (Xu et al., 2015, p. 11). It demonstrates public policy sustainability, public facilities, public service institutions, community and environmental

issues (Osborne, 2010, p. 413) by generating transparent actions, processes and transparent structures, which are more socially receptive (Patapas, Raipa and Smalskys, 2014, p. 28). NPG looks at public affairs management from numerous elements of socio-political influence, public policy influence, administrative governance, agreement governance, corporate governance, meta-governance, decentered control as well as network governance (Osborne, 2010, p. 6-7; Rhodes, 1996, p. 653; Rhodes, 2016, p. 6-7). The NPG theory is positioned on effective administration of organizational and outside environment factors, which can enable and compel public policy execution and provision of public services in a plural as well as a pluralist system (Osborne, 2010, p.415). A plural system entails where several interdependent players contribute to public service provision, whereas a pluralist system refers to where numerous processes notify the policy-making structure or system (Koenig-Archibugi, 2003, p. 319).

According to Kooiman (1993, p. 4), “no sole actor, whether public or private, has complete resources such as knowledge and data necessary to solve multifaceted, dynamic and different problems; no sole actor has adequate overview to ensure the utilization of needed tools effectiveness; there is no single actor with appropriate action possible to dominate individually in a specific governing model”. New public governance applications acknowledge that there is some change from direct governance forms to the process of governance implemented via plurality of players or actors, places, spatial scales, and procedures, under an increasing dependence by the government on the informal forms of authority and power instead of formal authority only (Kennett, 2010, p. 25).

This leads to the development of additional “joined up” policies and “people centered” methodologies or approaches where various levels of government operate together in closer collaboration with various public, private, charitable and informal public institutions to encourage more decentralized “self-sustaining structures of development” for the public welfare and satisfaction (Benington, 2003).

Why NPG theory to PPPs?

NPG work concentrate on how guidelines and norms are progressively co-created and co-controlled by the state, citizens plus non-state actors via autonomy as well as authority sharing to provide public services.

NPG promotes the delivery of public services via PPPs basing on dual collaboration and governance-controlled systems to allow actual partnership, straight power relations, close institutional relations, trust, status, reciprocity, joint interdependence and mutual decision-making as stated by (Stelling, 2014, p. 11; Mauri and Muccio, 2012, p. 51). Consequently, “PPP’s have turned to be a continuing reconfiguration of power in a world of politics” (Stelling, 2014, p. 12-13). This statement is justified by present governance and administration systems, which encourage coexistence of organizational, prescribed and informal connection structures where citizens, private sector, government, and Non-Governmental Organizations are provided with a chance to jointly direct and contribute to public service delivery. This prompts the PPP actions to be coordinated under well-networked institutional structures, managerial and organizational policies, which are focused towards the attainment of collectively determined service provision outcomes. The co-production as well as the co-regulation interventions developed by the NPG approach allow the public service shareholders to exchange a lot of information and utilize each other’s skills and knowledge to create more innovative and improved PPP products plus policy outputs to respond to broad societal problems (Klijn, 2010a, p. 73).

2.2.6 Relevance of the Theories to PPPs

Traditional Public Administration Theory (TPA) is not well-matched with the PPP practices, values and principles. This is because it has failed to encourage the participation of the private sector via competitive and or partnership ways, TPA does not permit the public and private sector actors to innovate, reduces the third sector’s influence, payments for the services can be in advance or soon after service delivery but it is not grounded on a long-term accrual basis, TPA theory leaves government as the only designer as well as implementer of the public policies during the delivery of public services.

New Public Management (NPM), Public Value (PV), New Public Service (NPS), and New public Governance (NPG) are more applicable as theories of PPPs, and they are applied to inform the general study. Although all these theories are applicable, the study utilizes mainly NPG as the main theory that interprets the role of PPPs contribution to economic growth and sustainable development goals.

All these theories above focus on interpreting PPPs from the governance perspective by emphasizing collaboration and coordination but fail to clearly interpret how PPPs contribute to economic growth and sustainable development. However, they provide us with the general means on how we should interpret PPPs from a governance and networking perspective. They are all encompassing in their interpretation of PPPs from a perspective of collaboration and coordination with governments. After having gone through the theoretical perspectives of PPPs, the next subsection, which examines the different models or types of PPPs will help us to see that PPPs are better understood from a function specific perspective on which they are designed.

2.3 Types of PPPs by Governance

According to (Parker, Dressel, Chevers and Zeppetella, 2018) it has been stated that Public Private Partnership is an arrangement between the private and government sector where the BOT model refers as build-operate-transfer is utilized to finance the large kind of projects such as infrastructure projects via PPP. Under this kind of model, the government usually grants the private organization to finance, build, and operate an appropriate project. These projects take time approximately 20-30 years with accomplishing the goals of obtaining the investment and then transfers the entire control of the project to the government party. In general, such projects are large-scale and infrastructural financed, built and operated by both the government and the private sector.

In addition, the public sector which is the government allows the private companies to collect and gather the revenue from the public users. For example, the national highway project which is contracted by the NHAI under the PPP manner where the company uses this BOT type to finance the entire project appropriately, built the highway, obtains the profit and revenue and transfers the amount to the government as the private company work ends with this. The revenues which have been earned through the project undergo operational costs, proper maintenance of the project and financing cost of overall project.

Similarly, Jin, Liu and Udawatta (2019) has stated that BOT type has the main purpose of using this method in large projects where the government allows the private companies to have a concession. Through the concession they can generate the appropriate profits easily and also can provide the different advantages of using the BOT type. The model is a short setup time kind of method where the private company which is having the contract of the large and long-term project can easily save up their time and efforts in the building using their own entire team. Moreover, it is easy for them to focus on the building using different strategies which will surely improve the business and encourages it to grow.

Additionally, it enables the company to share the knowledge and resources where they can be able to learn from different service providers and set up their entire team. Equally, they can also take the benefit by sharing the resources they use during the building and operations of the project. However, using the BOT effectively benefits the company by reducing the burden of documentary requirements. The documents can be done by the service provider on behalf of the company and can provide the definite result and outcome.

Alternatively, Sheth (2019) has argued that not only BOT is used in managing the large segment projects but, the DBFO variant is also used by the companies to effectively provide results to the public. The term DBFO simply refers as design, build, finance and operate where the private organisation takes up responsibilities to perform all these arrangements appropriately. For many companies there is a belief that the DBFO arrangement transfers rights to the private sectors, which gives them autonomy to operate. Thus, the overall responsibility and sponsorship of the project is over the private sector. The most common source of this project is through toll collection. In this type, the contractor has a duty to design, construct, facilities management and financing of the entire project which operates for a longer period.

In the design stage, the company must keep focus on client requirements so that they have to carefully understand and perform quality work. In general, this is a great risk given to the contractor, which is in most cases reflected in their charges. By giving an opportunity to the private companies to design, provides benefits to the company. This enables it to understand and update the fundamental infrastructural requirements of the project, which can

successfully meet the demands of the public. Fundamentally, this helps the private company not feel the financial burden of the government and can conduct the entire project on its own successfully.

Palcic, Reeves and Siemiatycki (2019) have stated that using the DBFO model is very effective and beneficial for the private companies. It facilitates companies to construct the project by themselves without any restriction and pressure of the governance. This also makes them able to put their best efforts in the designing of the project and can easily operate the capital from the project.

There are a number of advantages the private sector can adopt from using the DBFO model. The private sectors who are having the longer period contracts for a project can save their time on budgeting and can provide well-organized results. The private sector also can minimize the cost of the infrastructure by avoiding high fees that can result in public discontent. The involvement of the private sector in a project also helps to spread innovative ideas in project design to the public. Using this model can bring the new ideologies where the company can be able to provide effective results.

However, this has been criticized by Rahmah, Sari, Saraswati and Fatimah (2020) who argue in favor of the Build Own and Operate (BOO) variant, that is more effective and appropriate for the projects where the private company and public sectors can obtain the fruitful results and outcomes. Although the term BOO refers as Build Own and Operate, it simply represents a mechanism in which a government sector partly sells to a private sector to allow them to construct the project according to the agreed design. It also allows the private sector to operate the project within particular time. In other words, the private sector will have control over the profits and margins. This model is also used for the complex and large government infrastructural projects.

The government allows the private company to finance the entire project and build, operate the entire project successfully. Giving opportunities to the private sector to construct and operate projects on its own within a particular period helps them to obtain more projects. Such contracts from government facilitate private companies to put their innovative ideas in practice making the project successful.

This model is used for high dollar projects where the expertise and specialization are required to make the project successful. The BOO type is mainly used in water related projects. Francis, Achi and Nwosu (2020) have stated that the BOO form is quite excellent for the private and government agencies because it provides advantages to the public and companies. More specifically, it encourages the private sector to identify areas where the project can be able to become successful and can provide the beneficial results.

PPP ventures enable governments to undertake multiple projects, which can be constructed with effective results and revenue from the users. The BOO form covers all stages of project cycle leading to higher profits for both parties. Designing projects on their own helps them to reduce the risks, financial and government pressure so that they can complete the project successfully. The private sector brings expertise and technology into the project enabling the project to progress faster.

Overall, using the PPP models helps the public sector to get the appropriate outcomes from where they can easily use them and obtain the benefits.

2.4 Roles and responsibilities of PPP institutions

According to the World Bank (2009), the success of PPP projects is dependent on their institutionalization as partners with the government. Thus, the government's role is that of a key partner to any PPP venture; as with any key policy change or intervention, governments should have an institutional plan to ensure that change happens. In other words, PPP does not just occur, private stakeholders' partner with governments and establish a clear recognised pathway for institutional partnership. In this situation, there are two key institutional roles to consider in PPP ventures.

- The first role is private sector institutions to support development and project implementation.
- The second role is that of public sector institutions participating in the PPP project to manage its transition from provision of goods and services to the role of contracting and monitoring.

Regarding private sector concerns, service delivery changes from limited involvement to complete partner in service delivery. It is also assumed that all the related financial and management risks occur. This implies that their inclusion and responsibility levels increase and consequently, the institutionalisation of the development becomes a requirement to ensure outcomes by avoiding disappointment.

As for the public sector, once PPP is utilised as a policy instrument, the initial responsibility of the government agencies which formerly was directly offering the service should change.

According to the World Bank (2009), the proper way to describe clear PPP institutional roles and responsibilities is to create a designated unit or team within government. For example, this can be in the Ministry of Finance that clearly connects to the local government as well as the private investors. For instance, such departments or PPP units operate worldwide especially at national level like the Ireland's Central PPP Policy Unit and South Africa's National Treasury PPP Unit. Some departments operate at provincial level or as local government agencies such as Partnerships Victoria in Australia, and the Gujarat Infrastructure Development Board in India (World Bank, 2009). Examples of the roles of the PPP Units include conducting financial or economic feasibility studies to establish whether PPP projects are financially viable. Another function of the PPP unit is to coordinate with different departments to determine whether the scheme is significant for the government and the PPP Unit has the advantage of an "arm's length" standpoint.

In addition, the PPP Unit acts as a centre of knowledge for various government departments in the identification, organisation, and implementation of feasible PPP projects.

Conversely, the World Bank (2019) states that one of the key reasons for Public Private Partnership is to reduce bureaucracy in public service delivery despite, appearing unpleasant to governments. This is especially, important in developing economies where the government maturity and its suitable policy, legal, supervisory and institutional programs and appropriate local capacity (human, financial and institutional) is not the best. PPP as a collaboration between the private company and the public agency is used to finance, establish and operate projects for instance, transportation networks, convention centers and parks.

The success of PPP projects is based on the funding, which allows project managers to complete big government projects effectively at a right time. Project managers can obtain

tax concessions and other operational revenues. Furthermore, Keers and van Fenema (2018) have stated that, PPP permits large scale public projects to be accomplished using private funding.

Their role is to offer funding for government projects in order to benefit local people. That's why it is called Public Private Partnership since there is resource sharing between private and public agencies. For instance, private sector companies provide technology and innovation while public sector agencies offer incentives which enables project managers to complete public ventures such as road construction, parks among others within the specified budget and time.

In addition, Public Private Partnership are based on agreement or contract, which guards them against lawsuits and enables them to perform different tasks efficiently. PPP contract is usually made between 25-30 years or more. Therefore, private sector companies in the partnership are accountable for project design, funding and implementation whereas public sector is accountable for monitoring laws and compliance with project objectives. Equal distribution and sharing of risks between the parties involved makes it easier in assignment of roles, responsibilities, disagreements and arguments are addressed through negotiations.

Shahbaz, et.al. (2020) noted that governments require commitment and skills which can be contributed by the private sector, which results into an effective partnership that assists the local people to gain from complete public projects effectively. In addition, the combined role of PPP is to create representation in the economy through making countries competitive and on facilitating infrastructure. The funding, partnership plus shared innovative ideas enhance their businesses through infrastructure development. Partnership projects primarily help local people to improve on their economic conditions, business growth and development.

Through providing employment opportunities connected to public projects, PPP can contribute to improved economic conditions and provide innovative ideas and technologies. The partnership between public and private sectors creates incentives by making projects time bound, successful and cost-effective. Thus, Public-Private Sector partnership is

responsible for delivering cost effective projects in a timely manner and improving on the project quality and operational efficiency respectively.

Generally, PPPs play a big role in increasing availability of infrastructure services for the people which would have been achieved by using traditional public sector approach. PPP allows access to substantial financial resources of the private sector. It also permits the public sector to benefit from the private sector expertise associated with technology, efficiency and experience. Consequently, PPP enables public sector to transfer project related risks to the private sector. Private sector partnership is accountable to the significant portion of the associated project risks.

During project life operations, public sector also performs a vital role on monitoring the performance of private partner and contract enforcement. Payment of public sector is based on performance standards specified in the contract signed by both parties. In general, private sector as compared to the public sector plays key roles and contributes to innovation, capital-cost and technologies. Warsen, et.al. (2018) argued that PPP largely focus on outputs like infrastructure services but not infrastructures resources. The main reason of concentrating on infrastructure services rather than infrastructure resources or assets is to encourage effective use of public resources and to improve the quality of infrastructure services.

Through contractual agreement between the parties, the partnership brings both public and private companies together for about 30 years and this period is pre-defined by the two parties. Private partners for instance investors, operators as well as contractors are responsible for offering particular infrastructure facilities and in return, the public sector perform their role of paying grants via generated revenue from the private sector projects. Since the private partner plays a big role, they have a right to cause changes in users' fee and also receive revenue generated from the projects. The best PPP is where the public and private partners work together to maintain long term relationship to benefit both parties. Additionally, one of the best ways to explore private sector innovation, technology and experience with the aim of offering better quality public services is by improving operational efficacy. As compared to the public sector, private sector employees need to work hard to

achieve project goals and earn money since they have knowledge, experience, plus innovative ideas.

Cui, Liu, Hope and Wang, (2018) stated that the roles and responsibilities of public private partnership agencies bridges the gap between demand and supply of funds for infrastructure development projects. It offers much required experience, innovation, creativity, management proficiency and operational capability. PPP also plays a vibrant role in tourism development planning as well. PPP allows governments of various countries to spearhead development of the tourism industry in line with government priorities basing on the social and environmental standards. Applying PPP is among one of the effective ways of improving local private sector competences through joint venture with big international companies. PPP is appropriate for large development ventures and mostly, it is applicable in areas of civil work, security services and it enables service management and maintenance. It is a means of exposing state-owned initiatives to intensify private sector involvement. PPP ensures skills transfer and allows exportation of competences and expertise through bidding for the projects. Private sector also attracts the public sector to share its inadequate capacities to meet growing demand for infrastructure development for instance equipment and construction.

Singh (2020) highlighted the roles and responsibilities of PPP institutions with effective and positive stories of partnership in various countries. For example, in Indonesia, India and Rwanda, a number of successful projects were developed. In India, public-private sector partnership has led to quick and cost-effective projects in several sectors like infrastructure, technology and power. By providing opportunities to the private sector, PPP benefit people in the developing and developed countries. In addition, through increased employment opportunities, PPP can improve people's living standards and quality of life. Successful completion of the public sector projects attracts travelers from foreign countries and the travelers are the key sources of foreign exchange revenue and economic development. Furthermore, in India, PPP are of great value for taxpayers since they are benefiting from the impacts of such ventures. This PPP has resulted into reducing capacity constraints of the economy by creating productivity through optimal use of capital resources plus labor.

Therefore, the partnership between the government and leading companies have been effective in India by creating jobs and raising employment opportunities, leading to economic development of the country. The Indian government regulates partnership related projects and ensures accountability and delivery of better-quality products and services. In addition, the PPP agencies specify that any kind of partnership can be successful only if it takes into consideration satisfaction of the needs of people and is approved by the public private partnership including ensuring the value for money. Globally, PPP has contributed to the growth and development of economies for instance the Indian economy in different and it enables the counties to compete others. People get employment opportunities and by combining professionalism and corporate social responsibility with the welfare objectives of state, projects like Mumbai airport were established and It is well known for its advanced quality facilities and amenities.

Calabrò and Della Spina (2019) also noted that, PPPs assist participating employees and local people in sharing technologies, capabilities, creativity, innovative ideas and funding. In addition, by performing various roles and responsibilities, PPP can solve all problems experienced by the local people and employees including but not limited to the following: unemployment; poor product quality, and inadequate teamwork. Thus, the Public Private Partnership agencies should focus on developing several public projects to improve on people's living standards. The role of private sector partnership agencies has enabled the public sector to run and complete public projects successfully as it shares capabilities, experiences, and technological knowledge among the partners involved.

PPP agencies also share the risks that might occur while implementing or completing the projects, and it is found that the amount invested in project development can get in either half of it or full portion of project's services. Consequently, basing on the roles performed by both Private and Public sector agencies, it can be noted that, private sector agencies play a vital role compared to the public sector. So, it can be recommended that the public sector

should focus on contributing to innovation and creative ideas so as to cooperate equally in the partnership and improve on the general quality of public projects.

2.5 Impact of Private Sector components on the economy

According to Gründler and Potrafke (2019), the private sector refers to the component of the economy without any control by the state and can run its businesses and organization efficiently. The company can be managed by an individual person, and he/she has right to make decisions independently without taking advice and or permission from the government. The private sectors play an important role in both rural and urban areas from where it directly makes an impact on the economy of the particular country. Nevertheless, the private sector is expected to collaborate with the government in public-private partnership jointly to deliver services to the community appropriately and successfully. Private sector has been able to stabilize the prices by creating fair market conditions and can obtain effective results.

The private sector components impact on the economy, for instance a sole proprietor puts their best efforts in making the company grow and develop effectively. An individual proprietor pays fewer taxes at lower rates compared to the cooperation.

The income taxes contribute to government revenues and helps the economy to grow whereas the private sector component contributes great and huge impact on the economy. Sethi and Acharya (2018) stated that, not only the sole proprietor contributes to the county's growth but there are different forms of private sector components putting the best efforts in the development of the economy.

The partnership business also contributes efforts which impacts on the development of the economy of the specific country. In partnership business, more than one person is involved, and they are responsible for taking decisions of the company and the profits and losses are equally divided between the partners. The partnership business impacts are greatly on the since availability of resources is more than that of the sole proprietor. Partnerships increases revenue collections and enables payment of taxes accordingly which impacts positively on the country's development.

Ozcan and Ozturk (2019) argued that PPPs impact on the growth of the economy as economic growth is generally seen in terms of investment and increase in production outputs. The PPP companies provide better economic growth to the country through development projects like construction of infrastructure (highways, roads, and bridges) using appropriate technology and innovativeness. There are different sorts of areas where the public-private partnership successfully contributes to the country's economic growth for instance the trade unions. Trade in exports and imports of goods and services happens between two or more countries and helps in innovative ways and provide opportunities to the people by obtaining higher incomes as well as accelerating the growth of the economy.

According to Sobiech (2019), private sectors contribute their best efforts in making the economy develop successfully over the time by focusing mainly on the public needs and services. PPP focus on consumer expectations or desires and provide them with fruitful results. Consumers might be able to afford the products and services as the private sector keep the margins accordingly and provide the affordable products or service depending on the demand of the product in the society thereby impacting on economic growth. In addition, private sector creates employment opportunities to the country's population which also impacts positively on the country's economic growth and development.

Soecipto and Verhoest (2018) point out that private sector is the main engine of growth. Successful private sector businesses drive growth, create jobs, and improve employment conditions. By getting employment opportunities, employees improve on their economic condition in the country, and this increases cash inflow in the market as employees are facilitated or paid salaries. The cash inflow and outflow are important for improving the economic conditions of the people in the country.

Calabrò and Della Spina (2019) stated that, as compared to the public sector, private sector heavily liaises with public sector agencies to complete projects in a successful manner. In addition, PPPs work well only when private sector innovative ideas and technology combine

with public sector incentives for completing projects within specified time and budget. Public and private parties share resources such as labor, financing, and management, skills and technologies which permits completion of public projects. Furthermore, PPP are natural extension of mixed economic systems, and such partnership make it possible for individual workers to command a higher value for their labor and achieve high value of standards (Calabrò and Della Spina, 2019). Employees under private sector strive hard to complete the projects effectively and are given incentives which allows them to invest in essential needs thus increasing the cash flow in the market and this cash inflow is a sign of economic development.

Through improvement in economic conditions, countries make themselves competitive. Countries applying PPP have made tremendous growth and they are now competing with developed countries for example, India is one of the fast-growing economies.

Private sector work has led to reduction in poverty through improved standards of living of the people and employment opportunities for them especially among the local people. Public Private Partnership aim at increasing access to services or infrastructure at reduced or affordable prices. PPP provides benefits to the local people, countries, and government through improving people's economic conditions. Spraul and Thaler, (2020) argued that almost 35-40% of the population in India does not have access to electricity and good quality roads. Thus, PPP need to focus on developing countries rather than developed countries.

Globally, PPP is famous in India, UK, South Africa and Australia and other developed countries where it has developed projects successfully which has improved the countries' economic condition through providing employment opportunities to people.

In the UK, PPP programs developed and became one of the largest projects in the country. Transport is one of the key sectors PPP has invested a lot and through such big projects, the government and the citizens benefited from the various partnership projects. Wojewnik-Filipkowska and Węgrzyn (2019) stated that, there are a number of features associated with partnership competence and some projects may not be suitable for PPP. For instance, the UK environment is favorable for PPP projects and that is why it has developed one of the biggest

PPP projects. PPP is a complex organization that works on big projects with support from both the public and private companies at the time of operation and development.

Based on the above context, it can be said that both private and public sector agencies are responsible for improving economic conditions because both play their allotted roles, and responsibilities. PPPs assist in meeting financial demand from its revenue or taxes. In addition, it can also be said that a number of people get employment opportunities from PPP projects and improve their living standards. Developments in infrastructure helps project managers in improving economic condition as it creates jobs and provides employment opportunities to people and improves their living condition.

From the above, we can see that there is enough evidence affirming the positive contributions of PPPs. Projects initiated in developing countries have improved living conditions of inhabitants which has consequently led to improved economic conditions. It is known that people of India are now able to live a better quality of life, and it is making them feel valued. An improved infrastructure with the help of creative and innovative ideas has made this innovation possible.

2.5.1 Case of Indonesia

According to ISDIJOSO (2021), successful PPP strategies have been used in Indonesia for over 15 years. Indonesia has made significant progress in developing PPP for instance, 24 PPP contracts have been signed with a total investment value of about \$16.87 billion equal to 246.38 trillion Indonesian Rupiah. The contribution in terms of knowledge and financial resources from respective donors such as the PPP infrastructure advisory facility (PPIAF) is one of the key factors that helped Indonesia to succeed. Moreover, ISDIJOSO (2021) argue that although the current situation is unfavourable due to COVID-19 pandemic, infrastructure can help solve two of the main problems: It could spur Indonesia's economic recovery (post-pandemic), and it could be a vehicle for avoiding the "middle-income trap" in the medium and long term; The G20 Forum agrees that, infrastructure investment can help developing countries to cope up with the health and economic impacts of the pandemic (ISDIJOSO, 2021). Some of the 5 strategies used by Indonesia to turn around their PPP program include:

Establishment of the legal framework with the outreach of stakeholders; Establishment of a high-level de-bottlenecking committee; Establishment financing support for PPP; Having a dedicated PPP unit; and Working with all development partners to participate and support their vision.

Indonesia has come to understand that addressing infrastructure needs of their country cannot be solved with a one-way solution and it was necessary to collaborate with key stakeholders especially the private sector (ISDIJOSO, 2021). The support the country received, from other development partners has been critical in helping them to reach their goal. Indonesia is aiming at obtaining over \$183 billion (2,700 trillion Indonesian rupiah) or 42% from total infrastructure investment necessities from private investors between 2020 to 2022 (ISDIJOSO, 2021). Furthermore, according to Ma, et.al. (2019) economic growth in Indonesia suddenly began to increase since the crisis in economy struck in the year 1990. According to recent data, 2015 to 2018 Indonesia's economic growth had experienced a good increase.

For economic growth to increase, the economy needs to have adequate infrastructure and having a proper discussion on the growth of the economy, the government of Indonesia has realized the necessity to properly focus on the role of the private sector in meeting infrastructure needs. Through this discussion, the PPP was widely used to bridge the gaps in the infrastructure project development globally. Countries believed that PPPs will allow an individual to get different opportunities in the general project contract. In 1990s, PPP was an innovation in private companies and were responsible for financing the quality infrastructure project developments.

In Indonesia, the PPP has been implemented since 1997 to 1998 with the construction of new roads. The toll road industry had a positive outlook with strong demand for constructing new roads for transportation services. The reason behind building new toll roads was to reduce traffic in urban areas. Indonesia started to undertake such projects and out of 22 projects contracted through PPP scheme only 8 have been offered tender.

According to Yu, Chan, et.al, (2018), PPP is a long-term contract between private and public institutions with skills and abilities to undertake various roles, responsibilities and risk management for the development of public facilities. Construction of the toll roads in Indonesia as a public facility, the government and private sector decided to create valid planned goals, and joint investment. The toll road development started in 1978 where state owned enterprise such as PT Jasa was an operator and regulator of the toll roads. The government of Indonesia has invited private sectors to participate in toll roads by using the BOT model or scheme which was beneficial for both parties for the success of projects. On the other hand, Soemitro and Suprayitno (2020) noted that, besides the toll road project, the water supply was successful through PPP's proper management of the water supply. The water service project was also successful with implementation of proper legal frameworks.

The Indonesia PPP project was successful due to different factors for instance, governance competence, appropriate concessions, risk sharing between parties and a proper financial package. Thus, PPP projects have been successfully implemented in Indonesia as a result of various factors.

Therefore, this research will adopt Indonesia's strategy in implementation and application of successful PPP in Rwanda through collaboration with the space technologies to achieve sustainable development of the country.

2.5.2 Case of Vietnam

PPP projects' (e.g. roads, hospitals and schools) success or failure depends on various factors. According to Le, Kirytopoulos, Chileshe and Rameezdeen (2019), proper infrastructure of the country encourages economic growth. There are different kinds of models that have been utilised by Vietnam in PPP such as BOT, BTO and BO models in PPP projects. Despite the involvement of many foreign companies in Vietnam PPPs, its companies are dominated by BOT, BTO projects. Political, economic, and social factors impact on the relationship between the public and private sectors to operate together. Vietnam has faced difficulties and financial challenges for the infrastructure development, which are needed for effective implementation of larger PPP projects.

Public-Private Partnership projects have been developed and implemented previously in different countries like Vietnam to provide better facilities for the public. In addition, Xiao and Lam (2020) stated that a suitable and appropriate policy and legal framework is the reason behind successful implementation of the PPP. In order to deliver the PPP projects successfully and effectively, Vietnam governance has decided to establish an appropriate legal structure to expand public infrastructural facilities where local and external investors acquire reasonable return. The term, PPP is generally defined as Law on Investment 2014, where the contracts in form of PPP between the state or government, an investor and a project company implement the project accurately. Adequate establishment of the legal framework reduces misunderstandings and risk factors in dealing with the failure of the PPP project.

A legal framework for the operations of PPP is critical for the success of projects as laws should be followed for effective results or outcomes. Chon, Roffe, et.al, (2018) stated that, whenever it comes to Vietnam becoming a competitive destination for huge investment, achieving full economic potential is through PPP projects. The focus is on the PPP projects to encourage and foster infrastructural development projects under the PPP arrangement to obtain positive results.

Over the years, Vietnam's competitiveness has been supporting the MPI to develop the government relationship with the PPP projects. MPI supports the PPP investors and central governance in handling roads and ports like projects. Vietnam has started to experience rapid growth through infrastructure development and investment. New roads, bridges, ports, water and power services are required to have a definite growth since the year 2020. The Vietnam government didn't have enough resources to finance the mentioned projects. PPP is the only alternative to save the country from taking loans from banks and also provide funds for the infrastructure projects. Not only the private sector has to contribute financial resources, but also have skills and expertise needed to support infrastructure projects and the government of Vietnam should be able to learn from PPP markets.

2.5.3 Case of United Kingdom

Regarding the United Kingdom, PPP programs largely operate in the country's transport sector. The UK Transportation Sector is one of the key sectors operating under PPP and a lot of resources have been invested in such big projects. The citizens of this country have

benefited highly from such projects. PPP increases cash inflow in the market and result into improved economic conditions. In addition, Wojewnik-Filipkowska and Węgrzyn, (2019) highlighted that, there are several activities or features carried out in any partnership. Some features make partnership projects competent while others are not suitable for supporting PPP. The UK Environment is favorable for PPP's projects and that's why it has developed and is, recognized as one of the biggest projects for improving economic conditions. PPP is a complex organization that works on big projects and needs support from both public and private companies for operation and development.

Therefore, based on the above, both private and public sector agencies are responsible for improving economic conditions because both play their respective allotted work, responsibilities, and roles. PPP assist to meet financial demand from its revenue or taxes. The private sector partnership thrives with the aim boosting the economy through growth and development. Effective and efficient PPP can deliver investments, developments and services that are essential in boosting UK economic growth and recovery (Local Government Association, 2022).

Thus, "unprecedented actions such as protecting the vulnerable, mass-testing, the nation-wide rollout of the vaccine, distribution of business, support grants, and the establishment of recovery taskforce demonstrate what can be achieved through strong partnerships between the public and private sectors" (Local Government Association, 2022). The Local Government Association, UK also observed that whilst public-private partnerships (PPP) are able to deliver without their controversy, robust and well-coordinated partnerships present opportunities to bring together resources, expertise, and powers which may not be achieved in isolation or by one sector.

Moreover, councils in UK are now exploring how investment can unlock a range of social, environmental, and economic benefits in line with the local and national priorities. Partnership create direction with practical focus on insights from practitioners, councils, and special interest group to capture key challenges, barriers and opportunities that exist in establishing and running of successful partnerships.

Drawing from practical experiences in UK and elsewhere in the world, partnership has been useful when public and private sector came together to seek solutions to end Covid 19

pandemic by putting together the resources, manufacturing face masks, hand sanitiser and providing the vaccine. Moreover, to address key investment criteria in identifying potential overseas investors, it is important to consider investment in regional settings, including transport, skills, real estate availability and local business support.

These initiatives shape organisations by focusing on how approaches are used or can be improved, how risks can be mitigated, and how best practices can support resilience and effective interventions.

2.6 Discussing the Role of PPP in Rwanda

According to UNCHS Habitat, (2000), the role of PPP in developed countries is to improve service delivery and value for money while in developing countries including Rwanda, the motive is to generate revenue since PPPs are considered as a key solution for generating revenue. However, Gasana (2008) observed that reconciling the two aspects could be problematic due to the absence of an appropriate framework. According to Nzimimakwe, (2006), Rwanda has a political will to make PPP a success story especially in social and economic sectors particularly in education, health, transport, agriculture, and energy.

Thus, in 2008, the Government of Rwanda (GoR) initiated PPP projects and declared them as procurement options in the National Public Investment Policy (NPIP). This informed the government to continue focusing on the roles of PPP and the expected collaboration with private sector development in Rwanda. The Government further highlighted various challenges encountered by PPPs whilst playing the role of improving public services and offering genuine value for money (Rwanda PPP Handbook, 2016). The flow of funds from private sector especially donors to the public sector would help in the reduction of the burden on government.

There have been arguments that Rwanda does not have PPPs that what actual exists are just fair concessions given to some investors in the key areas (Nuwagaba, 2013). But this argument

was nullified by World Bank, PPIAF and IFC Report, (2005) and Delmon (2008) with clarity on classified concessions as one of the major types of PPPs. This clarified the fact that Rwanda is practising some kind of PPP in form of concessions/ However, some PPP projects are not suitable for concession type of contracting out thus a challenge to the implementation of a fully developed PPP.

Nevertheless, the Rwandan government in 2015 passed the first law to establish the legal context on guidelines for contracts between PPP and the Government (Pic, 2017). In addition, Rwanda has fast growing development needs that are essential to make further efforts to prevent the sub-optimal requests of the limited resources. The priority areas of PPP investments are identified in Rwanda's Economic Development and Poverty Reduction Strategy (EDPRS), and they include: the national road networks; the transport sector in general; the ICT sector; the energy sector; the urban and rural settlement programs; the water services; and the sanitation services.

According to MINCOM (2008), a considerable investment in any infrastructure can reduce corporate costs by refining the quality and quantity of energy supplied to urban and rural areas while improving the transport networks. These may entail roads, building bridges, expanding airports and regional railways, increasing ICT capacities both in provision and utilisation, improving existing water structure for irrigation and washing stations (MINCOM, 2008).

Although, there are different types of PPPs, there is little or no evidence to indicate the associated merits of one or any form of PPPs in the context of developing countries such as Rwanda. Therefore, in Rwanda, the coverage and extent of the services for any potential PPP, requires the provision of quality services under the existing PPP arrangements but with the operational constraints, and other effects on stakeholders are not empirically known.

Hence, Rwanda relies on the institutional capacity of the government to design, negotiate, implement, and monitor partnerships. The Government of Rwanda has recognised the above

challenges and enacted a Law N°14/2016 of 02/05/2016 for governing PPPs in Rwanda. Thus, the Law requires Rwanda development Board (RDB) to issue general guidelines for procurement of PPP and advise the government on matters related to PPP (Nkusi, 2016). There is a lack of appropriate legal framework on PPP implementation in services for instance infrastructure sector (Nkusi, 2016). Gubic and Baloi, (2019) noted that Rwanda is on the outgrowth of the key regional areas where the country is a prominent member of the East African Community. Rwanda has one of the fastest growing GDP in the whole world it attracts market through effective Public-Private Partnership.

In 2015, the government of Rwanda passed the first law of launching the rules and regulations for the future contracts between the private sector and government agencies. It has been already acknowledged that PPP is a kind of contract between private and public sector, and both are responsible for managing the risks, finance, designing, construction, rehabilitation, and a proper maintenance of the infrastructure property. There are different roles and responsibilities of Rwanda Department Board (RDB) to ensure effective results and success of the PPP projects. In general, PPP has been adopted for infrastructure development projects to enable the private sector to finance the projects so as to benefit the public and achieve economic development and growth.

RDB (Rwanda Development Board) is a government institution which has been established to achieve economic development through private sector development. Engagement of PPP contracts in Rwanda is one of the significant factors for growth and development of the economy. Using different kinds of models for PPP, contractors must ensure effectiveness in the entire project design, planning, implementation, and monitoring. For instance, Yongabo and Göktepe-Hultén, (2021) argued that the energy infrastructure project is a key opportunity for the PPP in Rwanda and is a priority area for improving electricity services. For example, sometimes there are short-term electricity outages in some areas of the country and the government is improving its efforts to enhance the services. To reduce electricity costs, proper cooperation is necessary from policymakers to change the financial feasibility of electricity.

Rwanda needs to explore new energy saving innovations projects which are not expensive. One of the largest hydroelectric projects is developed by Contour global (Kivu-Watt). Rwanda is trying to develop hydroelectric projects through PPP contracts. Rwanda explored energy projects like hydro-electricity power as an alternative source of energy. The creation of an appropriate legal and policy framework helped Rwanda to conduct PPP projects successfully and has an influence on economic growth and development.

Haque and Rashid, (2019) argued that transportation infrastructure is the most important and sensitive project in Rwanda with a focus on PPP contracts. Building of roads led Rwandan investment fund to construct quality roads. Construction of roads also give opportunities for jobs to Rwandan citizens and achievement of the country's development goals. The construction of the roads and highways through PPP contracts gives the private sector a right to design, fund and build infrastructure projects accordingly. Transportation also includes railways, airports, bridges, tunnels, and waterways and proper budgeting is required to be done to avoid misunderstandings. PPP is needed to provide adequate infrastructure services and foster economic growth and development.

Izuwah, (2019) noted that, the rapid growing population of Kigali requires Rwanda to put more efforts for better infrastructure development services. For instance, the contract has been taken under PPP for Bulk water project to ensure access to safe and clean and water. The government was committed to improve water services and supply, aiming at 100% coverage in Kigali by 2028. To meet the target of the supply services, the government of the Rwanda develops new water source with the public-private partnership. Later on, the government of the Rwanda retained the advisor to develop the bulk water supply PPP project.

The government of Rwanda has adopted the structure (model) of PPP using the BOT arrangement (build-operate-transfer) where private sectors have major responsibilities to finance, construct, design and operate projects. Also, PPP had to keep proper maintenance

of the water supply and production. Having the public-private partnership arrangement, the water supply project increase by in Kigali by 40%.

According to Rurangwa, Kinyanjui, et.al., (2018), economic development in Rwanda is still necessary and community need to develop themselves. Building of the infrastructure such as parks is required and need to be maintained properly through public-private partnership to benefit the county. Designing, financing, building, and operating PPP projects is the best model and structure of governance. Therefore, this justifies the need for proposed research to inform government and other stakeholders for improved and efficient best practices or frameworks that can help in capacity building and production based on the PPP in different sectors in Rwanda.

2.7 Risks associated with PPP projects

Public private partnerships play a vital role in contributing to positive impact on the local people and economic development. For instance, PPP provides employment opportunities and help people to earn incomes through quality infrastructure quality and contributes to the development of the economy. However, public private partnership is not risk-free as it entails a number of risks associated with such projects.

According to Marzoukand El-Hesnawi, (2018), PESTLE key factors (Political, Economic, Sociological, Technological, Legal and Environmental) are some of the risks that are associated with PPP. It includes political changes, economic changes risks, technical changes risks, environmental changes such as climate change. These risks create barriers for successful completion of public projects. Additionally, changes in the needs of people and high demand, increasing tax rates and other legislations can also create pressure on PPP agency.

In addition, the PESTLE, STEEPLE, INSPEECT are some of the risks associated with such projects. It includes pestle factors as well as international, demographic, ethics, communication, and operational risks. All these risks affect the quality of public projects being developed by PPP and it is important for the organisation to focus on mitigating the risks so that it can accomplish its set goals and benefit the society. Sanda, et.al., (2020) argued that

the above-mentioned risks are external and there are some common internal risks that may occur anytime and can affect the quality of projects.

Some of the internal risks associated with public private partnership include operational risks, finance risks, construction, and relationship, legal, regulatory and sustainable risks. Regarding finance cost for preparing roads and other public projects, there is requirement for bidding and ongoing cost. PPP finance costs are likely to be greater than traditional government procurement process. The cost is attached to debt, but private sector companies have capability to finance the project effectively. Some projects may be easily financed than others and this occurs when the agency complete all legislation formalities, and the technology must be clear. So, risks are associated with PPP projects can be reduced through proper innovation and monitoring.

Furthermore, if both private and public sectors perform their roles in an ethical manner, then the risks can be mitigated. But still, the private sector is the one responsible for risks involved while completing projects under public private partnership. In addition, the private sector is cautious about accepting major risks beyond their control such as risks of existing assets, exchange rate and others. Government is also responsible for managing risks since citizens expect government to build high quality projects otherwise, it may affect their image and reputation in the market. Private sector as compared to public sector is considered as more experienced and capable. Consequently, the government focuses on retaining sufficient expertise. It monitors performance of the private sector and make sure everyone is working as per the set performance matrix according to the rules and regulations.

Keers and Van Fenema (2018) stated that, public projects that come under public private partnership are long term in nature as such projects require too much of time for completion. So, it becomes difficult for private sector to identify all possible contingencies at the time of project development. In addition, some projects may fail and may be terminated prior to the projected terms and conditions. Some reasons that make projects fail include changes in government policy, failure by the private operator and government to perform their obligations.

Some of these issues can be addressed in project management of PPP agreement. In most of the projects, it has been observed that the real project cost overrun the estimated cost of project due to some reasons including delays in submission of project, inefficient working, new tax rates and modification in governmental policies. It has also been noted that for the risks and failure, the private sector parties are blamed more than government parties. Project completion time is also associated with private sector parties because contractors are responsible for project completion.

If any delays happen, then private sector is blamed, and it increases pressure on them. It increases fear among them, and they are more likely to strive hard for accomplishing goals and completing projects as per the set criteria, budget and time. To reduce such risks, they need to focus on proper supervision to increase standard and quality of construction. Also, routine inspection by the public sector makes it easier for the private sector to mitigate all the risks.

Keers and van Fenema, (2018) supported the above view and stated that the design risk is also part of PPP's projects which may affect the overall quality of projects. This type of risk includes any risk or mistake in design specification or in the design structure element. If there is damage in structure element, then it becomes difficult to decide as whether damage is due to mistakes in designing parameters or design itself. Contractor is responsible for managing such risks as they need to make proper parameters so that they mitigate such risks. Project quality and success rely on this main element. If design of public project is not efficient, then it can affect negatively the image of both private and public parties, and they may find problems in producing such projects in the future. In addition, the environmental factors and specific environmental liability within project zone can also affect the quality of the project.

Therefore, both private and public parties need to make a proper planning before starting the projects, they need to take permission or approval of environmental authorities. This can also protect them against paying penalties as well as extra charges. Generally, there are number of risks associated with public private partnership projects.

2.8 The concept of Sustainable Development and PPPs

According to Toli and Murtagh (2020) sustainable development refers development that meets the needs of present without compromising needs of the future generations. It is important for organisations whether they are from private sector or public to focus on sustainability. There are three main pillars of sustainability by which people can develop: social, economic and environmental. In addition, it can be said that it is about change in all aspects of life like limiting needs for protecting natural resources and the environment for future generations. It can be facilitated by following 4-5 principles that ensure healthy and strong society, living within environmental limits, promoting good governance, and utilising information communication technology as a social responsibility.

Expanding the view above, Zore, Čuček and Kravanja, (2018) have stated that sustainable development is about using natural resources in a limited manner so that pollution can be decreased. Having positive impact on environment and people concerns sustainable development. For example, in the construction sector where constructors develop projects related to building roads, bridges, parks and others requires focusing on this concept. The construction sector produces waste to the great extent and for completing large scale projects. Controlling pollution in air, water and conserving biological diversity can improve image of construction companies. This can be done by improving sustainability, which results into positive impacts on societies and the environment.

PPPs develop public projects that can provide benefits to the public. Normally, these projects have wide scope and are run for long time. Yu et.al, (2018) have stated that PPPs are complex and require a number of skills that are usually found in private sector. There are number of factors that facilitate the success of PPPs projects. These factors entail coherent policy, legal framework, strong enabling institutions, transparency, putting people first and achieving sustainable development. In this regard, it can be said that if private and public sector parties do not focus on sustainability development then they cannot make projects effective and successful.

Deriving from this, it can clearly be stated that sustainability is important in PPPs projects. In addition, it can be said that one of the main principles of PPP's is putting people first, which

leads to sustainable development. Following this principle, it is important for private and public sector parties to define public interest, consult people, disclose information in contracts, involve and independent auditors.

It is through satisfying needs of people that sustainability is achieved, and the image of companies improved. Public and private partnership organisations need to choose between profit and social as well as environmental development. Although consideration of the two affects their profitability, they are still able to earn profit and to accomplish their goals in an effective manner.

Marx (2019), stated in this regard that public and private institutions are converging towards the achievement of development results. One of the sustainable development growth priorities is to facilitate convergence as well as leading to shared responsibilities in development changes. There are two main goals that public private partnership needs to focus on in achieving sustainable development. These will always include businesses and people and aligning public private partnership for sustainable development.

Deriving from experiences of MDG-F, PPPs contribute to achieving development capacity building, sustainable development goals and wealth distribution. It can be done by this organization if the focus on using resources in an effective and limited manner. If they make an effective planning as well as they facilitate discussion between public and private sector as well as civil society on specific development theme, then it can contribute to sustainable development. PPPs are known as tools for sustainability development because they contribute resources that contribute to economic growth and reduced levels of poverty. This helps to reduce the gap between the rich and the poor ultimately between rich and poor nations.

2.9 Sustainable Development and Space Technologies

Space technologies facilitate achievement of sustainable development by predicting solutions to the world challenges like climate change, disaster prevention, poverty, and agriculture development issues among others. Rwanda like other states, relies on new and existing technologies to respond to pandemics including tracking, tracing, controlling expansion of

viruses' using GPS, Arc GIS technologies in the distribution of vaccines. Space technologies accelerate sustainable development and benefit international research cooperation, which presents application of space science and technology for achieving SDGs (UN, 2019). Space technology also helps in monitoring natural resources, poverty reduction, health as well as improved communication.

Furthermore, space technologies also examine the impact of technological developments using space-based applications and collaboration with local, national, regional, and international stakeholders. They explore how the technologies can potentially increase success in achieving the SDGs particularly in developing countries. Space plays a vital role for sustainable development through use of resources for only peaceful purposes. Space technology contributes to socio-economic outcomes by protecting nature and other resources for the future generations. This is done through cooperation and discussion by ensuring that people are convinced of outer space benefits.

Expanding the same idea, Xu *et.al*, (2020) have stated that sustainable fuel is the top priority that can promote greener space travel. It was also found that for sustainable development to be attained, space crafts should use variety of fuels instead of only the dominant fossil fuels. There is a greener option that can be adopted by spacecraft for encouraging sustainable development such as oxygen and liquid hydrogen. These are being used by the new shepherd propulsion module from private spaceflight company blue origin. For this reason, it is one of the sustainable space technologies, and it has made it able to attract customers as well as improving the image.

Through space we are able to observe the earth, and it is a cost-effective way of obtaining unbiased data on the physical world. Decision makers find it easier to evaluate the needs and understanding of the trends by using all collected information through observation. Basing on this information, they can develop programs and policies to the best interest of population.

In addition, sustainable development is globally recognised as a symbol through which a number of sustainable development initiatives can re-brand themselves. Sustainable development Goals are compiled as a set of goals that can be achieved globally via effective cooperation between all United Nations member states and all stakeholders. In general, by ensuring space sustainability, all negative environmental impacts can be reduced.

Furthermore, Di Pippo (2019) stated that, there are number of goals that have been set by spaceships for ensuring sustainability. The 2020 Agenda aims at ensuring that development patterns lead to social inclusion and well-being. People are using effective space technologies and assets to support most of the goals. In regard to effectiveness and contribution of space, it is found that, space provides non-invasive tools with capacity for repeatable objective measures. To understand the importance of space for sustainable development, it is vital to understand reasons for sustainable development and how people have contributed to pollution and other negative environmental impacts. For instance, human activities like using vehicles and mismanagement of natural resources like water and other resources to the great extent have had an indisputable impact on the earth and environment.

Some negative impacts that human activities have on the environment include soil degradation, deforestation, and climate change. Space based technologies such as remotely sensed data have increased scientific understanding of water cycle. Different space-based tools are helping companies and people in reducing negative environmental impacts. Consequently, space technology has great impact on sustainable development. It can help the public private partners in completing their projects in a successful and effective manner. It can be beneficial for environment, local people, and boost growth and development of the economy. It can protect future generation as natural resources can be used in an effective manner.

2.10 Space supporting Sustainable Development with Spaceflight Technologies

According to Crusan *et.al.*, (2018), technologies emerge on a daily basis and offer many opportunities. Despite technological progress, there are many factors such as the societal challenges that are needed to be considered in order to cope up with the environment to achieve human development. UN involves the 190 members from different states with the 2030-year agenda to address the sustainability issues accounting all challenges in form of SDGs. UN has recognized the importance of the earth observation roles and geo-location to achieve development goals. Space based services and technologies are more efficient in order to develop the understanding about the climate.

Utilising space offers better contribution for the policy areas which also includes climate and weather monitoring services. Space also helps in providing various services such as easy access to education, healthcare and efficiencies in transportation. For the past years, spaceflight is becoming a main driver for the technological development in various fields like production of the electrical power and other systems. Human spaceflight mission mainly requires the rare resource which is oxygen resource, and it can further be distributed to the team so that the target can be achieved. However, the spaceflight technology usually involves high costs and there is also lack of immediate approval.

Additionally, some are arguing in regard to making the sustainable living on the earth. Living on earth and living in space are two distinct things which come with lots of challenges. Awareness for the requirement of sustainability is the biggest concern for several decades, but now it requires consideration on the urgency basis. Robinson and Mazzucato (2019) stated that, humanity is starting to realise that Earth's resources are not limitless, and utilization of Earth resources is creating challenges for the ecosystem. With the help of the spaceflight technology, dimensions can easily have influence on the lunar surface ecological aspect that need to be zero or nearby, because there is no ecology, and it has been found that it can be easily exploited.

Equally, for the Earth planet, it is important to conserve the resources rather than exploiting it. For instance, it is found that potable water on the Earth is limited in some areas, it is estimated that, around 2 billion people are not able to access safe drinking water (they haven't seen clean drinking water). With the help of technology, sanitation can be improved as well as ensuring easy access to clean water. Furukawa et.al, (2020) stated that, lead users are the individual experts who efficiently participate in the innovation process as they support the scientists, developers, and engineers to make the innovation. Spaceflights and the human spaceflights mainly present the lead user situation. Here the requirements are concerned with the autonomy, performance, robustness, and radiation hardness that are mainly exceeding other terrestrial applications because of the vulnerable space environment.

Moreover, cost is also linked with the space mission, and it also entails the fact that, human life is depending on the flawless operation of the technical elements. There are many countries which are financially investing in space environment thus making the whole world to rely on the space. UNOOSA is upholding the United Nations to increase the utilization of

space technology to reduce chances for the disaster risks. Also, emergency services are introduced in order to cope up with the damages and to prevent human lives and property from danger.

Since the aim of the study is to examine the contributions of PPPs to agricultural productivity and sustainable development, this section discusses the theories on how PPPs technologies contribute to economic growth and sustainable development.

2.11 Theoretical Structure of PPP's and Sustainable Development

According to sustainable development, the PPP concept is dependent on the three factors for instance economic, social and environmental aspects. It is highly able to influence on the future discourse regarding development of science. This implies that within the best choices which are likely to meet the needs of the society, including being economically and environmentally viable for equitable and sustainable development. This leads to three interconnected spheres for sustainability that demonstrate the relationship between the environmental, social and economic aspects.

Based on the comprehensive evaluation, it has been summarized that every business has specific plans which automatically have implications on the economy, environment, and the society and should continue to exist for the wellbeing of human beings. The human decisions and actions are highly based on such aspects, and they are extremely interrelated to each other. The data depicts the proper decisions on sustainable resource use and management for sustainable development of the society (Ma and et.al. (2020). It comprises various examples such as land, surface water management, building, designing and construction, energy management, and education among others. Sustainable development emphasizes a positive transformation essentially in the social, environmental and economic factors.

Therefore, in general it has been emphasised that economic, social and environment are the three pillars for the approach. In terms of economic sustainability, it implies that, the system of production where one can consume their portion successfully without compromising future requirements. In the previous era, the economists assume that supply of natural resources are unlimited in nature, and they also believed that their growth is accompanied

by the help of technological advancements to replenish natural resources destroyed within the production process. In terms of social sustainability, it encompasses empowerment, equity, accessibility, cultural identity, and corporate stability. Social sustainability entails empowerment of people, communities, and promotion of cultures to achieve meaningful life and stability across the globe (Li and et.al. 2019).

Furthermore, environmental sustainability is based on natural environment and ensuring that it remains productive and resilient to support human life. It is dependent on the ecosystem and integrity of the natural environment. This reduces the wastage of important resources and maintain an equilibrium among all kinds of system boundaries.

On the other hand, the public private partnership entails the collaboration between the Government Agency and Private Sector company to finance and operate projects or development activities. The partnership between the private companies and government helps to improve the operational efficiency by providing public services (Aladağ and Işık, 2018).

In order to discuss the theories and models that are associated with the delivery of services through public private partnership, the following designs are considered:

- **Operation and maintenance contract:** This is based on the fact that the private agent operates publicly under the government contract and own assets for a specific period of time. Although, formal ownership of the asset remains with the public entity. In identification of risks that are associated with the private sector, it has been identified that this model is at a lower level and the end of the spectrum for both risk and involvement.
- **Building finance:** The private ally able to generate assets and finances the costs especially at the time of construction or implementation to fulfil its responsibilities. In context of private sector risk as well as involvement, this model gains lower end of the scope for both measures.

- **Build operate transfer:** This represents the general integration of the project delivery, the similar type of contract that governs the design, operations, construction and project financing required meet the purpose of ppp-private public partnership (Ma and et.al. 2018).
- **Build own operate transfer:** This is different from other structures in which the private entity owns the work. In order to recover the cost of investment and maintenance the primary goal is to achieve the higher margins of the project.
- **Build lease transfer:** The private entity builds complete projects and leases it to the government. In such a manner, the control over the project has been transferred from the project owner to a lessee.
- **Design build finance maintenance:** In this model, the private sector designs, builds and finances assets via providing services of facilities to manage and maintain services in the long-term agreements. This model is among the middle of the overall spectrum for the involvement of the private sector.
- **Design build finance maintain operate:** This is the project delivery method which is highly similar to build, own, operate and transfer approach except that there is no actual ownership that has been transferred. Furthermore, the contractor assumes the risks that are associated with the finance up to the end of the contract period. This model is broadly utilized in specific projects.

Moreover, PPP is not just an investment between the private and public actors, but the distribution goes across all management actions such as strategies and policies are devised with the co-governance of both participants (Van Marrewijk et al., 2008; Hueskes et al., 2017). For the PPP social responsibilities, the public sector role is crucial for the sustainable development and management of the partnerships (Crawford and Helm, 2009).

In the public private partnership (PPP), the profit is shared by public sectors and related risks, and cooperate with private sectors to control the time, quality, and cost of the projects undertaken (Chang, 2013).

Sustainable development (SD) seeks to improve the performances through direct participation, indirect leadership, and supervision in the project (Miller and Hobbs 2005; Lin et al., 2017).

The sustainability of a project can be seen as the result or a secondary effect of project practices that stimulate and promote environmental protection, human development promotion, social progress, economic development and promote sustainable development (Boz and ElAdaway, 2014). Sustainability goes beyond the goals of the project management triangle (quality, cost, and time) and needs careful action and thinking at macro level and in the long-term (Ma et al., 2017; Lu et al., 2013). This is because most development project in organizations or teams are temporary and have different employees throughout the project life cycle (Son and Rojas, 2010).

The continuity of the project is critical in achieving the objectives for sustainable development (Aarseth et al., 2017; Chang et al., 2017).

The Theory of Performance Measurement

According to (Liu et al. 2014), PPP performance is essential to business and project success. Limitations on public funds have encouraged several governments worldwide to use PPP to procure economic and social infrastructure development projects. Similar to traditional procurement, ex-post evaluation is being widely used in PPP projects. However, PPPs are more complicated than other traditional procurement approaches. Examination of literature suggests that limited research has been undertaken to examine if conventional ex post evaluation is sufficient to measure the performance of PPPs (Liu et al. 2014).

The use of Public-Private Partnership (PPP) arrangements has been advocated in several countries in the previous decades, with a rapid increase in adoption in different social and economic development sectors (Bovaird 2010a, Liu et al. 2014, Narbaev et al. 2020, Ruiz Díaz,

2020). PPP arrangements have been used to capitalise on the benefits of financing and cost outcomes, time, risks, and project delivery (Chowdhury et al. 2011, Geng et al. 2020). As mentioned earlier, to ensure business success at project level, performance improvement using performance measurement is critical (Bassioni et al., 2008) and a prerequisite (Liu et al., 2014). In most countries, monitoring and evaluating performance of PPP are the core activities of contract and project management (European Investment Bank (EIB), 2012). The comparative analysis of the evaluation of PPP development projects began to focus on the project's continuity and influence.

Economic PPP Theory

This theory focusses on the trade-off between quality and cost. Public-private partnerships (PPP) construct infrastructure assets and deliver the associated services emerging in their modern system in the UK in the 1990s. Although their quantitative significance has remained limited, a rich economic-theoretical PPP literature has emerged. In particular, the trade-off between allocative and productive efficiency has been extensively analysed in contract-theoretical literature. The empirical literature comparing PPP procurement with traditional public procurement is, however, inadequate. It may be futile to expect any simple empirical conclusions to emerge, and the limited or thin evidence-based means that public procurement decisions are strongly influenced by considerations other than economic efficiency (Välilä, 2020). According to (Rene, 2019), in 1992 PPPs were projected as an instrument of the New Public Management movement introduced by the United Kingdom (UK) government. The PPP policy was meant to create Private Finance Initiatives (PFI) to inspire private involvement in infrastructure improvement and social service provision, to ensure effectiveness of the public sector management (Burchell, 2000). Recently, researchers have regarded PPP as institutional activities to achieve public value for which governments are deficient in the know-how (Naik et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2014; Reynaers and De Graaf, 2014). In the subsequent years, most advanced as well as emerging economies approved PPP guidelines by setting up PPP units, for example in South Africa. Presently these partnerships between the public and the private sectors are recognised substitutes for the customary state delivery of public services.

Debatably, this combined working method permits of the public and private sectors to merge resources and skills to drive and achieve a common goal, which earlier could not have been achieved by just one party or group (Akintoye et al., 2003). Conversely, the application of PPP is not stress-free and direct (Ameyaw and Chan, 2015). While some PPPs have had a positive performance on results, others have had remarkable disappointments that have led some scholars to express caution in their adoption (Ameyaw and Chan, 2015). As stated by the World Bank (2003), the termination and renegotiation of PPP agreements for instance the ICT service providers globally have made headlines and, for numerous intentions, the renegotiation of contracts has not been an uncommon incidence. On the other hand, while sustainability has become a buzzword in discussions about the environment and development, work on theories of sustainable development has received much less attention. However, the theory is vital in understanding the origins and development of the PPP concept which is the key to achieving successful implementation and sustainability.

One of the PPPs development theories is strong sustainability theory (Ott/Döring, 2004) which is described as the one that rising arguments and would make that concept appear advantageous compared with other concepts which are not based on the idea of strong sustainability. Sustainable development (SD) has become a fundamental strategy to guide the world's social and economic transformation.

Strong Sustainability Theory is a nature-centred view where natural capital plays an irreplaceable role in production and consumption. This concept is mainly based on the steady-state economic theory that processes or manufactures capital and cannot be duplicated without the input of natural capital. Therefore, the process of development should not only require an increase in the total amount of capital, but also require the rationality of the capital structure and not affecting the ecological thresholds.

Moreover, economic development should not exceed the natural limit. Absurdly strong sustainability theory not only believes that natural capital cannot be replaced by manufactured capital, but also believes that the exploitation and utilization of ecosystems should be eliminated (Shi et al., 2019).

Weak Sustainability Theory

The weak sustainability theory is defined as a human-centred understanding or view that natural capital can be replaced by manufactured capital. As an extension of neoclassical welfare economics, weak sustainability considers the total amount of manufactured capital and natural capital as the most important. Therefore, if the total amount of capital increases in the process of development, even if the natural capital reduces to an unrecoverable state, it is still sustainable.

In addition, sustainability consists of numerous theories, Corporate Social Responsibility, Stakeholder Theory, Corporate Sustainability, and Green Economics (Shi et al., 2019). Moreover, (Shi et al., 2019) highlighted that there was an evolution process of SD theory developed through practice, and the study of SD cannot be separated from the implementation of relevant policies. SD has experienced the incubation of ideas, and then a series of SD practices, for instance the United Nations Sustainable Development Summit. Many changes have taken place, and SD has evolved from tackling environmental issues to dealing with the global strategic issues (Shi et al., 2019).

Based on the study of evolution of SD thoughts and the formation of SD theory by (Shi et al., 2019) and other scholars, there is also a theory based on the steady-state economic conditions and this theory focuses on “*manufactured capital*”.

Therefore, the process of development should not only require an increase in the total amount of capital, but also needs the rationality of the capital structure without affecting the ecological thresholds negatively. Moreover, economic development should not exceed the natural limit.

2.12 Space Technologies in achieving the aims of Sustainable Development

The UN strives to improve international collaboration in outer space and usage of space technologies for sustainable development. In recent years, there has been increasing interest among developed countries about using space technologies for sustainable development. Corsi, Pagani and Kovaleski, (2020) noted that space technologies are helping PPP’s projects

in achieving sustainable development. Application of sustainable technologies increases food security, reduces risks of disaster, prevents humanitarian crises and reduces poverty.

Several space technologies have been used in realizing SDGs in PPP's projects. For instance, the Hubble space telescope, space suit technology, The Kepler Space telescope and International Space Station are some of the technologies that can be used for improving sustainability in public projects. To implement development projects successfully, PPP companies need to use space technologies to make their work easier and save time as well.

2.13 PPPs with a Sustainable Development Perspective

Globally, PPPs are taken as an innovative model for infrastructure and public service delivery, and they are gradually becoming more popular around the world. PPP is faced with the predicament of development direction and value orientation since current studies and practices are mostly performed from the economic perspective (Cheng et al., 2020). PPPs are managed according to the sustainable development goals. According to Sergi et.al, (2019), PPP in context of sustainable development necessitates meeting the requirements of the current generation without compromising the ability of future generations. Various studies relating to sustainable development often adopt three dimensions which, include economic, environmental and social sustainability.

PPP concept has been in operation from past decades at both the local and the international level. In the PPP concept, the private actors are involved in one or more of different steps or part of policy making negotiation, resource provision, implementation and monitoring or reinforcement.

In the public private partnership, the key policy function is delegated to the private actors. It is still in hierarchical form dominated by public policymakers. Private actors are the ones who perform functions which the public actors are unable perform effectively. This specific form of PPP complements the traditional forms of command alongside controlling various policies. On the other hand, there is emergence of new and advanced kind of public private

partnerships which are autonomous public and private policy instruments, combined into new governance structures and framework. This is much more like a collaborative form of governance which is less steered and structured, within which the independent policymakers combine over all forces in the general policy procedure.

According to Wang (2021), the adoption of the agenda relates to sustainable development goals. PPP acts as one of the most significant and most effective tools to ensure sustainability. Apart from this, it has been also claimed that PPP have the power to alleviate the impact of shortage of fiscal funds into government procurement while making full use of the private sector expertise, technological innovation, and experiences.

The primary and foremost attribute of PPP is offering instrumental economic value and creation of potential social value that have been strategically associated with the need for achieving sustainable development goals.

Alabi, Kasim and Lasisi, (2020) highlighted that commitment towards achieving the sustainable development goals entail pursuing progress over economic, social and environmental targets. SDGs are cross-cutting and ambitious in nature and require a shift on how the work has been combined as partnership.

The great example to illustrate the PPP is the building of resilient infrastructure in order to promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization to foster innovation within the projects. It is both explicit and implicit kind of component to achieve the sustainable development goals.

The focus within this kind of partnership is over the trust factor because it is an important aspect as the partners are of different nature. The continuous support from public actors makes the private public partnership highly effectual in nature. Thus, there are various references available which represent that the PPP is the widely acknowledged tool within the area in which the companies are trying to work.

2.14 PPP as a Mechanism of Financing Sustainable Development

According to Li and et.al, (2020) sustainable development is one of the critical notions of the theory related to economic growth and expansion. Sustainability is the kind of criteria which evaluates economic growth in the well-balanced manner. It is all inclusive, entailing development for socio-economic and ecological systems so that economic growth does not damage the environment. The divergence between the two causes the shortage of financial resources for financing sustainable development.

The primary cause is associated with deficit of state budgets which is different for developed and developing countries. The second cause is related to low commercial attractiveness of investment into projects for the private companies due to legal limitations in order to receive profit margins. Because of this reason, on the government side, financing of sustainable development projects is limited to narrow and small budget while on the private business side, it is limited to separate and small budget corporate responsibility initiatives.

Bolomope and et.al, (2020) state that this has led to low flexibility of the projects in the area of sustainable development with low effectiveness. From a research point of view, the issues related to evaluation of effectiveness in financing sustainable development show detailed evaluation about the topic. Innovation acts as one of the most significant features for sustainable development. It is thus significant to undertake actions aimed at facilitating external financing procedures including PPP processes. Lack of such kind of actions may result into limited number of investment projects, thus, leading to negative economic impacts.

Considering the growing impact of sharing economy, local governments should consider the opportunity of cooperation with private investors in this area. These projects share great amount of potential for return over investment and are difficult to be implemented by one of the parties only.

Furthermore, Amović, Maksimović and Bunčić, (2020) state that the growing significance of sharing economy is estimated to amount into millions and upcoming years should increase the popularity of promoting green projects. Irrespective of whether the finances come from

the private or public sector, funding infrastructure development has specific distinct features from the perception of an investor.

The characteristic of infrastructure investment is a kind of asset which provides limited amount of flexibility as compared to other commercial activities. The private sector has the capability to raise financing by taking commercial loans and drawing over equity from bond markets. Thus, to be financially sustainable is the most basic sense and infrastructure development projects must be able to repay the interest and principal of commercial lenders.

PPP are not only utilized for the creation of physical assets and services but also meet the broad environmental as well as social goals. In context of environmental sustainability, PPP have the potential to realise broad positive impacts such as reducing the carbon emissions, promoting energy efficiency, creating green jobs, promotion of new and innovative thinking about the requirements related to infrastructure development for the future.

2.15 Space Historical Perspective

Globally, space continues to be a point of interest as innovation technology remain a key factor for development and makes a significant impact on the world. Space technology and data economy today accounts for over \$400billion globally while, in Africa the sector accounts for \$7million and is projected to grow to exceed \$10 billion by 2024. In Rwanda and elsewhere in the world, governments seek to explore and expand capabilities for satellite communications, navigations, Earth observation, exploration systems and other space applications. Rwanda has also learned good practices from different successful countries and recognises the significant role played by PPPs in delivering services in collaboration with developed countries such as USA, Europe, and UK. These developed countries already use space technologies to handle different disasters and predict them before they can occur. For instance, Earth-observation satellites monitor greenhouse gases, other climate indicators and analyse Earth's health ecosystem more effectively. Some technologies adapted from space use including GPS and semiconductor solar cells have dramatically reduced greenhouse gas emissions.

Developing countries such as Malawi, Kenya, Afghanistan, Algeria, Mauritius, Myanmar, Nigeria, South Africa, Syria, Thailand, Zambia and Turkey are commissioning the science technology and innovation solutions. They use them to monitor and address increasing challenges resulting from climate change. The above countries have benefited from the use of space technology in different areas for example, in combating food insecurity after completing a 2-month online workshop on the application of a crop monitoring system using satellite data. UN agency UNCTAD has initiated cooperation to support developing countries to know how to use satellite data in monitoring crop conditions for better agriculture productivity. The system was provided by the Crop Watch Innovative Cooperation Programme (Crop Watch -ICP), which is an initiative that resulted from discussions during the UN commission on Science and Technology for Development (CSTD).

Food security has been significantly at risk due to climate change. Hence, the use of space technology in monitoring crops has become a national emergency mission as mentioned by Shamika N. Sirimane, UNCTAD's director of technology and logistics (UNCTAD, 2021). Furthermore, in 2018, member states of the African Union emphasised the importance of science, technology and innovation as tools and enablers for socioeconomic transformation of the continent.

African Union has therefore adopted the decisions and recommendations made by the executive council meeting held in January 2013 in Addis Ababa in Ethiopia. During the sectorial/ministerial conferences, the focus was on the increasing need for Africa to develop a well-structured Space Policy and Strategy. That could guide the continent to implement a global competitive outer space program. This program would enable member states to bind space resources in a more coordinated and systematic manner. That could be used to address the continent's challenges and develop an African space market and industry. Three years later in 2016, a further reminder on the decisions adopted by the assembly happened in January 2016 in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia to adopt the African space policy and strategy. This was in view of formalizing the AU agenda 2053 for developing local capacities in Earth observation, satellite communication, navigation and positioning, Space science and astronomy. The African Union (AU) Space working group was requested to develop the framework for the implementation of the African space policy and strategy. Its governance

framework that covers the relevant legal requirements and protocols for operation of African outer space programme (UNCTAD, 2021). In addition, the AU has recognised the potential of the space science, technology and innovation in Africa's development and the realisation of the aspirations of the long-term vision.

AU (African Union) Agenda 2063 will jointly address common development challenges. These include natural hazards and disasters, climate change mitigation and adaptation, agriculture and food insecurity, conflicts, disease outbreaks, provision of education and health services in rural and remote areas. Furthermore, connecting citizens, proactive management of natural resources and the environment are also outlined in the African Space Policy and Strategy. There is need for appropriate institutional arrangements for effective governance, promotion and coordination of space activities on the continent. This should be aimed at achieving maximum benefits such as an Integrated, Prosperous and Peaceful Africa, driven by its own citizens and representing a dynamic strength in the global arena.

Thus, African Union (AU) has introduced a statute of the African space agency. Africa's space programs account for a very small part of the world's space activity. In 2017, the African Union passed a legislation to establish the African Space Agency and approved Egypt as host country for the new agency's headquarters.

2.16 Space Technologies

The use of space technologies has been vital in achieving sustainable development. Several developments in satellite positioning technology and flight platforms can have a positive impact on the achievement of sustainable development goals. There are many promising examples of satellite positioning technology for future applications.

Firstly, data from permanently recorded reference stations can be used in the Global Positioning System to extract information about tropospheric and atmospheric water content that can be incorporated to improve weather forecasting for agriculture in areas with heavy rainfall and food manufacturing activities.

Secondly, the United States is experimenting the use of continuously recorded station data from the Global Positioning System to track tsunamis that pass-through ocean basins due to the effects of ionosphere. When a tsunami is detected, it is possible to predict its origin, possible passage through the ocean basin, and possible impact 24 hours in advance.

In addition, the Earth observation satellite platform is developing a “Global Wireless Spectrum Monitoring” capabilities, applying digital gap tracking, wireless penetration (such as the Long-Term Evolution Tower in Kenya) and the economic performance of developing countries. Drones can be a relatively inexpensive alternative compared with satellites, they are the source of earth observation data that have wider applications, and it is increasingly used for food security applications and crop prediction.

In Cape Town, South Africa, the Aero-View platform uses unmanned aerial vehicles to obtain infrared images of farmland that is helpful for farmers to quickly identify problem areas in crops and avoid agricultural losses (Abardazzo, 2017). The cost of a drone is thousands of dollars, and a single battery can travel more than 100 kilometers. However, in many countries/regions, their use is usually regulated by law that serve as sources of earth observation data.

International science and technology are the world’s largest cooperation program that is, the “International Space Station”, that has been in operation since 1998. Canadian Space Agency and the Japanese Aerospace Research Institute, Europe (ESA), Russian Federation (Roscosmos) and United States (NASA) have collaborations between each other through this program for sustainable development in their respective countries as they jointly developed the project, they currently operate and use the space station together.

The space station itself is an outstanding engineering and technological achievement. Its components are launched from various continents and countries. There are three laboratory modules designed for this sustainable development project Columbus Laboratory (Europe; 2008), Kibo Laboratory (Japan) and Destiny Laboratory Module (USA; 2001). These laboratories are equipped with external platforms and research equipment to support applications and experiments in technology, space exploration and earth observation.

Furthermore, numerous developments in satellite positioning technology and flight platforms have emerged and contribute to the achievement of the sustainable development goals. There are different examples of promising satellites positioning technology for future applications (United Nations ,2021). For instance, recorded station data from global positioning system are being used for prevention of disasters and extracted information content can be incorporated to improve weather forecasting for agriculture in areas that are more affected by heavy rainfall and food manufacturing purposes (United Nations, 2021).

Moreover, the United States is experimenting the use of constant recorded station data from the Global Positioning System which are used to track tsunamis that pass-through ocean basins due to the effects of ionosphere. This is very important because it reflects and modifies radio waves used for communication and navigation (Space weather prediction center, 2021). This is important because when a tsunami is detected, it helps decision makers to predict and detect its origin and make possible plans ahead, simultaneously observe and monitor its impact 24 hours in advance (Angove et al., 2019). In Rwanda, drones are effective in the health care sector as they are used to transport blood from one hospital to another when emergency need occur. Moreover, in science and technology, drones are used to take photographs or pictures in different ceremonies and save space and hassles.

In 2019, NASA executives has announced that the space station would open its airlocks to commercial businesses and private astronauts (Fernholz, 2019). This has allowed the public private partnership (PPP) to test innovative new technologies and train astronauts under microgravity. Houston-based company Axiom Space has a plan to build a new commercial module on space station to spur the growth of an off-Earth economy (Howell, 2021). The absence of assets, population growth and environmental changes has presented enormous environmental and social difficulties. The support capacity is characterized by having the option of addressing recent concerns without losing the capacity of the frontline to address its problems. This explanation has been recognized by associations and governments generally.

In 1997, Elkington (1994) presented the rule of the "Triple Fund" (Triple Bottom Line also known as TBL Fund which help preserve affordable housing, create local jobs, and address climate change among other social, economic, and environmental aspects, for the community at large) to quantify the support capacity, suggesting to comply with the triple guidelines of the economy, society, and climate.

According to Rijsberman and van de Ven (2000), the support capacity is not concerned about the needs of a few ages, but it is identified with the limit of normal support frameworks to keep up with nature, climate, and hydrology.

Cong and Ma (2018) proposed a planned structure for PPP projects to support evaluations, including practical standards that depend on the competition of the project, the investment of the partners, the executives limit, the socioecological comparison, the use of assets and the value in cash.

2.16.1 Africa Space Strategy

African countries active in space activities represent 20% of the Earth's land surface area and spent less than \$100million (translating to less than 0.2% of the global space budget)) compared to USA, India, China, and Europe together- spent more than \$50 billion on space activities in 2013. In terms of performance in the space sector, in 2013 South Africa was ranked among the top thirty countries globally (23rd) in terms of its space budget (\$41 million) and 30th in terms of scientific production in satellite technology (accounting for 0.87% of global publications in the domain).

The above evaluations demonstrate a significant need for African continent to invest in space technologies. This will help to overcome various challenges such as climate change and disasters which limits Africa's potential fast-growing sector that can make a significant contribution to the continent's challenges. These include provision of food, shelter, clean water, education, and health environment (African Union, 2017). Space based products and services can provide critical spatial data which can be used in decision making in order to assist in achieving the sustainable development goals.

Africa is said to have potential for growth compared to the developed countries if it invests and commits to social, economic, and environmental ambitions. Thus, many of the technological developments need to address socio-economic challenges faced by the African continent and cannot be outsourced (African Union, 2017).

2.16.2 Rwanda Space Agency

Rwanda is one of the countries that continues to lead in economic success in Africa. Therefore, Rwanda space agency program does not come in as a surprise. The Rwandan government is seeking to expand its capabilities for satellite communications, navigation, Earth monitoring, exploration systems and other space applications. While recognizing the significant role played by the private sector, PPPs can deliver these capabilities at reduced cost and risk. Rwanda actively participated in the work of the “African Union Space Science and Technology Working Group”, which formulated Africa’s space strategies and policies, and deployed its first satellite RWASAT1 in 2019. The second satellite was put into orbit with collaboration with “Russian Soyuz rocket” (Kourou, 2019). Rwanda Space Agency also established a partnership with an American company “One-Web” and its headquarters are in Arlington, Virginia, led by Greg Wyler and launched the first six dedicated satellites for the internet communications. There are few national level space agencies in the African region and some of these agencies took such steps such as agencies in Egypt, South Africa, Zimbabwe, Algeria, Tunisia, Morocco, Nigeria, Angola, and Kenya (Geneva, 2021).

According to the Report by the Aerospace Industry, Africa's aerospace budget is currently estimated to be around 7 billion U.S. dollars and is expected to grow at an average annual growth rate of 7%, and by 2024 it will exceed 10 billion U.S. dollars (Spaceref.com, 2019). RSA uses satellite data and service images to support agricultural forecasting and planning, urban planning, disaster risk reduction and environmental monitoring. Ingabire announced in a press release that RSA is responsible for regulation and policy formulation for sustainable environmental development.

It will support and coordinate research in space science and technology, capacity-building programs and design, infrastructure. I will also, launch of satellites as a part of sustainable development in collaboration with private public partnership. The Rwanda Space Agency will be managed through cooperation with international space as governmental organization.

2.16.3 The Impact of Space Activities

Space data is useful in different sectors toward development of any country because of its contributions to the economy. Space data helps on how to use space assets for various applications, the impacts on economy and society in general. The aim is that many space-based services have positive impacts on society. However, issues concerning economic data definitions and methodologies have to be resolved to allow the benefits to be identified and measured more precisely.

There are a number of benefits from space-based services on solving key societal challenges. There are also impacts of institutional space programmers on space firms (OECD, 2007). The adoption and diffusion of new technologies such as space technologies, can bring about significant changes although they may be imperceptible.

Important capabilities made possible by space assets include the ability to disseminate information over broad issues, instantaneous telecommunications and a global vision of the world. However, providing civilian space-based infrastructure as a useful complement to terrestrial ones is a relatively recent objective.

Space activities were (and still are in some cases) developed primarily for strategic and military purposes, not for economic or societal gains. This perspective has slowly changed with the growing integration and universal use of space-based services in various policy making and commercial activities. It is nevertheless acknowledged that science and space exploration as long-time drivers of innovation in space developments are the key missions of space agencies (OECD, 2005).

Today, space assets have diverse impacts on society although those impacts are generally not well identified and the information available tend to be more qualitative than quantitative.

Furthermore, space activities embedded in the larger aerospace domain can be a noteworthy contributor to an economy. The main issue is to provide reliable measures of the impacts, and this requires sound background data. As already mentioned, the current supply of space-related statistics contains many gaps. Many of the currently available input metrics are of low comparability across countries or of limited availability. This is a general problem as the most available indicators of space activities are the least useful for tracking the development of the

“space economy” (e.g. services), whereas the most valuable indicators are largely missing except for a few applications.

There is a lack of official space related data for calculating true productivity based on value added per employee from the sales of space goods and services. For example, the effect of space on competitiveness is also hard to determine. This is because it would require data on the cost of using specific space production processes or the profitability of specific space products (Spaceref.com, 2019).

2.16.4 Space Impacts on Key Societal Challenges (Environment and Natural Disasters)

Unique characteristics of space applications could make a considerable contribution to several long-term challenges of the 21st century. These challenges include the environment, the use of natural resources, the management of natural disasters, international mobility and the knowledge of the society (OECD, 2005). Based on benefits derived from existing space systems, now days several key activities could not operate without space systems. But like water, energy or other infrastructures, space systems and their products (e.g. communications links, imagery) have become so embedded in modern societies that their benefits go largely unnoticed, except when systems fail to function as expected. Weather forecasting is a good example.

Quasi-real-time space data integrated into better computer models have significantly improved the economic value of weather forecast information (e.g. precipitation forecasts for agriculture, temperature variations for electric utilities). The traditional error in a three-day forecast landfall position of hurricanes has been reduced from about 337 kilometres in 1985 to about 177 kilometres in 2004 (SSB, 2005), thus, giving more time to warn populations and businesses.

The improved accuracy is partly due to better knowledge of the oceans gained from space borne observation. Ocean monitoring from space became operational in the late 1990s with the Franco-American mission Topex/Poséidon. Satellite altimetry enables water levels to be measured within 3cm at basin level, but also provides information for monitoring phenomena for instance, variations in ocean circulations like El Niño, seasonal changes in oceans, and tide mechanisms.

In most instances, space infrastructure needs to be closely combined with terrestrial facilities to become fully effective (e.g., Earth observation data need to be integrated into models with complementary non-space data). The main benefits from using space systems for tackling societal challenges generally take the form of decreased transaction time, cost savings, cost avoidance, improved productivity, and increased efficiency for end-users of space assets.

A number of cost-benefit studies on space systems have been conducted over the years, however it is still challenging to track specific benefits to space technologies. The calculation of the ratio between the costs of the system and the flow of the socio-economic benefits obtained is at times contentious because space solutions can rarely be considered in isolation. Diverse methodologies are used in benefits assessments, in particular non-market valuation methods (e.g. contingent valuation, and choice modelling), due to the good nature of some of the benefits. In natural disasters management, the benefits from space infrastructure are clear. Space-based observations allow the Earth to be seen as a dynamic integrated system of land, water, atmosphere, ice, and biological processes, while satellite telecommunications allow worldwide connections.

This is increasingly useful, as the number of disasters worldwide has already exceeded 300 a year since 1998. There is a clear upward trend for both economic and insured losses related to natural disasters (OECD, 2006). Floods play a dominant role in both the number of disasters and the number of people affected due to increase in population growth along coastlines. Disasters also entail important economic losses globally, and floods is one of the most important factors (Figure 4.3b). In 2005, economic losses from catastrophes amounted to more than USD 170 billion.

Losses due to flooding can be reduced by creation of adequate flood defences (e.g. levees) and water management infrastructures (e.g. reservoirs), providing warnings to the threatened area and taking the appropriate emergency actions to fight floods (e.g. evacuation). Remote sensing from space provides data for the whole cycle of information for flood prevention, mitigation, pre-flood assessment, response (during the flood), recovery (post-flood), and weather newscasts (with 0–3-hour forecasts). For example, according to the French Civil Protection agency, regular satellite observations over the past five years have contributed to improving the control of water pumping efficiency on a large-scale during floods. In 2001, it took three months for the cities and villages in the French department of

the Somme to dry out. During flooding in the Arles area of the south of France in 2003, the use of timelier satellite imagery contributed to more appropriate siting of the Civil Protection's water pumps, thus taking "only" three weeks to get the city dry again.

2.16.5 Challenges in Rwanda's Agricultural Sector

The International Trade Administration (2021) acknowledged Rwanda's Agricultural Sector as the best industry sector for the country. This is because agriculture is crucial for Rwanda's growth and reduction of poverty, as the backbone of Rwanda's economy. According to World Bank, employment in agriculture sector contributes 62.3 percent of total employment in Rwanda, occupied by 71 percent of females and 53 percent of males employed in the sector. It remains a key sector in Rwanda's efforts to foster private sector development.

However, according to UN Food and Agricultural Organization (2022), there is a strong link between agriculture and poverty in Rwanda, hence, the challenges in the agriculture sector are also the drivers of rural poverty. Tackling poverty remain a priority to the country despite the remarkable development over the years from 2015 to date, since Rwanda's agricultural sector faces several challenges including the following.

Location: Rwanda is located in a geographical region that experience a disproportionately large number of natural disasters. It has experienced more Floods and landslides that were increasingly reported in the high altitude western and Northern provinces, and the droughts made severe damages in the eastern province. Rwanda is susceptible to many diseases that are influenced by climatic factors such as malaria, meningitis, and cholera etc.

Land Degradation and Soil Erosion: These factors are among the main challenges faced by the private public partnership supporting the agriculture sector. Around 90% of Rwandan territory lies on slopes and consequently experience soil loss, erosion and reduced soil fertility. It was estimated that 1.4 million metric tons of soil per year is lost, accounting for the huge loss of 320.000 US dollars. There is an on-going pressure caused by the growing population and this has a negative effect on land availability leading to land fragmentation, land conflicts and grabbing.

Land use and distribution. In Rwanda, land categorized as rural is nearly 98% of the total land area, with around 49% classified as arable. A Land Law passed in 2005 established a private

market for land titles and eliminated customary land tenure systems. Under the law, landowners are obliged to register their land holdings and land titles are equally available for women and men. However, in some cases informally married women have insecure land rights and women in general face difficulties in claiming inheritance.

Dependency on rainfall and climate vulnerability: Rwanda's agriculture sector presents a strong dependence on natural rainfall and there is vulnerability to climate shocks. The low-level use of water resources for irrigation makes agricultural production unpredictable from one season to another.

Low levels of productivity for both crops and livestock: Due to low input use, poor production techniques and inefficient farming practices. The use of chemical fertilizers in Rwanda saw a steady rise in 2007 when the Government of Rwanda (GoR) started the Crop Intensification Program (CIP). Under the program, subsidized fertilizers are provided to farmers for the cultivation of six priority crops with the collaboration of PPP. Most farmers' adoption of fertilizers remains quite low compared to other countries in the region.

Weak processing capacity and value addition of products placed on the market. Between 1999 and 2008 the share of food crops processed never exceeded 6.5%. Furthermore, only 34% of the total food produced in the country reaches the market. The reasons for unexploited processing capacity lies in lack of appropriate technologies, expertise, financing incentives and rural infrastructure. Lack of access to an adequate water supply and at times energy supply makes it difficult for processing businesses or industries to function.

Shortage of land availability: Due to shortage in land availability, the Government of Rwanda is promoting intensification as a strategy to increase production and farmers' incomes. According to the PSTAIII, "In the long term, the goal is to move Rwandan agriculture from a largely subsistence sector to a more knowledge-intensive, market-oriented sector, sustaining growth and adding value to products." To do so, in line with the document for EDPRS II, the GoR considers agriculture a catalyst sector and will promote the development of value chain with stronger links with the private sector. The crops of interest include coffee, horticulture and cereals among others plus dairy.

Lack of equipment: Scarcity of local ground-based equipment led to failure in obtaining timely information about the state of the environment as monitoring is done by RSA.

2.17 Theoretical Perspectives on PPPs Contribution to Economic Growth (Theoretical Framework)

After having gone through the literature above, this research adopts a framework that encapsulates aspects of PPP, SD, Space technology and innovation policies in Rwanda to accelerate economic growth through the proposed knowledge of best practice /model and transfer processes. The discussion above, indicates that PPPs lie between either contracting-out and private delivery, or contracting-out and public delivery (Stelling, 2014). In as far as contracting is concerned, PPPs cover more public facility provision responsibilities to the private sector organizations. The NPM (new public management) theory responds to the failures of the government in the delivery of public services by engaging the private sector with an extensive range of tasks to create more effective delivery solutions. PPPs which apply this approach encourage “a less government but a more market philosophy”. Consequently, the tasks and authorities of the public sector are lessened to the level of just creating policies or supervising the accomplishments of established performance goals of the private sector.

However, in such a PPP provision approach, the private sector tends to be worried with maximizing profits instead of delivering efficient public facilities. Basing on the interventionist technique, the New Public Service (NPS) and Public Value (PV) theories act as an answer to the private sector’s deficits in the delivery of public services. Public servants and citizens are offered more powers to inspire the delivery of public services so as to protect the general society interests against harsh behavior of different private sector actors.

However, the private sector still has more tasks in the implementation of genuine PPP project responsibilities, its control and power to guide the delivery of public services are lessened, and its contribution is heavily controlled and strictly supervised by public sector bosses in partnership with the citizens. The NPS (New public service) and public value (PV) principles may work well in countries where there is some sound level of democracy, and on the government schemes where intergovernmental institutions that encourage good governance participate.

Comparing the New public service theory, the fact that researchers have offered frameworks which might be used to legitimize, generate or measure the delivery of public valued services,

this is what makes the PV (public value) theory stand out. Basing on the structural and managerial approaches, the NPG theory is a reply to both the government and market failures in the delivery of public facilities or services. The NPG theory highlights joint value making via comprehensive public service provision cooperative relations.

The influence of the public bosses, private sector actors and the voted political leaders is lessened as public service provision decisions are taken and executed based on dual and semi-joint organizational, formal and informal institutional, agreed and non-agreed structures via joint managerial policies and networks. Therefore, neither the private nor the public sector actors might directly influence the other project players to act in ways which may contradict their will. From the above conclusions, it can be noted that, the key influence of NPS and PV over the NPM is the understanding that public sector influence in the delivery of public facilities or services requires to be strengthened than being lessened. Alternatively, unlike NPG that is entirely embraced, NPM, PV, and NPS concentrate on PPP projects providing effective and efficient public services, but they are less concerned with inter-organizational relationships. The NPM, NPS plus PV contribute or subscribe to the ally or partner co-responsibility aspects. Figure 2.1 below shows the theoretical framework of PPPs that encapsulates economic growth, sustainable development and use of pace technologies in Rwanda.

Figure. 2.1 Theoretical Framework

After having reviewed the literature above that touches the different aspects of our research and the most pertinent theories to PPPs, I have to note that the current study benefited immensely from the previous studies. While, drawing inspiration from them and adjusting their lines of inquiry, this study differs from them in the following ways:

a) A more Inclusive definition of Private Public Partnerships (PPPs)

The literature from the previous works definition of PPPs is more skewed in favour of infrastructural procurement and provision of financing resources for investment. These studies have defined PPPs from the period the contract takes as long-term contracts between the public entity and the private entity, where the private would agree to design and build, expand, or upgrade the public sector infrastructure. It would also take responsibility for financial, technical, and operational risks. Although assuming a more cooperative approach of PPPs and benefits both parties (BOT model), this study differs from the previous studies by adopting a more inclusive definition of PPPs. PPPs should be deliberated from a function-specific perspective, emphasizing collaborative efforts with other parties. This takes into consideration legal aspects bringing government and private sector together stressing mutuality, obligation and trust as social aspects of the partnership. The adopted definition is more inclusive because it takes into consideration the social aspects of the partnership that would lead to achievement of sustainable development goals.

b) A gap in the Literature on PPPs, Space Technologies and Sustainable development in Rwanda

Despite a lot of attention that has been devoted to developing countries on achievement of sustainable development goals, none has focused on Rwanda. The argument here is that Rwanda after its violent past merits much attention, but an extreme focus on the use of space technologies in aiding achievement of sustainable development goals. The use of space technologies (RSA) increases revenue for the country's strategic plan and helps in delivery of

more sustainable goals. According to (Maria Jose and Mathieu, 2021) in their article “Unpacking the dangerous illusion of PPPs” they argued that Public Private Partnership (PPPs) are increasingly being promoted as a way of securing much needed funds to deliver development projects. The PPP promoters continue to argue that they are an efficient way to link the gap in infrastructure and provide essential services in order to achieve the sustainable development Goals as established in UN’s Agenda 2030.

Previous studies have not considered the role of PPPs from a wide economic perspective in enabling achievement of sustainable development goals that would ensure the requirements of future generations.

Subsequently, this study takes into consideration the social aspects of PPPs by adopting a three-way contribution of PPPs in enabling sustainable development goals in Rwanda through economic, environmental and social sustainability.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

In explaining the impact of PPPs on sustainable development in Rwanda and their contribution to Rwanda's economic growth, the study adopts a positivist research approach by relying on the use of quantitative methods. This highlights the path or direction through which the aims and objectives of the study are met. This chapter builds on chapters 1, 2, as a methodology to describe the research process and the decisions behind the chosen methods for collecting and analyzing the data. It begins with a brief description of the approach followed, research philosophy, quantitative methods, sample size and period, procedure, data processing and analysis.

3.1 Deductive Approach

This research follows a deductive research approach to test existing theories by researching current literature and theories connected to the research subject (Soiferman, 2010). Existing theories refers to how current literature displays PPPs contribution to economic growth and sustainable development in Rwanda. Additionally, conducting a deductive reasoning starts with recognizing a social dilemma or theory and then test the data from a general level to a more in-depth and specific perspective (Soiferman, 2010). Therefore, this thesis will compare prior theories and literature with similar research methodology and approach. As a consequence, deductive reasoning is chosen as the investigative strategy (Gallaire et al., 1989). Furthermore, the identified gap in the literature shows that there is lack of inclusion and integration of what PPPs entail and how they contribute to economic growth and sustainable development.

Moreover, the deductive reasoning is utilized to test the hypotheses whether PPPs contribute to economic growth and sustainable development.

3.2 Research Philosophy

The research philosophy followed by this study is positivism because it has a strong correlation to quantitative research methods. The quantitative approach is connected to positivism because it involves the methodology of collecting empirical and scientific data

which is based upon statistical information. Furthermore, positivism also more appropriate for this research because it enables the researcher to be confident or sure regarding a particular subject due to prior gathered scientific data supporting the assumption (Crossan, 2003; Collis & Hussey, 2013). Therefore, the positivist research approach is used as it helps the researcher to compare prior literature with findings of this study. This will show whether there exists a statistical significance between the PPPs and economic growth and the extent of their contribution if any.

Why Rwanda Space Agency as a Case Study?

This study employs a case study approach to obtain a bigger picture of how PPPs support agricultural productivity in Rwanda. RSA is chosen as a case study because it provides a good case of a public entity that operates in partnership with public companies. Its positive support in promoting agricultural production is an indicator of how private companies aid public bodies with finances to provide services to society. By looking at the contribution of RSA we are able to identify the contribution of PPPs to agricultural sector through the use of data collected by satellite and predictions of future seasons for successful agriculture production. Furthermore, the RSA case provides a good example of a government entity in collaboration with the private sector.

The RSA collaborates with the African Union Space Science and Technology which is a working group that drafted the African space policies and strategies which was also launched. Rwanda Space Agency (RSA) is basically the National Space Agency, which was established in 2021 with a mission of developing Rwanda space sector for better socio-economic development. The agency has a mandate to coordinate and regulate all activities related to space within the country. RSA is also responsible for creating an environment able to promote entrepreneurial and total industrial development to allow the commercialization of products that are internationally competitive for local consumption as well as for exports markets.

Rwanda Space Agency is also responsible for designing and implementing capacity building programs in space science as well as technologies and their application in order to build skilled professionals in the space industry. This has been implemented through various partnerships with different stakeholders. The agency is motivated by the need to develop Rwanda's space

sector towards achieving socio-economic development. Moreover, they share the vision of building a competitive space ecosystem at the global level.

Despite issues of land scarcity for operations, location, mountainous ground, RSA aims at developing Rwanda's space sector towards socio-economic development and stability. The company faces various challenges due to Rwanda's location (Danielle, 2020). The development of space application products and services requires the improvement on additional capabilities in the industry. Furthermore, the challenges are also related to the maintenance of the high-quality investigations and education framework in order to participate in space science.

Apart from this, space development requires high level of investments given that the country is land locked and hence faces difficulties while trying to launch and install satellites in their homeland. The Rwanda space agency is also focused on making and targeting specific applications such as biodiversity monitoring, flood predictions, wildlife conservation, drought management, climate monitoring, climate adaptation, agriculture monitoring, disaster management, ground transportation management, air transportation and control, investigation and capability building, health status among others. Currently, the Rwanda Space Agency is able to collaborate and coordinate the space activities in different sectors for instance agriculture, forests, biodiversity, land and disaster management, climate change adaptation, urbanisation etc. It also focuses on the improvement of the air quality and control. It is because of these activities, which provide answers to our research question that RSA is chosen as a case study.

3.3 Quantitative Methods

The quantitative method is chosen because it enables a systematic investigation aimed at exploring different social phenomenon by analyzing quantifiable data gathered through statistical and mathematical methods (See Figure 3.8). Furthermore, the quantitative approach collects information and data through different collection methods such as online surveys and questionnaires (Parylo, 2012). Since this study looks at the existing literature in comparison to the findings, the contributions of PPPs to economic growth and sustainable development, the quantitative research approach is deemed most suitable. Not only due to

the statistical nature of the research purpose but in order to sufficiently explore the gap in the literature by providing extra data on how PPPs contribute to economic growth.

3.4 Introduction of Hypotheses and Variables

To establish features of Public Private Partnerships in Rwanda and the theoretical contributions of the Public Private Partnerships to sustainable development, I developed an empirical study of contributions of PPPs, probing whether or not and to what extent PPPs contribute to agricultural productivity in Rwanda. Explicitly, I explore how the Rwanda Space Agency increases agricultural productivity in Rwanda and how it contributes to its sustainable development agenda. I further, investigate whether PPPs have a contribution to Rwanda's economic growth. Furthermore, I investigate whether changes in its agricultural sector correlate with its economic growth and whether PPPs models contribute to sustainability in Rwanda. The investigations of PPPs impact in Rwanda are particularly important because it contributes to economic growth. Through investment, it ultimately contributes to the country's sustainable development.

Thus, this thesis makes advances both the data in the academic arena regarding PPPs, their contribution and efficiency in contributing to sustainable development in Rwanda. Specifically, this is examining how Rwanda Space Agency contributes to agricultural productivity and sustainable development. This is done by examining the following three hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: *Impact of PPPs on Agricultural Productivity.*

- **HO** = Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) involving the Rwanda Space Agency do not significantly increase the productivity in Rwanda's agricultural sector.
- **H1** =Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) involving the Rwanda Space Agency significantly increase the productivity in Rwanda's agricultural sector.

Hypothesis 2: *Influence of PPPs on Economic Growth.* Tests whether there is a direct link between PPPs and economic growth indicators.

- **HO** =The involvement of PPPs in Rwanda's agricultural sector does not positively correlate with an increase in Rwanda's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

- **H2** =The involvement of PPPs in Rwanda's agricultural sector positively correlates with an increase in Rwanda's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Hypothesis 3: Effectiveness of PPP Models (Types) in Long-term Sustainability. This Hypothesis focuses on the long-term aspect of PPPs.

- **H0** =Current PPP models employed in Rwanda are ineffective in ensuring long-term sustainable development in the agricultural sector.
- **H3** = Current PPP models employed in Rwanda are effective in ensuring long-term sustainable development in the agricultural sector.

3.4.1 Dependent variable

The dependent variable (outcome variable) refers to is the overall result of the production year. Thus, the frequency of a dependent variable might vary and alternate as a result of the independent variables (Leatham, 2012). Dependent variables used in this thesis are from the literature in this study. The application of dependent variable (outcome variable) as production years remains the most appropriate method for this study research.

3.4.2 Independent variable

Independent (explanatory) variables are delineated as a set of variables, which have a direct effect and impact on the dependent variable (s) (Collins & Hussey, 2013). Additionally, the independent variable is defined as the reason or cause and its frequency or value is independent of the other variables in the study (Leatham, 2012). In this study, the independent variable is represented by the different crops that are produced such as cereals, beans, tubers, since they have a direct influence on the way the dependent variable is understood and perceived.

3.5 Sample Size and Data Period

The study applies data for a six-year period from 2015-2020 mainly from the Rwanda Space Agency. The Agency is a private public partnership collaboration and sustains the economy by monitoring different targeted projects. RSA activities include bio-diversity monitoring, flood

prediction and management, wildlife conservation, drought management, climate monitoring and adaptation, agriculture monitoring, disaster management, teleports installation, maintenance and utilization, ground transportation management, air transportation and control, research and capacity building and health.

The agricultural sector is the main focus of the study because it is the second main contributor of Rwanda’s GDP at 27 percent. Data of the agricultural sector was readily available and is more amenable to quantitative methods than data from the service sector which was hard to gather because of the COVID19 situation. Also, the rest of the data from other sectors was not included because they are not significant contributors to Rwanda GDP.

Data from RSA was complemented by data from various bodies including Rwanda Ministry of Finance (MINECOFIN,) National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda (NISR), Rwanda Space Agency (RSA), Rwanda Geoportal (Spatial Data), Private Sector Federation (PSF), African Development Bank (ADB), Rwanda Development Board (RDB), International Monetary Fund (IMF), Esri Rwanda and World Bank (WB) (See Appendices, A, C and D).

	A	B	C
1			
2	List of SAS 2018 Tables		
3	Table 0	Summary of Seasonal Agricultural Survey Main indicators	
4	Table 1	List of strata	
5	Table 2	Classification of potential land for agriculture per district (ha)	
6	Table 3	Share (in percentage) of area occupied by agricultural strata within districts	
7	Table 4	Selected segments per district	
8	Table 5	Agricultural land use for potential arable land per district (Ha)	
9	Table 6.1	Season A, Cultivated area by crop type by province (ha)	
10	Table 6.2	Season B, Cultivated area by crop type by province (ha)	
11	Table 6.3	Season C, Cultivated area by crop type by province (ha)	
12	Table 7.1	Season A_Harvested area by crop type Per Province (Ha)	
13	Table 7.2	Season B_Harvested area by crop type per Province (Ha)	
14	Table 8	Average plot size by cropping system per district (In sqm)	
15	Table 9.1	Season A_Production of main crops by Province (MT)	
16	Table 9.2	Season B_Production of main crops by Province (MT)	
17	Table 9.3	Season C_Production of main crops by Province (MT)	
18	Table 10.1	Season A_Yield of Main crops by Province	
19	Table 10.2	Season B_Yield of Main crops by Province	
20	Table 10.3	Season C_Yield of Main crops by Province	
21	Table 11.1	Sowing dates per crop (Percentage) in Segments	
22	Table 11.2	Sowing dates per crop (Percentage) for Large Scale farmers	
23	Table 11.3	Sowing dates per District (Percentage)	
24	Table 12.1	Percentage of plots with number of crops per plot by District	
	Summary	Main Indicators	Table 1 Table 2 Table 3 Table 4 Table 5

Figure 3.1. Data Source from Rwanda Space Agency

3.6 Sample Collection

The data collected on agriculture is representative of all provinces, districts, the crops, their improvement, challenges and diversification through Rwanda's Space Agency. The datasets provided were from 2015 to 2016 covering 3 seasons A, B and C and details on fertilizers and tools. (See Appendix A: List of Data).

There were six (6) years' worth of observation on agricultural production data survey results from 2015 to 2022. The data for the years before 2015 could not be obtained due to poor keeping of agricultural seasons data. Although the 6-year data period is small, it still provides us with the rough picture on how PPPs have contributed to economic growth through agricultural productivity.

Season A: The data for the 6 years were all gathered and documented from the survey collected by the Rwanda Space Agency for 2015 – 2020 with a sample survey of 2015 Season A shown below with missing values and outliers which were not used in the analysis. (See Appendix B - 2015 Seasonal Agriculture Survey - Season A)

Season B: The data gathered for this season from the surveys were also fully documented for the years in view 2015 -2020 except with few missing values as in Season A. (See Appendix C for 2015 Season B samples data)

Season C: The data collected in this season had some missing values, some agricultural products were not available, and some years have no Season C etc. for example the 2015 Season C does not include some crops and could influence the result either negatively or positively depending on the analysis. See Appendix D for Season C and missing data.

Production of Main Crops (MT)				
Crops	1.2	2.1	2.2	Total
Tubers and Roots	59,431	30,441	2,354	92,226
Sweet potatoes	144	9,127	2,354	11,625
Irish potatoes	59,287	21,314	-	80,601
Legumes and Pulses	35	2,823	318	3,177
Beans	35	2,050	179	2,264
Bush Beans	0	2,050	179	2,229
Climbing beans	35			35
Peas	-	423	-	423
Soya beans	-	350	140	489
Vegetables	3,953	40,111	5,187	49,251

Table 1: Sample of missing data

These were issues synonymous with all the season data surveys gathered in 2016, 2017, 2018 and 2019 in different format that demonstrated inconsistency in heading and crops in the data collection with missing values. (See Appendix B) Thus, the datasets survey of Season C was not used in this analysis in order to avoid any misleading outcome as a result of data inconsistencies, outlier and missing values. The data was further subjected to more cleaning to remove the outliers and carrying out summation of both Season A and Season B for each of the years from 2015 to 2020.

Data Composition and Categorisation

The datasets were made up of 20 Agricultural Products and 7 variables with the values +1 or -1 in Metric Tonnes for years recorded in the available from 2015 to 2020. The agricultural products included Maize, Paddy rice, Sorghum, Wheat, Cassava, Sweet Potatoes, Other

cereals, Sweet Potatoes, Irish Potatoes, Yams, Cooking Banana. Dessert Banana, Banana for Alcohol, Beans, Bush beans, Climbing Beans, Peas, Ground Nuts, Soya beans, Vegetables and Fruits.

Summary of seasons (a and b) values

The cleaned datasets were merged from 2015 Season A to 2020 Season A were summed up with the cleaned dataset of the merged 2015 Season B to 2020 Season B respectively to present the total values of each crop production in metric tons (MT) for the periods 2015 to 2022.

Crops Production	2015A	2016A	2017A	2018A	2019A	2020A
Maize	295,365	300,330	324,368	332,670	331,090	353,999
Paddy rice	38,695	49,430	41,662	36,581	37,584	42,231
Sorghum	31,147	47,522	55,217	57,934	59,286	52,225
Wheat	2,772	4,365	3,651	5,950	7,082	4,138
Other cereals	1,988	1,100	0	3,981	2,620	1,930
Cassava	402,436	405,961	451,362	486,440	523,117	578,545
Sweet Potatoes	502,709	503,760	574,500	661,583	674,257	635,007
Irish Potatoes	335,394	369,691	378,906	439,512	468,931	427,471
Yams & Taro	78,570	82,244	129,630	70,653	71,104	85,414
Cooking Banana	378,499	379,196	415,868	406,044	456,351	502,972
Dessert banana	96,981	97,304	113,032	112,283	112,937	120,868

Banana for beer	508,509	529,434	456,585	434,356	450,853	476,241
Beans	245,179	248,945	274,568	251,189	252,569	226,570
Bush beans	146,682	151,715	145,446	164,011	164,163	142,983
Climbing beans	98,497	97,230	78,787	87,178	88,406	83,588
Peas	12,474	11,673	6,768	9,001	9,115	7,933
Ground nuts	5,919	6,054	11,873	12,546	9,362	5,762
Soya beans	11,925	12,346	10,686	12,156	13,638	12,284
Vegetables	129,576	137,608	133,118	162,936	158,927	160,114
Fruits	35,568	34,438	54,940	35,884	48,791	23,542

Table 2: Cleaned Rwanda Agricultural datasets for Season A, 2015 to 2022

Similarly, the datasets for Season B were also cleaned shown below in Table 3.

Crop Production	2015B	2016B	2017B	2018B	2019B	2020B
Maize	74,775	73,937	85,912	91,534	90,128	94,634
Paddy rice	58,740	116,310	118,310	118,111	122,042	128,258
Sorghum	102,148	61,114	64,715	55,946	72,291	64,279
Wheat	5,223	5,558	7,224	7,525	8,605	8,673
Other cereals	552	436	1,199	1,214	1,473	1,540
Cassava	522,215	524,259	590,481	640,759	658,708	701,037
Sweet Potatoes	416,693	392,114	483,898	498,790	546,788	611,425
Irish Potatoes	326,631	309,052	398,934	396,064	422,266	352,441
Yams & Taro	70,952	69,590	93,131	97,331	100,700	102,628

Cooking Banana	387,039	391,886	315,481	353,652	362,165	410,259
Dessert banana	89,670	90,720	111,312	117,057	123,502	138,090
Banana for beer	402,143	410,186	326,729	346,304	344,825	383,641
Beans	186,634	184,951	276,435	233,540	230,744	209,383
Bush beans	109,994	108,902	139,343	142,077	140,066	125,425
Climbing beans	76,640	76,049	86,788	91,463	90,678	83,958
Peas	4,062	4,192	5,600	5,689	6,136	5,668
Ground nuts	5,229	5,206	8,805	9,734	10,200	10,542
Soya beans	9,325	9,183	12,925	10,427	10,588	10,955
Vegetables	130,597	124,801	155,476	145,272	155,506	166,272
Fruits	12,620	10,963	16,378	17,711	23,315	24,830

Table 3: Cleaned Rwanda Agricultural datasets for Season B, 2015 to 2022.

Following the merging of the different datasets into two distinct datasets with all headings, titles and crop productions, a total summary of the Season A and Season B for each year, from 2015 to 2020 as contained in the datasets were summed up to give the total value of product for the years as included below and also see (See Appendices, A,B, C and D).

Crops Production	2015 (A+B)	2016 (A+B)	2017 (A+B)	2018 (A+B)	2019 (A+B)	2020 (A+B)
Maize	370,139	374,267	410,280	424,204	421,218	448,632
Paddy rice	97,435	165,741	159,972	154,691	159,626	170,489
Sorghum	133,295	108,636	119,932	113,880	131,577	116,504
Wheat	7,995	9,923	10,875	13,475	15,686	12,811

Other cereals	2,540	1,536	1,199	5,195	4,092	3,469
Cassava	924,651	930,220	1,041,843	1,127,200	1,181,825	1,279,581
Sweet Potatoes	919,402	895,874	1,058,398	1,160,373	1,221,045	1,246,432
Irish Potatoes	662,024	678,743	777,840	835,575	891,197	779,913
Yams & Taro	149,521	151,834	222,761	167,984	171,803	188,042
Cooking Banana	765,538	771,082	731,349	759,696	818,515	913,231
Dessert banana	186,651	188,024	224,345	229,340	236,439	258,959
Banana for beer	910,652	939,620	783,314	780,661	795,678	859,883
Beans	431,814	433,895	551,003	484,729	483,314	435,954
Bush beans	256,676	260,617	284,788	306,088	304,229	268,408
Climbing beans	175,138	173,279	165,576	178,640	179,084	167,546
Peas	16,537	15,865	12,368	14,690	15,251	13,601
Ground nuts	11,148	11,259	20,678	22,279	19,561	16,304
Soya beans	21,250	21,528	23,612	22,583	24,226	23,239
Vegetables	260,173	262,409	288,594	308,208	314,433	326,386
Fruits	48,188	45,401	71,318	53,595	72,107	48,372

Table 4: Summation of values for Seasons 2015A to 2020A and the 2015B to 2020B

In order to have a framework for easy distribution and analysis the different crops were grouped into 5 categories to ensure the class of the crop production used in the analysis.

Crops Production Categories

The 20 Agricultural products grouped into 5 class categories are shown in the table below for the 6 years from 2015 to 2020.

Class	Crops	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Cereals		611,404	660,103	702,258	711,446	732,200	751,906
	Maize	370139	374,267	410,280	424,204	421,218	448,632
	Paddy rice	97435	165,741	159,972	154,691	159,626	170,489
	Sorghum	133295	108,636	119,932	113,880	131,577	116,504
	Wheat	7994	9,923	10,875	13,475	15,686	12,811
	Other cereals	2540	1,536	1,199	5,195	4,092	3,469
Tuber		2,655,599	2,656,670	3,100,842	3,291,132	3,465,870	3,493,968
	Cassava	924,651	930,220	1,041,843	1,127,200	1,181,825	1,279,581
	Sweet Potatoes	919,402	895,874	1,058,398	1,160,373	1,221,045	1,246,432
	Irish Potatoes	662,024	678,743	777,840	835,575	891,197	779,913
	Yams & Taro	149,521	151,834	222,761	167,984	171,803	188,042
Banana		1,862,841	1,898,726	1,739,007	1,769,697	1,850,633	2,032,073
	Cooking Banana	765,538	771,082	731,349	759,696	818,515	913,231
	Dessert banana	186,651	188,024	224,345	229,340	236,439	258,959
	Banana for beer	910,652	939,620	783,314	780,661	795,678	859,883
Legumes		912,563	916,444	1,058,025	1,029,010	1,025,666	925,051

	Beans	431,814	433,895	551,003	484,729	483,314	435,954
	Bush beans	256,676	260,617	284,788	306,088	304,229	268,408
	Climbing beans	175,138	173,279	165,576	178,640	179,084	167,546
	Peas	16,537	15,865	12,368	14,690	15,251	13,601
	Ground nuts	11,148	11,259	20,678	22,279	19,561	16,304
	Soya beans	21,250	21,528	23,612	22,583	24,226	23,239
Vegetables and Fruits		308,361	307,811	359,912	361,803	386,540	374,758
	Vegetables	260,173	262,409	288,594	308,208	314,433	326,386
	Fruits	48,188	45,401	71,318	53,595	72,107	48,372

Table 5: Categorisation of the Rwanda's Crop Production from 2015 to 2020

The crops were classed as follows.

- A.1. Cereal Crops:** Maize, Paddy rice, Sorghum, Wheat and Other cereals
- A.2. Tuber Crops:** Cassava, Sweet Potatoes, Irish Potatoes and Yams & Taro
- A.3. Banana Crops:** Cooking Banana, Dessert banana and Banana for beer
- A.4. Legumes Crops:** Beans, Bush beans, climbing beans, Peas, Ground nuts and Soya beans
- A.5. Vegetables and Fruits Crops:** Vegetables and Fruits

The Final Cleaned Dataset

The final dataset was cleaned and categorized to cover all crop production from 2015 to 2020 as shown below which demonstrated the final dataset used in the analysis for this research work.

Crop Production /Production Year	Cereals	Tuber	Banana	Legumes	Vegetables and Fruits
2015	611,404	2,655,599	1,862,841	912,563	308,361
2016	660,103	2,656,670	1,898,726	916,444	307,811
2017	702,258	3,100,842	1,739,007	1,058,025	359,912
2018	711,446	3,291,132	1,769,697	1,029,010	361,803
2019	732,200	3,465,870	1,850,633	1,025,666	386,540
2020	751,906	3,493,968	2,032,073	925,051	374,758

Table 6: Final cleaned dataset used for analysis

After the completion of the final dataset, it was imported into Inzight for analysis with the different variables identified and the set of variables respectively following the quantitative analysis steps to achieving successful data analysis. The variables were classified as ratios as there are different types and quantities of crops used in the analysis. Thus, a true 0 (zero) exists in this analysis which makes it easy to sum the values. Whilst the crops were categories as nominal value they have no individual nominal value, as they are grouped according to the types of crops or class.

3.7 Data Analysis Tools

The researcher relied on Microsoft Excel also known as Excel or Spreadsheet to organize the data. Excel enabled the researcher to format, organize, and making information easier to view. Data organization is made easier because Excel contains number of boxes called cells that orders the data in rows and columns. As a consequence, the data was collected in Excel CSV files which were merged and cleaned to ensure there was no duplication of values so that various missing information did not affect the outcome of the analysis. The spreadsheet was used to collect the results from the data entries and surveys carried out by the agricultural operators with the Rwanda Space Agency.

From the Excel organization, Data was analysed by Inzight and R: Inzight a statistical and analytics software developed by the department of Statistic, University of Auckland in New Zealand. Inzight is free software used for statistics that can be integrated with R via the R Console which is also a statistic software tool used by Data Scientist. Inzight statistical software can analyse data and help in important decision-making. It provides in-depth analysis of the research problem. Via Inzight, the data is analysed by diverse statistical tests, leading to a graded list of aspects, which highlight how PPPs contribute to economic growth and sustainable development.

Data analysis permits measurement and the degree level at which the independent variable impacts on the dependent variables (Kiviluoto et al., 2011). Thus, the multivariate or multiple regression analysis is applied to measure how PPPs contribute to economic growth through the RSA agricultural activities. In addition, every factor will be connected to the p-value and the p-value over the significance level (0,05) shows no statistical importance. Statistically significant data, mean or standard deviation will be deliberated and compared so as to reveal whether there is a different connection between the agricultural productivity and economic growth. In addition, every factor is related with a hypothesis that later can be examined or analyzed in terms of the statistical importance. This is complemented by use of an inference prediction model approach to test the hypothesis and determine whether Rwanda can continue to sustain its development using the Spearman's Ranking Correlation. Moreover, highest ranking aspects in terms of the mean value as well as standard deviation can be understood and investigated to give further explanation for the reasons it is considered as vital from PPPs standpoint.

Thus, the statistical tools, which will be applied in this thesis is the multivariate multiple - regression analysis, the mean squared analysis as well as the standard deviation. Through carrying out the mean value and the standard deviation for data analysis conclusions and comparisons are drawn between the findings and the current literature. Furthermore, by carrying out a multivariate multiple-regression analysis we are able to establish the extent to which the independent variable (cereal) influences crop production output.

The Mean Score

The mean score analysis is the statistical measurement, which specifies and assess the significance levels of specific variables (Wan et al., 2014). The mean can be estimated in terms of its comparative position concerning the stated factors included in the survey. Additionally, mean score can thus generate data concerning rating of various factors and the significance levels to the participant (Wan et al., 2014).

Standard Deviation

Standard deviation will too be incorporated in the thesis since it offers the capability to rate extracted mean values professionally (Wan et al., 2014). In other words, aspects characterized by the low standard deviation will thus be rated higher than those with the high standard-deviation (Osei-Kyei & Chan, 2017; Wan et al., 2014).

The Multiple Regression Analysis

The Multivariate Multiple-Linear Regression (MMLR) refers to the extension of a traditional multiple-linear regression analysis (Hartung & Knapp, 2005). MMLR is the suitable statistical tool once forecasting the multiple variables when utilizing a single or numerous various variables. In addition, the MMLR tool may also be applied so as to measure arithmetical relationship among the variables (Hartung & Knapp, 2005). MMLR is very helpful in the situation where more than a single dependent or independent variable exist. Therefore, MMLR may competently determine the connection between numerous variables and again test our three hypotheses (Hartung & Knapp, 2005). The thesis will also integrate MMLR analysis since it can incorporate several diverse dependent variables with one classed set of an independent variable. Thus, MMLR allows research concerning the connection among the production per year and perceived significance of classed set of an independent variable.

The P-value approach

The P-value approach is a type of measurement utilized in statistics to confirm a hypothesis compared to the discovered data. The p-value regulates the likelihood of attaining the observed findings, on the assumption that the irrelevant hypothesis is right. The minor the p-value is, the robust the evidence is, for the different hypothesis. Mostly, the p-value at for instance 0.05 or below is considered as statistically substantial, hence resulting to the refusal

of the irrelevant hypothesis and taking the alternative (Greenland, 2018). Where the value is greater than 0.05, it implies that there is absence of statistical deviation from the irrelevant hypothesis and is thus acknowledged. Consequently, a p-value over 0.05 leads into refusing the hypothesis.

Validity of Research Instruments

The research instruments show the degree of fitness of the variables measured (Kothari, 2004). The validity of such tools is relevant to the data gathered and the researcher tested the legality of the instrument as well as its reliability to ensure the reliability of the data used. Validity was focused on the data collected to see if it fulfills the research objectives.

3.8 Reliability or Dependability of Research Instruments

According to Kothari, C.R. (2004), reliability refers to the measurement as to how accurate test results or facts are generated by different tests. For the purposes of verifying the reliability of such data, a determination is carried out until the finalized categories are divided to the population for information gathering.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

In this study, ethical considerations were followed and this started from the initial design of the study that aimed at public good “and at the very least should do no harm”. This goes on until communication or dissemination of findings and the study ensured transparency or openness, publicness as well as replicability. The study guaranteed replicability of the study findings and thus, better transparency of the research procedures as well as integrity of research data. Other ethical conditions to meet while using secondary data were: The study ensured that the data must be de-identified before release to the researcher.

The ethical considerations are not just vital for investigators who participate in secondary research themselves, but even to those who conduct primary data gathering with the purpose of documenting or archive their information and make them accessible for the future re-use. Archiving may, and would, be performed by all and in such situations, it is important to

consider advice from the professional data services, from the initial stages of the study, to design the entire data lifecycle in a way that may be ethical, lawful, and value-maximising (Garfinkel and Cranor, 2010).

Furthermore, throughout the study, the researcher would ask for permission from the responsible departments or sources to access data. However, permission for further usage and analysis was implied. Nevertheless, the ownership and rights of the original information was acknowledged or recognized. Thus, ethical considerations were followed throughout the research by balancing issues of transparency and confidentiality.

3.10 Understanding the Source

The researcher tried to understand the sources of data before using it and conducting data analysis and this was done by trying to understand where it came from, how it was gathered or collected, and the limitations or biases it might have. The researcher also checked the terms and conditions of the data providers and respected any limitations or restrictions or consents or permissions they have set. For instance, some of the used data in this study was publicly accessible, but required acknowledgment and this was done or achieved by the investigator in this study. On the other hand, where the other data was confidential or sensitive, the researcher tried to seek for consent or approval to use the data.

3.10.1 Protecting the Privacy

While using the secondary data from RSA, the researcher also tried to protect the privacy of the agencies, individuals and groups who participated and were represented in the data. The investigator avoided disclosing any individual or personal or identifiable data, for example the names, addresses, or phone numbers, unless given have their consent or the legal obligation. The investigator also ensured to anonymize or combine or aggregate data to minimize the risk of re-identification or damage and harm. For instance, the researcher used codes, classifications, categories, or ranges instead of particular values, and classed the data according to the crops.

3.10.2 Acknowledgement of the limitations

The researcher also acknowledged the limitations plus uncertainties that might impact on the data validity or reliability. The investigator did not make claims or conclusions, which go beyond the scope and quality of the information or data, or those that contradict the original objective or purpose as well as the context of the data. The researcher also did a comparison (compare and contrast) of the data with various sources and described any differences or gaps.

3.10.3 Citation of the sources

The investigator cited the sources of data or references appropriately and correctly, basing on the standards and conventions of study area. The researcher acknowledged and gave credit to the original authors of the data, and specified any changes or adaptations made. The study also shows the details or links of the formation or data sources to ensure that other readers can access, authenticate, or reproduce the information.

3.10.4 Communication of the findings or results

While using secondary data, the investigator communicated the findings or study results openly, clearly and ethically and ensured that there is no misinterpretation of the data or misleading data. The study applied appropriate and reliable methods or formats in data analysis and presentation for example tables, charts, statistics, and graphs. The data was interpreted and discussed in relation to the research question, objectives, or hypotheses while emphasizing major findings and implications. For instance, the research used headings, captions, and summaries to organize and describe the information or data.

Seeking feedback

The researcher also sought feedback from the supervisors, peers, mentors and experts to improve on research quality and credibility. The researcher was open as well as honest about the data sources, methods, and assumptions of the data by acknowledging any recommendations or criticisms. The researcher also responded to any questions and concerns raised especially from the supervisors and addressed any ethical challenges that emerged during the study.

3.10.5 Conclusion

This chapter has addressed the methods that were followed in analysis of the data that was gathered throughout the research. The chapter has discussed the research methodology and approach that was used to gather, present and analyze information. The data was mainly collected from RSA and was analyzed and presented while observing specific ethical guidelines as enumerated above. The data that was gathered was then analyzed and discussed in Chapter four (4)

Figure 3.8: Steps on Quantitative Analysis

Figure 3.8: Steps on Quantitative Analysis

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS, DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.0 Introduction

The researcher in the previous chapters 1, 2, 3 demonstrated the research background, theory, hypothesis, literature review and the research methodology. This chapter comprises of the findings collected from data analysis. In addition, the chapter will discuss and analyze the findings. This will enable us gain additional insights into the relationship between production year and the production of different crops. How do the different crops produced supported by PPPs through the RSA and how do they contribute to economic growth of Rwanda and its achievement of sustainable development goals? Additionally, the chapter enable us to examine the statistical significance of variables relation to the regression analysis as well as various statistical measurements.

4.1 Significance Testing

Significance testing will be done by the p-Value and Spearman's Ranking Correlation in the second section to show how agricultural productivity has been consistent in Rwanda. Therefore, this section will base on the findings of the statistical examination, the connection between the production year and the different crops produced in Rwanda. By relying on the p-value technique the research will respond to research questions especially, in finding out whether the crops produced in the country are a result of PPPs influence. Additionally, the established research hypothesis can be tested in relation to its statistical importance (Wan et al., 2014). Consequently, the multiple-regression analysis was done so as to discover the degree at which the independent variable impacts on the other remaining 15 influences or dependent variables that might influence agricultural productivity, which ultimately lead to improved economic growth in Rwanda (Wan et al., 2014).

4.1.1 SECTION 1

Table 7: Inzight inference using normal theory: the dependent variable production year and the independent variables cereal, tuber crop, banana, legumes, vegetables and fruits (cubic trend coefficients with 95% confidence intervals)

Variables	Estimate	Lower	Upper	p-value
CEREAL CROP PREDICTION				
Intercept	2005.5	-651.53	4662.5	0.083
Cereal	0.00011482	-0.01161	0.011839	0.970
Cereal^2	-3.1642e-10	-1.7513e-08	1.6881e-08	0.944
Cereal^3	2.5202e-16	-8.1334e-15	8.6375e-15	0.909
<i>P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0</i>				
TUBER CROP PREDICTION				
Intercept	1656.8	-2363.3	5677	0.22
Tuber	0.00035691	-0.0035823	0.0042961	0.73
Tuber^2	-1.1875e-10	-1.3974e-09	1.1599e-09	0.73
Tuber^3	1.3258e-17	-1.243e-16	1.5082e-16	0.72
<i>P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0</i>				
BANANA CROP				
Intercept	-11157	-65836	43523	0.47
Banana	0.021232	-0.066199	0.10866	0.41
Banana^2	-1.1388e-08	-5.7905e-08	3.513e-08	0.40
Banana^3	2.0326e-15	-6.2025e-15	1.0268e-14	0.40
<i>P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0</i>				
LEGUME CROPS				
Intercept	-22079	-40014	-4144.6	0.034
Legumes	0.072062	0.017904	0.12622	0.029
Legumes^2	-7.1679e-08	-1.261e-07	-1.7256e-08	0.030
Legumes^3	2.3719e-14	5.5166e-15	4.1921e-14	0.030
<i>P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0</i>				
VEGETABLES AND FRUITS				
Intercept	9472	1826.1	17118	0.033
Vegetables and Fruits	-0.06414	-0.12991	0.0016348	0.052
Vegetables and Fruits ^2	1.8295e-07	-4.7999e-09	3.707e-07	0.052
Vegetables and Fruits ^3	-1.7308e-13	-3.5098e-13	4.829e-15	0.053

As seen in table 7 above, 3 crops have a p-value below the significance level of (0,05). This denotes that there exists a statistical significance (0,05) related to production year. These crops are legumes which seem to contribute less to the economic growth of Rwanda

ultimately failing to make significant changes in achieving its sustainable development goals. These crops provide p—values with legumes1 at (0,029), Legume 2 at (0,030) and Legumes 3 at (0,030). However, this low statistical significance in the production of legumes is not necessarily an indicator that PPPs do not contribute to economic growth Rwanda. Since the developed hypotheses refers to whether the PPPs impact on agricultural productivity, influence of PPPs on economic growth and effectiveness of PPPs on Long-term sustainability. The production year influences the levels of the crops produced as seen in the table 7 a p-value below the associated confidence interval of 0,95 (5%) means that the production year is influenced differently by the different crops produced in that particular year with differing levels.

Therefore, the rest of the crops indicate statistically significant p-values, it indicates that the crops produced have a differing impact on the production year. This influences agricultural productivity ultimately economic growth in Rwanda however, not we cannot confirm if it contributes to long-term sustainability of the agricultural sector. Hence, we accept the hypotheses that PPPs contribute to agricultural productivity, that PPPs have an influence on economic growth. However, the three crops as identified in Table 7 show no statistical significance in the p-Value. As a consequence, these crops (legumes) have no contribution to either agricultural productivity or economic growth through PPPs.

Variables with the p-Value below associated significance level

There are only 3 crops out of the 15 that showed extreme differing p-values and this implies that only a slight portion of the crops are acknowledged and understood differently (Greenland, 2018). The three crops have a lot to tell us regarding the null hypothesis that PPPs to a certain extent are ineffective in in ensuring long-term sustainable development. Although this thesis applies the same research as other previous studies (APMG, 2016; Xu et al, 2015), there is recognition of three crops below their reasonable significance level. These aspects were suitable as they make us aware that PPPs, where they are involved do not necessarily contribute to agricultural productivity.

Consequently, this thesis has acknowledged that basing on the contribution of PPPs long-term sustainable development. Consequently, the effects of testing H3 specifies that there is a numerical connection among the legume's contribution to sustainable development and how

PPPs can be made effective to contribute to economic development through agricultural output. On-going, another identified aspect below significance level included bananas, which also shows that their contribution to economic growth through PPPs to be differing (Greenland, 2018).

Conversely, using the graphs below, the analysis shows the contribution of PPPs to agriculture in Rwanda and how agricultural productivity contributes economic growth. This is shown by interpreting the results based on Rwanda agricultural crops production datasets to help in achieving the research objectives.

AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION

Figure 4. 3: Increase in agricultural production from 2015 to 2020

The above chart shows the overall increase and consistency in Rwanda's annual agricultural production from 2015 to 2020 in metric tons based on the research survey data from the Rwanda Space Agency. This is an indication of sustainable growth in the overall agricultural production as well as the contribution of the agricultural sector to Rwanda's economic development. According to the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO, 2020), Rwanda's agricultural sector accounted for 40% of the national GDP and the country's GDP has been growing consistently at a rate of 7% since 2014 with tea and coffee being the major exports

as well as dry beans, potatoes, maize, rice, cassava flour, maize flour, poultry, plantains, cassava, potatoes, sweet potatoes, maize and beans as these are the most productive crops. This finding supports Sethi and Acharya (2018) who stated that the production of agricultural goods by sole proprietors contribute to the county’s growth. However, there are different private sectors that contribute to agriculture in view of developing the economy.

GROWTH IN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR AS AN ECONOMIC ACTIVITY

Figure 4.4: Growth in agricultural sector as an economic activity

According to the 2020, Food and Agriculture Organization Report (2020) on Rwanda, agriculture is the main economic activity in Rwanda with 70% of the population engaged in the sector, and around 72% of the working population is employed in agriculture. The period for cultivation is divided into the first cultivation season (from September to January) and the second cultivation season (from February to June).

The chart above shows that there have been some changes in each year from 2015 to 2020 as a sign that agriculture sector is major economic activity in Rwanda contributing to the county’s economic growth and development. This is further complemented by the University of Pennsylvania report indicates that Rwanda's economy is almost exclusively agriculturally based with more than 90% of the population depending on agriculture for their livelihood

inform of food crop production, employment or industrial work and the sector contributes more than 40% of the nation's GDP.

RWANDA'S FOREIGN EXCHANGE EARNING

The chart below shows a consistent increase in Cereal agricultural product in Metric Tons as a source of foreign exchange earnings from 2015 to 2020. According to the data indicated below, there is a significant change in Rwanda's economic growth and the tremendous effect on income it has generated from exports as well as increase in the country's foreign exchange earnings over the years. This study complements findings by other studies (Ozcan and Ozturk ,2019) that PPPs contribute to foreign exchange earnings, which impact on the growth of the economy.

Thus, the production of more crops contributes to economic growth especially in terms of production outputs. It is through increased production of such crops that PPPs enable economic growth in Rwanda. The increase in crops produced in the country facilitates trade in exports and helps in innovative ways to provide opportunities to the people by obtain better incomes as well as expanding the size of the economy.

Figure 4.5: Consistency in increase in foreign exchange earnings from 2015 to 2020

A similar consistency can be found in the Tuber Crops production over the same period of years as shown below between 2015 to 2020. It also shows that the year 2015 and 2016 has similar or same quantity of agricultural production. The chart above shows that there has been some form of changes in each year from 2015 to 2020.

Figure 4.6: Consistent increase in Tuber crop production and foreign exchange earnings from 2015 to 2020

It is revealed in the above two graphs that there is consistent improvement in production of agricultural products which are essential sources of income as well as foreign exchange revenue and this impacts positively on the county's economic growth and sustainable development. This finding is in-line with findings by Sobiech (2019) who has remarked that agricultural produce is an essential source of foreign exchange that contributes to the development of the economy. That this is aided by the private sector, which makes the economy develop successfully over the time by focusing mainly on the public needs and services.

Figure 4.7: Increase in Crops Production from 2015 to 2020

According to International Monetary Fund (2018), Rwanda's GDP per capita in 1994 was \$146 but in 2017, this had increased to \$774 and was projected to increase to about \$819.65 as an estimated forecast at the end of fiscal year 2018. The current IMF statistics show that, Rwanda's economy has been growing steadily between 6% and 7% annually with majority of the country's growth resulting from agricultural activities and other sectors of the economy. Rwanda's current GDP growth stood at 6.4% as of 30th April 2022 according to the International Monetary Fund's real GDP statistic as shown in the screenshot below.

Figure 4.8: Rwanda's Current Real GDP Growth as of April 2022 (6.4%)

4.1.2 SECTION II

INFERENCE PREDICTORY ANALYSIS FOR EACH PRODUCT

From the findings and the interpretations above, the researcher was encouraged to carry out further data analysis using an inference prediction model approach to test the hypothesis and determine whether Rwanda can continue to sustain its development using the Spearman's Ranking Correlation.

INZIGHT INFERENCE USING NORMAL THEORY FOR CEREAL CROP PREDICTION

=====

Response/outcome variable: Production. Year (numeric)

Predictor/explanatory variable: Cereal (numeric)

=====

Total number of observations: 6

=====

Inference of Production. Year versus Cereal:

Cubic Trend Coefficients with 95% Confidence Intervals

	Estimate	Lower	Upper	p-value
Intercept	2005.5	-651.53	4662.5	0.083
Cereal	0.00011482	-0.01161	0.011839	0.970
Cereal^2	-3.1642e-10	-1.7513e-08	1.6881e-08	0.944
Cereal^3	2.5202e-16	-8.1334e-15	8.6375e-15	0.909

P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0

iNZight Summary

Response/outcome variable: Production. Year (numeric)

Predictor/explanatory variable: Cereal (numeric)

Total number of observations: 6

=====
Summary of Production. Year versus Cereal:

Cubic trend:

$$\text{Production. Year} = 2005 + 0.0001148 * \text{Cereal} - 3.164e-10 * \text{Cereal}^2 + 2.52e-16 * \text{Cereal}^3$$

Rank correlation: 1.00 (using Spearman's Rank Correlation)

INZIGHT INFERENCE USING NORMAL THEORY FOR TUBER CROP PREDICTION

Response/outcome variable: Production. Year (numeric)

Predictor/explanatory variable: Tuber (numeric)

=====
Total number of observations: 6

Inference of Production. Year versus Tuber:

Cubic Trend Coefficients with 95% Confidence Intervals

	Estimate	Lower	Upper	p-value
Intercept	1656.8	-2363.3	5677	0.22
Tuber	0.00035691	-0.0035823	0.0042961	0.73
Tuber^2	-1.1875e-10	-1.3974e-09	1.1599e-09	0.73
Tuber^3	1.3258e-17	-1.243e-16	1.5082e-16	0.72

P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0

=====
iNZight Summary

Response/outcome variable: Production. Year (numeric)

Predictor/explanatory variable: Tuber (numeric)

Total number of observations: 6

=====
Summary of Production. Year versus Tuber:

Cubic trend:

$$\text{Production. Year} = 1657 + 0.0003569 * \text{Tuber} - 1.187\text{e-}10 * \text{Tuber}^2 + 1.326\text{e-}17 * \text{Tuber}^3$$

Rank correlation: 1.00 (using Spearman's Rank Correlation)

INZIGHT INFERENCE USING NORMAL THEORY FOR BANANA CROP

Response/outcome variable: Production. Year (numeric)

Predictor/explanatory variable: Banana (numeric)

Total number of observations: 6

=====

Inference of Production. Year versus Banana:

Cubic Trend Coefficients with 95% Confidence Intervals

	Estimate	Lower	Upper	p-value
Intercept	-11157	-65836	43523	0.47
Banana	0.021232	-0.066199	0.10866	0.41
Banana^2	-1.1388e-08	-5.7905e-08	3.513e-08	0.40
Banana^3	2.0326e-15	-6.2025e-15	1.0268e-14	0.40

P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0

iNZight Summary

=====
Response/outcome variable: Production. Year (numeric)

Predictor/explanatory variable: Banana (numeric)

Total number of observations: 6
=====

Summary of Production. Year versus Banana:

=====
Cubic trend:

Production. Year = -11160 + 0.02123 * Banana - 1.139e-08 * Banana^2 + 2.033e-15 *
Banana^3

Rank correlation: 0.14 (using Spearman's Rank Correlation)

INZIGHT INFERENCE USING NORMAL THEORY FOR LEGUME CROPS

=====
Response/outcome variable: Production. Year (numeric)

Predictor/explanatory variable: Legumes (numeric)

Total number of observations: 6
=====

Inference of Production. Year versus Legumes:

=====
Cubic Trend Coefficients with 95% Confidence Intervals

	Estimate	Lower	Upper	p-value
Intercept	-22079	-40014	-4144.6	0.034
Legumes	0.072062	0.017904	0.12622	0.029
Legumes^2	-7.1679e-08	-1.261e-07	-1.7256e-08	0.030
Legumes^3	2.3719e-14	5.5166e-15	4.1921e-14	0.030

P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0

INZight Summary

Response/outcome variable: Production. Year (numeric)

Predictor/explanatory variable: Legumes (numeric)

Total number of observations: 6

=====
Summary of Production. Year versus Legumes:

=====
Cubic trend:

Production. Year = -22080 + 0.07206 * Legumes - 7.168e-08 * Legumes^2 + 2.372e-14 *
Legumes^3

Rank correlation: 0.43 (using Spearman's Rank Correlation)

INZIGHT INFERENCE USING NORMAL THEORY FOR VEGETABLES AND FRUITS

=====

Response/outcome variable: Production. Year (numeric)

Predictor/explanatory variable: Vegetables and Fruits (numeric)
=====

Total number of observations: 6
=====

Inference of Production. Year versus Vegetables and Fruits:
=====

Cubic Trend Coefficients with 95% Confidence Intervals

	Estimate	Lower	Upper	p-value
Intercept	9472	1826.1	17118	0.033
Vegetables and Fruits	-0.06414	-0.12991	0.0016348	0.052
Vegetables and Fruits ^2	1.8295e-07	-4.7999e-09	3.707e-07	0.052
Vegetables and Fruits ^3	-1.7308e-13	-3.5098e-13	4.829e-15	0.053

P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0
=====

INZight Summary

Response/outcome variable: Production. Year (numeric)

Predictor/explanatory variable: Vegetables and Fruits (numeric)

Total number of observations: 6

=====

Summary of Production. Year versus Vegetables and Fruits:

Cubic trend:

Production. Year = $9472 - 0.06414 * \text{Vegetables and Fruits} + 1.83e-07 * \text{Vegetables and Fruits}^2 - 1.731e-13 * \text{Vegetables and Fruits}^3$

Rank correlation: 0.89 (using Spearman's Rank Correlation).

SPEARMAN –INFERENCE PREDICTION OBSERVATION

The Spearman's rank-order correlation is the non-parametric version of the Pearson product-moment correlation. Spearman's correlation coefficient, (ρ , also signified by r_s) which measures the strength and direction of association between two ranked variables. This ensures that a Spearman correlation of 1 result when the two variables being compared are monotonically related, even if their relationship is not linear. This means that all data points with greater x values than that of a given data point will have greater y values as well and the Spearman correlation coefficient, r_s , can take values from +1 to -1. Were.

- 'rs' of +1 indicates a perfect association of ranks,
- 'rs' of zero indicates no association between ranks
- 'rs' of -1 indicates a perfect negative association of ranks.

Therefore, the closer 'rs' is to zero, the weaker the association between the ranks and the probability of a perfect positive association of the ranks which means a likelihood of the predication occurring or happening.

In order words, where the value is between '0' – '1' is a positive indication that the prediction will occur but with low uncertainty. But where the value is '1' is a high possibility of the

predication occurring as predicated with higher certainty of occurrence. Whilst '-1' is a clear indication that the predication will not occur with a high certainty the likelihood is negative.

The Spearman's correlation inference analysis outcome can be supported with the reports by the current IMF Statistics on Rwanda's GDP between 2020 and April 2022 for comparative analysis.

The prediction analysis from the observation points above, showed positive probability of some sort of consistency in the growth of agricultural sector which is evident in the International Monetary Fund data mapper dashboard on Rwanda's GDP in 2021 with a real GDP growth of 10.2% as an increase, compared to 6.1% in 2020. This finding supports Soecipto and Verhoest (2018) who underscored that successful growth of the private sector even when it is agriculture drives growth, creates jobs and improves employment conditions. Thus, consistency in agricultural growth would improve economic conditions in the country by increasing cash inflow in the market as employees are paid better salaries. The cash inflow and outflow are important for improving the economic conditions of the people in the country and increasing the GDP.

Figure 9: Rwanda's Real; GDP Growth for 2021 was 10.2 %

Similarly comparing this observation with the current GDP of Rwanda from the IMF Bank data, shows the positive growth in 2022. Thus, the inference prediction analysis from the observation points showed positive probability of consistency in the growth of agricultural sector which is evident in the International Monetary Fund data mapper dashboard on Rwanda's GDP in 2020 with a real GDP growth of 6.1% as an increase, compared to 6.4% in 2022 as at April 2022.

Figure 10: Rwanda had higher probability of increased GDP in Dec 2022

From the above screenshot as of April 2022, Rwanda's GDP stood at 6.4% with this prediction result, there was positive probability that Rwanda's GDP could double or triple at the end of the fiscal year in December 2022 unless an unforeseen external factor affects the country.

Discussion

In this section the findings of the study are debated and analyzed by relating them to the previous literature. Moreover, this is done to gain additional understanding concerning the connection between the agricultural productivity and PPPs and how agricultural productivity contributes to economic growth in Rwanda. Additionally, we shall show that this thesis integrates both the role PPPs, agricultural productivity and the economic growth of Rwanda by assessing the linkage between the existing literature and the findings of this study. This is done in regard to the significance of both the similarities and dissimilarities.

Although the findings in this study are not exhaustive, they provide room for the role of PPPs in agricultural productivity and economic growth in Rwanda. The findings also lay a ground to

justify PPPs contribution in the sustainability of its economy especially through agricultural production. This is corroborated with previous studies (Rurangwa, Kinyanjui, et.al., 2018) state that economic development in Rwanda is still necessary because the community needs to develop itself. They argue that this development can be achieved through building infrastructure, which is facilitated by PPPs. It is through PPPs that financing that building infrastructure can help people improve their lives while at the same time contributing to economic growth.

Besides PPPs contribution to agricultural productivity, they are an efficient framework to facilitate capacity building and production of agricultural produce in Rwanda. While expanding the same view, Zore, Čuček and Kravanja, (2018) have stated that sustainable development can be achieved through a better use of PPPs in natural resources and also the construction sectors by reducing the amount of waste, reducing pollution as well as conserving biological diversity.

Furthermore, the findings of this study indicate that PPPs can lead to sustainability of agriculture in Rwanda. This is noticed from the cereal production for a year as a foreign exchange earner from the iNZight inference result using normal theory production for a year. This is against the cereal per cubic trend and the ranking correlation analysis using the Spearman's rank correlation on a total number six (6) observation. The ranking correlation of '1.00' is a positive (+1), which indicates the likelihood that Rwanda can sustain the agricultural production of cereals for export in large quantities at a co-efficient with 95% Confidence Intervals. This high level of confidence seems supported by other previous studies assertion that PPPs improve service delivery and value for money and are a solution for generating income (UNCHS Habitat, 2000). According to Nzimimakwe, (2006), PPPs are a solution to sustainable provision of education, health, transport, agriculture and energy. It is through their abilities to facilitate productivity in agriculture that they aid sustainability of cereal crop production.

It is on the basis that PPPs offer value for money, that in 2008 the government of Rwanda initiated collaboration between the private sector and the public sector. This is because PPPs facilitate the flow of funds from private sector to the public sector reducing the financial burden on the government. Li et.al, (2020) have remarked that sustainable development is one of the critical notions related to economic growth and expansion. Through, sustainability

of agricultural productivity Rwanda is able to achieve economic growth in the well-balanced manner. This will make sure that it includes development for socio-economic and ecological systems without economic growth damaging the environment.

Furthermore, the findings indicate that Rwanda production of the tuber crop for exports is sustainable at a co-efficient with 95% confidence intervals. This is the same with the production of the banana crop for export which indicate that its export is sustainable by Rwanda at a co-efficient of 95% confidence. Additionally, the % impact of public private partnership indicates that it facilitates Rwanda's to achieve sustainable development.

This is highly influenced by the agricultural sector which impacts heavily on the rest of the other sectors in the development of the economy at 81.2%. These findings point to the evidence that Rwanda's Agriculture Sector is probably the major source of income and economic growth. It also points to the fact that the agricultural sector provides employment to majority of the population improving the standards of living and contributing to economic growth.

Subsequently, it is accurate to conclude that this is an indication of a positive impact by Private Public Partnerships (PPPs) projects on sustainable development in Rwanda. Thus, if Rwanda's economy continues to experience the current success rate in the economic growth, Rwanda would have $3 * 6.4\%$ GDP growth by the end of 2022 with considerable increase of (+/- 5%) if we factor in influences of external factors. A consequence, we can assert that there is a tendency and possibility of a very high probability that Rwanda's GDP for 2022 would be between 14% and 25%.

These findings are corroborated by findings of other studies (Izuwah, 2019; Wang, 2021; Izuwah, 2019) who have noted that PPPs have a positive contribution on sustainable development in Rwanda. According to Izuwah (2019) PPPs are necessary for the development of water infrastructure in Rwanda. That is why the government of Rwanda has adopted the structure (model) of PPP using the BOT arrangement (build-operate-transfer) where the private sector has a major responsibility to finance, construct, design and operate projects.

Additionally, the findings of the study complement what Wang (2021) has noted about PPPs regarding sustainable development in Rwanda as the most effective tools to ensure sustainability. This is because they alleviate the impact of shortage of fiscal funds into

government procurement while making full use of the private sector expertise, technological innovation, and experiences. Furthermore, in highlighting the impact of PPPs on sustainable development Alabi, Kasim and Lasisi, (2020) have stressed that commitment towards achieving the sustainable development goals entails pursuing progress over economic, social and environmental targets. PPPs facilitate in the building of infrastructure to promote inclusive and sustainable development through contribution of scarce resources.

Despite PPPs well-known positive contributions in the agricultural sector as illustrated by the findings in the study, PPPs have been criticized in Rwanda for operational constraints and having no clear empirical impacts on stakeholders. That is why the government of Rwanda relies on institutional capacity of the government to design, negotiate, implement, and monitor partnerships (Nkusi, 2016). This has also been supported by enacting a law that setting up rules and regulations for the future contracts between the private sector and government agencies. These are further supported by roles and responsibilities of Rwanda Department Board (RDB), which ensures results and success of the PPP projects. Broadly, PPPs have been adopted to aid the financing of infrastructure development projects that benefit the public and achieve economic development and growth.

Furthermore, the findings of the study indicate that PPPs contribute to economic growth through agricultural production, which is also supported by Haque and Rashid (2019). They have argued that projects that promote economic growth such as road infrastructure rely on PPPs, which helps to provide employment opportunities to Rwandan citizens contributing to the country's development goals. Although the construction of the roads and highways through PPP contracts gives the private sector a right to design, fund and build infrastructure projects, it facilitates the provision of suitable infrastructure and fosters economic growth and development.

Although another interesting finding of the study is that vegetables and Fruit Crops Production can be a major export, it indicated that Rwanda has a possibility of sustaining and increasing their production in larger quantities/ However, this can be achieved with a lower certainty even when at a co-efficient of 95% confidence. This low probability of producing the crops sustainably has according to Bolomope et.al, (2020) led to low flexibility of the projects

in the area of sustainable development with low effectiveness. From a research point of view, this results into actions that lead to less interests in seeking PPPs as a financial solution to such projects. Projects that share little potential for return over investment and are difficult to be implemented by any of the parties involved.

Thus, deriving from the findings of this study, which is also supported by previous studies, we can confidently assert that PPPs are not only utilized for the creation of physical assets and services but also meet the broad economic growth venture such as agricultural productivity. In the context of sustainability, PPP have the potential to achieve broad positive impacts such as creating jobs, promotion of new and innovative thinking and improving infrastructural development for the future.

4.2 New Public Governance Theory (NPG)

The analysis of the data in this study has followed NPG because it is a practice that agitates for agitates for public policy sustainability, public facilities, public service institutions, community and environmental issues (Osborne, 2010:413). It generates see-through actions, processes and transparent structures, which are more socially receptive. It looks at public affairs management from numerous elements of socio-political influence, public policy influence, administrative governance, agreement governance, corporate governance, meta-governance, decentered control as well as network governance. As already noted, it is more appropriate for analyzing how agriculture contributes to economic growth and sustainable development. It enables and compels public policy execution and provision of public services in a plural as well as a pluralist system (Osborne, 2010:415). A plural system would include all inter-reliant players who contribute to service provision, whereas a pluralist system refers to where numerous processes notify the policy-making structure or system (Koenig-Archibugi, 2003:319).

Since no single actor has enough resources to solve multifaceted, dynamic and different problems, there a necessity for PPPs to provide a plurality of players or actors. This ensues into the development of additional “joined up” policies and “people centered” methodologies

or approaches where various levels of government operate together in closer collaboration with various public, private, charitable and informal public institutions.

Hence, NPG promotes the delivery of public services via PPPs basing on dual collaboration and governance-controlled systems to allow actual partnership, straight power relations, close institutional relations, trust, status, reciprocity, joint interdependence and mutual decision-making. As a consequence, NPG is the most appropriate theory that helps us to understand how PPPs contribute to agricultural productivity, how agricultural productivity contributes to economic growth and how effectiveness of PPP types in long-term sustainability.

4.3 Conclusion

This chapter has presented the findings collected from data analysis and discussed them in relation to the previous studies. This has enabled us to gain deeper insights into the relationship between production year and the production of different crops. Further, relying on NPG theory, the chapter has shown how PPPs contribute to agricultural productivity, how agricultural productivity contributes to economic growth and effectiveness of PPP types in long-term sustainability. The findings clearly indicate that agricultural productivity contributes to economic growth and is sustainable through PPPs contribution. How do the different crops produced supported by PPPs through the RSA contribute to economic growth of Rwanda? How agricultural production contributes to economic growth and its sustainability in Rwanda and how it can be sustained through PPPs? Additionally, the chapter has enabled us to examine the statistical significance of each variable in relation to the regression analysis, the p-Value and Spearman rank order correlation.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Introduction

This section entails the summary of the chapters, conclusions drawn from the study, and the limitations and recommendations that have been identified. Additionally, the results are defined plus a section for the future research is provided. Whereas PPPs contribute to projects and agricultural productivity in different states, there is little information on PPPs and agricultural productivity in Rwanda. There is scarcity of studies or research concerning how PPPs influence agricultural productivity and how the agricultural sector contributes to economic development and its sustainability. Thus, a quantitative research study has been done to integrate and examine the three aspects and their link with PPPs through a multiple regression-analysis.

u5.1 Summary and Conclusions

Chapter 1 presented the introduction and background to the study of PPPs on sustainable development in Rwanda specifically through RSA. Additionally, it discusses the statements of the research problems, gaps and hypotheses.

Chapter 2 Focused on the literature, definitions of PPPs, the theoretical underpinnings and the diverse models of public-private partnerships, their roles and responsibilities, impacts on the economy, causes of their success the concept of sustainable development, role of space technologies, space technologies and the Rwanda Space Agency. The chapter ends with identification of the gap in the literature.

Chapter 3 This chapter has addressed the methods that were followed in analysis of the data that was gathered throughout the research. It provides a detailed quantitative methodology followed the variables and the hypotheses to be examined while focusing on Rwanda Space Agency as one of the agencies running PPPs projects in Rwanda and how the impact on agricultural productivity and presented while observing specific ethical guidelines as enumerated.

Chapter 4 Presents and analyses the findings helping to gain deeper insights into the relationship between production year and the production of different crops. Further, relying on NPG theory, the chapter has shown how PPPs contribute to agricultural productivity, how agricultural productivity contributes to economic growth and effectiveness of PPP types in long-term sustainability. The findings clearly indicate that agricultural productivity contributes to economic growth and is sustainable through PPPs contribution. How do the different crops produced supported by PPPs through the RSA contribute to economic growth of Rwanda? How agricultural production contributes to economic growth and its sustainability in Rwanda and how it can be sustained through PPPs? Additionally, the chapter has enabled us to examine the statistical significance of each variable in relation to the regression analysis, the p-Value and Spearman rank order correlation.

Chapter 5 Has presented the conclusion, findings, contributions and the recommendations for future research.

The aim of the research was to investigate the impact of PPPs on sustainable development in Rwanda, specifically through the RSA. This was fulfilled through testing the following hypotheses to articulate the expected relationship between PPPs and agricultural productivity: -

Hypothesis 1: *Impact of PPPs on Agricultural Productivity.*

- **HO** = Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) involving the Rwanda Space Agency do not significantly increase the productivity in Rwanda's agricultural sector.
- **H1** =Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) involving the Rwanda Space Agency significantly increase the productivity in Rwanda's agricultural sector.

Hypothesis 2: *Influence of PPPs on Economic Growth.* Tests whether there is a direct link between PPPs and economic growth indicators.

- **HO** =The involvement of PPPs in Rwanda's agricultural sector does not positively correlate with an increase in Rwanda's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).
- **H2** =The involvement of PPPs in Rwanda's agricultural sector positively correlates with an increase in Rwanda's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Hypothesis 3: Effectiveness of PPP Models (Types) in Long-term Sustainability. This Hypothesis focuses on the long-term aspect of PPPs.

- **H0** = Current PPP models employed in Rwanda are ineffective in ensuring long-term sustainable development in the agricultural sector.
- **H3** = Current PPP models employed in Rwanda are effective in ensuring long-term sustainable development in the agricultural sector.

5.2 The Findings

Although this research is not conclusive, according to the findings it has provided more room for research to be conducted in order to ascertain whether Rwanda's collaboration with the Public Private Partnership (PPP) in the development of the country's economy is sustainable. Thus, each result analysis from the 5 categories of agricultural products can be interpreted individually as follows:

1. Cereal Production as Foreign Exchange Earner: The iNZight inference result using normal theory based on the summary of production year versus cereal from the cubic trend and the ranking correlation analysis using the Spearman's rank correlation on a total number six (6) observations shows that the correlation ranking is '1.00' which is a positive (+1). Therefore, it shows that probability or likelihood of Rwanda sustaining the production of cereals as an agricultural produce in larger quantity for export is achievable at a co-efficient with 95% Confidence Intervals.

2. Tuber Production as Foreign Exchange Earner: The iNZight inference using normal theory for tuber crop prediction based on the total number of six (6) observations 6 as observed from the summary of production year versus tuber according to cubic trend and ranking correlation of 1.00 based on the Spearman's rank correlation also a positive indication that the likelihood of Rwanda sustaining the production of Tuber product as an agricultural produce in larger quantity for export is achievable at a co-efficient with 95% confidence intervals.

3. Banana Crop Production as Foreign Exchange Earner: The iNZight inference using normal theory for banana crop was also based on a total number of six (6) observations from the cubic trends and can be seen in the summary of production year versus banana that the ranking correlation is '0.74' from the Spearman's rank correlation analysis result. This is also a positive indication that Rwanda has a possible likelihood of sustaining the production of Banana Crop products as an agricultural produce in larger quantity for export but with a lower amount of certainty which is also achievable at a co-efficient of 95% confidence.

4. Legume Crop Production as Foreign Exchange Earner: The iNZight inference using normal theory for legume crop production based on same total number of six (6) observations from the cubic trends and the summary of production year versus legumes, shows that the ranking correlation is '0.43' from the Spearman's rank correlation analysis result. This is also a positive indication that Rwanda has a possible likelihood of sustaining the production of Legume Crop products as an agricultural produce in larger quantity for export but with a lower amount of certainty which is also achievable at a co-efficient of 95% confidence.

5. Vegetables and Fruit Crops Production as Foreign Exchange Earner: The iNZight inference outcome produced from using the normal theory for vegetable and fruit prediction analysis based on a total number of six (6) observations from the cubic trends and the summary of production year versus legumes showed that the ranking correlation outcome was '0.89' from the Spearman's rank correlation analysis result. This is also a positive indication that Rwanda has a very possible likelihood of sustaining and increasing the production of vegetables and fruit crops as agricultural produce in larger quantity for export but with a lower certainty of occurring but achievable at a co-efficient of 95% confidence.

Rwanda Export Crops	Spearman Rank	Average Correlation Rank
Cereal	1	$\frac{1 + 1 + 0.74 + 0.43 + 0.89}{5} = \underline{4.06}$ $= 0.812$
Tuber	1	
Banana	0.74	
Legumes	0.43	
Vegetables and Fruits	0.89	
The % Impact of PPP on Rwanda's SD		81.2 %

Table 8: Predicted Percentage Impact of PPP Calculation on Sustainable Development

Deriving from the above, the % Impact of public private partnership in Rwanda's sustainable development from the agricultural sector in the development of her economy is 81.2%. From these findings we can assert that Rwanda's Agriculture Sector is the major source of income and contributes to economic growth. In addition, it is accurate to conclude that this is an indicator that there is a positive impact of Private Public Partnerships (PPPs) projects on sustainable development in Rwanda.

Thus, if Rwanda's economy continues to experience the current success rate in the economic growth, Rwanda would have 3 * 6.4% GDP growth by the end of 2022 with consideration of (+/- 5%) influence from the external factors. As a consequence, there is a high probability that Rwanda's GDP for 2022 may be between 14% and 25%. Regarding our hypotheses above, the findings have shown that PPP contribute to agricultural production. They have also shown that agricultural productivity contributes to the economic growth of Rwanda and the production of some crops can be sustained.

5.3 Contribution of the Study

The contribution of this study is three-fold, gap in the literature, methodological and practical in nature.

a) The study is practical

In that it is the first of its kind to assess the contribution of PPPs to economic agricultural productivity and economic development in Rwanda. Hence, it provides pertinent information on how PPPs can be used to support the economy and economic growth in the country. It also provides the best success factors that could be copied and applied for the success of PPPs in future.

b) A more Inclusive definition of Private Public Partnerships (PPPs)

The literature from the previous works definition of PPPs is more skewed in in favour infrastructural procurement and provision of wanting resources for investment. These studies have defined PPPs from the period the contract takes as long-term contracts between the public entity and the private entity, where the private would agree to design and build, expand, or upgrade the public sector infrastructure. It would also take responsibility for financial, technical, and operational risks. Although assuming a more cooperative approach of PPPs and benefits both parties (BOT model), this study differs from the previous studies by adopting a more inclusive definition of PPPs. PPPs should be deliberated from a function-specific perspective, emphasizing collaborative efforts with other parties. This takes into consideration legal aspects bringing government and private sector together stressing mutuality, obligation and trust as social aspects of the partnership. The adopted definition is more inclusive because it takes into consideration the social aspects of the partnership that would lead to achievement of sustainable development goals.

c) A gap in the Literature on PPPs, Space Technologies and Sustainable development in Rwanda

Despite a lot of attention that has been devoted to developing countries on achievement of sustainable development goals, none has focused on Rwanda. The argument here is that Rwanda after its violent past merits much attention, but an extreme focus on the use of space technologies in aiding achievement of sustainable development goals. The use of space technologies (RSA) increases revenue for the country's strategic plan and helps in delivery of more sustainable goals. According to (Maria Jose and Mathieu, 2021) in their article "Unpacking the dangerous illusion of PPPs" they argued that Public Private Partnership (PPPs) are increasingly being promoted as a way of securing much needed funds to deliver development projects. The PPP promoters continue to argue that they are an efficient way to link the gap in infrastructure and provide essential services in order to achieve the sustainable development Goals as established in UN's Agenda 2030.

Previous studies have not considered the role of PPPs from a wide economic perspective in enabling achievement of sustainable development goals that would ensure the requirements of future generations. As a consequence, this study takes into consideration the social aspects of PPPs by adopting a three-way contribution of PPPs in enabling sustainable development goals in Rwanda through economic, environmental and social sustainability.

5.4 Research Limitations

This research work is a product of the best outcome as result of time and energy put into this work by the researcher believing that the research approach and research methodology used in arriving at the research conclusion may not be sufficient due to limitations in the research process and resources available. Like all other research works, there are various limitations that affected this research work which were due to circumstances beyond the researcher's control.

The empirical findings stated in this thesis are subjected to various limitations. The study was carried out utilising a quantitative research technique and nevertheless, the fact that the numerical measures that were done demonstrated that the results were satisfactory, it is worth stating that the sample size was also inadequate, implying that the trouble of categorising noteworthy relations among diverse factors increased.

Furthermore, a slight sample size lessened the probability of a sample being generalized for the entire population, limiting the possible conclusions of the study. The time limitation is a distinct factor that condensed the possible results of the study within the thesis. The limited time-frame, unavailability of data, and the fact that data correction started under COVID 19 lockdown limited data collection and reliance on only the agricultural sector to examine the contribution of PPPs to Rwanda's economic growth.

There was a limitation of data resources, this also had an impact on the results of the study. From the researcher's perspective, the major limitation was the availability of data, since this research would benefit more on accessing more dataset and conduct analysis from various economic sectors. That is what led to the examination of only the agricultural sector and RSA case study. Hence, it would have been more advantageous if the data available from the Rwanda Space Agency included the other sectors of the economy. This would have provided a better analysis, comparison and interpretation of the impact of PPP on Rwanda's sustainable development.

The other limitation was lack of access to list or records of private public partnership organizations in Rwanda 's development projects including Energy, Infrastructure, Manufacturing and Healthcare. These would have helped to expand the data set and the assessment of the contribution of each stakeholder or organization in the sustainability of Rwanda's economy. An expanded data set would have made the findings of the study more robust. In addition, that would be more amenable to quantitative analysis. However, the question of the dissertation could better be answered by relying on both quantitative and qualitative analysis in order to ascertain the impact of public private partnership in Rwanda as a case study with the Rwanda Space Agency.

The positive side was that the data source from Rwanda Space Agency (RSA) includes the data credible databases, namely: Rwanda Ministry of Finance (MINECOFIN,) National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda (NISR), Rwanda Geoportal (Spatial Data), Private Sector Federation (PSF), African Development Bank (ADB), Rwanda Development Board (RDB), International Monetary Fund (IMF), Esri Rwanda and World Bank (WB) but they were all on agriculture sector of the Rwanda's economy.

Finally, this research work was set out to determine the impact of PPP projects on sustainable development in Rwanda focusing on Rwanda Space Agency as a case study but the various

issues and personal situation including Covid-19 pandemic made things more difficult for the researcher. This contributed to the difficulty in getting access to the required resources from the Rwanda Space Agency, which caused huge constraints to the researcher's effort in delivering this project within the best status and possible time.

5.5 Recommendations for future research work

The researcher suggested some recommendations for the future research work on private public partnership and sustainable development in Rwanda for other researchers who are interested to further the research work of this project.

1. **Accessing Rwanda's Data for Different Economic Sectors:** There is need to use diverse data that captures the entire of as possible from Rwanda's economy database for future work in order to provide a more robust data pool for the analysis of the impact of public private partnership in the sustainability development of Rwanda rather than the use of sample data that focus on only the agricultural sector of the economy. Thus, the researcher recommends the collection and use of datasets that cut across all sectors of Rwanda's economy.
2. **Research Work Time Constraint:** There is also the need to allocate a lot of time for any future research work that would involve used of raw data especially from multiple sources and with different formats. The required time to complete future research work would be a huge constraint if not properly planned and adequate. The time factor needs to be adequate owing to the various external factors including the individual researcher's circumstances that needs to be factored into the research time.
3. **Expanding the scope of the research work:** The researcher also recommends that any future work on the impact of public private partnership in sustainable development should be expanded to cover other areas of Rwanda's economy where there is adequate data especially in the areas of energy, healthcare, infrastructure, and manufacturing to determine the effect of PPP on Rwanda's economy development and sustainability.

4. **Access to Public Private Partnerships' Organisations:** The researcher recommends a facilitation process to meet with the PPP organisation or stakeholders involved in the implementation of PPP projects in Rwanda as part of the research in order to have access to the required information with the relevant stakeholders without being biased and also avoid unconscious biasness in the hope of seeking the true situation of the Private Public Partnerships' projects.

5. **Starting Early to Set the Target:** The researcher recommends starting the research work early to allow enough dedicated time for other resources that could be utilise for the research work in terms of getting Public Private Partnerships' Organisations directory and contacting them to make enquiries very early before the research work commence and liaising early with your research supervisor to ensure your target or research goal are achievable.

6. **Eclectic Methodology**

Future research should use a combination of methods both qualitative and quantitative to obtain a bigger picture of how PPPs impact on agricultural productivity and how agricultural productivity impacts on economic growth.

7. **Set a SMART Objective:** The researcher also recommends that it is not enough to have a research title, target and objectives, but rather the research objectives and topic as a whole need to be **SMART**.

- **Specific** – Setting the real numbers of objective with straight forward and simple meaning that are relevant to the research work and makes sense.
- **Measurable** – Ensure your objectives and targets can be measured.
- **Achievable** – Don't embark on any research work you cannot achieve.
- **Realistic** – Ensure your research work is real and relevant in a way.
- **Time – bound** – Ensure the timeline is adequate and works for you.

The above recommendations are not exhaustive but are meant to encourage and prepare any researcher that is interested in carrying out further research work on the impact of private public partnership projects in sustainable development in Rwanda.

5.6 Conclusion

This chapter has discussed the conclusions drawn from the study, and the limitations that have been identified. Additionally, the results are defined plus a section for the future research is provided. Whereas PPPs contribute top projects and agricultural productivity in different states, there is little information on PPPs and agricultural productivity in Rwanda. There is scarcity of studies or research concerning how PPPs influence agricultural productivity and how the agricultural sector contributes to economic development and its sustainability. Thus, a quantitative research study has been done to integrate and examine the three aspects and their link with PPPs through multiple regression-analysis. state and with statistical evidence if the investors' level of experience impact on the participants' perception on various factors of the PPPs in developing nations.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A - SEASONAL AGRICULTURE SURVEY SEASON A

Crops Production	2015A	2016A	2017A	2018A	2019A	2020A
Maize	295,365	300,330	324,368	332,670	331,090	353,999
Paddy rice	38,695	49,430	41,662	36,581	37,584	42,231
Sorghum	31,147	47,522	55,217	57,934	59,286	52,225
Wheat	2,772	4,365	3,651	5,950	7,082	4,138
Other cereals	1,988	1,100	0	3,981	2,620	1,930
Cassava	402,436	405,961	451,362	486,440	523,117	578,545
Sweet Potatoes	502,709	503,760	574,500	661,583	674,257	635,007
Irish Potatoes	335,394	369,691	378,906	439,512	468,931	427,471
Yams & Taro	78,570	82,244	129,630	70,653	71,104	85,414
Cooking Banana	378,499	379,196	415,868	406,044	456,351	502,972
Dessert banana	96,981	97,304	113,032	112,283	112,937	120,868
Banana for beer	508,509	529,434	456,585	434,356	450,853	476,241
Beans	245,179	248,945	274,568	251,189	252,569	226,570
Bush beans	146,682	151,715	145,446	164,011	164,163	142,983
Climbing beans	98,497	97,230	78,787	87,178	88,406	83,588
Peas	12,474	11,673	6,768	9,001	9,115	7,933

Ground nuts	5,919	6,054	11,873	12,546	9,362	5,762
Soya beans	11,925	12,346	10,686	12,156	13,638	12,284
Vegetables	129,576	137,608	133,118	162,936	158,927	160,114
Fruits	35,568	34,438	54,940	35,884	48,791	23,542

Table 2 for Cleaned Rwanda Agricultural datasets for Season A, 2015 to 2022

APPENDIX B - SEASONAL AGRICULTURE SURVEY SEASON B

The datasets for Season B were also cleaned shown below in Table 3.

Crop Production	2015B	2016B	2017B	2018B	2019B	2020B
Maize	74,775	73,937	85,912	91,534	90,128	94,634
Paddy rice	58,740	116,310	118,310	118,111	122,042	128,258
Sorghum	102,148	61,114	64,715	55,946	72,291	64,279
Wheat	5,223	5,558	7,224	7,525	8,605	8,673
Other cereals	552	436	1,199	1,214	1,473	1,540
Cassava	522,215	524,259	590,481	640,759	658,708	701,037
Sweet Potatoes	416,693	392,114	483,898	498,790	546,788	611,425
Irish Potatoes	326,631	309,052	398,934	396,064	422,266	352,441
Yams & Taro	70,952	69,590	93,131	97,331	100,700	102,628
Cooking Banana	387,039	391,886	315,481	353,652	362,165	410,259
Dessert banana	89,670	90,720	111,312	117,057	123,502	138,090
Banana for beer	402,143	410,186	326,729	346,304	344,825	383,641
Beans	186,634	184,951	276,435	233,540	230,744	209,383
Bush beans	109,994	108,902	139,343	142,077	140,066	125,425
Climbing beans	76,640	76,049	86,788	91,463	90,678	83,958
Peas	4,062	4,192	5,600	5,689	6,136	5,668
Ground nuts	5,229	5,206	8,805	9,734	10,200	10,542
Soya beans	9,325	9,183	12,925	10,427	10,588	10,955
Vegetables	130,597	124,801	155,476	145,272	155,506	166,272

Fruits	12,620	10,963	16,378	17,711	23,315	24,830
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Table 3 represent Cleaned Rwanda Agricultural datasets for Season B, 2015 to 2022.

APPENDIX C - SEASONAL DATA SAMPLE OF CROP PRODUCTION

The datasets for season A&B from 2015-2020 are shown below in Table 4 and 5.

Crops Production	2015 (A+B)	2016 (A+B)	2017 (A+B)	2018 (A+B)	2019 (A+B)	2020 (A+B)
Maize	370,139	374,267	410,280	424,204	421,218	448,632
Paddy rice	97,435	165,741	159,972	154,691	159,626	170,489
Sorghum	133,295	108,636	119,932	113,880	131,577	116,504
Wheat	7,995	9,923	10,875	13,475	15,686	12,811
Other cereals	2,540	1,536	1,199	5,195	4,092	3,469
Cassava	924,651	930,220	1,041,843	1,127,200	1,181,825	1,279,581
Sweet Potatoes	919,402	895,874	1,058,398	1,160,373	1,221,045	1,246,432
Irish Potatoes	662,024	678,743	777,840	835,575	891,197	779,913
Yams & Taro	149,521	151,834	222,761	167,984	171,803	188,042
Cooking Banana	765,538	771,082	731,349	759,696	818,515	913,231
Dessert banana	186,651	188,024	224,345	229,340	236,439	258,959
Banana for beer	910,652	939,620	783,314	780,661	795,678	859,883
Beans	431,814	433,895	551,003	484,729	483,314	435,954
Bush beans	256,676	260,617	284,788	306,088	304,229	268,408
Climbing beans	175,138	173,279	165,576	178,640	179,084	167,546
Peas	16,537	15,865	12,368	14,690	15,251	13,601
Ground nuts	11,148	11,259	20,678	22,279	19,561	16,304
Soya beans	21,250	21,528	23,612	22,583	24,226	23,239
Vegetables	260,173	262,409	288,594	308,208	314,433	326,386

Fruits	48,188	45,401	71,318	53,595	72,107	48,372
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Table 4 shows Summation of values for Seasons 2015A to 2020A and the 2015B to 2020B

Class	Crops	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Cereals		611,404	660,103	702,258	711,446	732,200	751,906
	Maize	370139	374,267	410,280	424,204	421,218	448,632
	Paddy rice	97435	165,741	159,972	154,691	159,626	170,489
	Sorghum	133295	108,636	119,932	113,880	131,577	116,504
	Wheat	7994	9,923	10,875	13,475	15,686	12,811
	Other cereals	2540	1,536	1,199	5,195	4,092	3,469
Tuber		2,655,599	2,656,670	3,100,842	3,291,132	3,465,870	3,493,968
	Cassava	924,651	930,220	1,041,843	1,127,200	1,181,825	1,279,581
	Sweet Potatoes	919,402	895,874	1,058,398	1,160,373	1,221,045	1,246,432
	Irish Potatoes	662,024	678,743	777,840	835,575	891,197	779,913
	Yams & Taro	149,521	151,834	222,761	167,984	171,803	188,042
Banana		1,862,841	1,898,726	1,739,007	1,769,697	1,850,633	2,032,073
	Cooking Banana	765,538	771,082	731,349	759,696	818,515	913,231

	Dessert banana	186,651	188,024	224,345	229,340	236,439	258,959
	Banana for beer	910,652	939,620	783,314	780,661	795,678	859,883
Legumes		912,563	916,444	1,058,025	1,029,010	1,025,666	925,051
	Beans	431,814	433,895	551,003	484,729	483,314	435,954
	Bush beans	256,676	260,617	284,788	306,088	304,229	268,408
	Climbing beans	175,138	173,279	165,576	178,640	179,084	167,546
	Peas	16,537	15,865	12,368	14,690	15,251	13,601
	Ground nuts	11,148	11,259	20,678	22,279	19,561	16,304
	Soya beans	21,250	21,528	23,612	22,583	24,226	23,239
Vegetables and Fruits		308,361	307,811	359,912	361,803	386,540	374,758
	Vegetables	260,173	262,409	288,594	308,208	314,433	326,386
	Fruits	48,188	45,401	71,318	53,595	72,107	48,372

Table 5 for Categorisation of the Rwanda's Crop Production from 2015 to 2020

APPENDIX D - SEASONAL CLEANED AND MISSING DATASETS

The tables below represent cleaned and missing datasets.

Crop Production /Production Year	Cereals	Tuber	Banana	Legumes	Vegetables and Fruits
2015	611,404	2,655,599	1,862,841	912,563	308,361
2016	660,103	2,656,670	1,898,726	916,444	307,811
2017	702,258	3,100,842	1,739,007	1,058,025	359,912
2018	711,446	3,291,132	1,769,697	1,029,010	361,803
2019	732,200	3,465,870	1,850,633	1,025,666	386,540
2020	751,906	3,493,968	2,032,073	925,051	374,758

Table 6 represents final cleaned dataset used for analysis

Production of Main Crops (MT)				
Crops	1.2	2.1	2.2	Total
Tubers and Roots	59,431	30,441	2,354	92,226
Sweet potatoes	144	9,127	2,354	11,625
Irish potatoes	59,287	21,314	-	80,601
Legumes and Pulses	35	2,823	318	3,177
Beans	35	2,050	179	2,264
Bush Beans	0	2,050	179	2,229
Climbing beans	35			35
Peas	-	423	-	423
Soya beans	-	350	140	489
Vegetables	3,953	40,111	5,187	49,251

Table 1 of missing Data

OTHER DATASETS USED FOR ANALYSIS

Production of Main Crops (MT)						
Agricultural Operators						
Crops	1.1	1.2	2.1	2.2	3.0	S/Total
Maize	221,529	6,882	36,541	3,794	10,557	279,302
Paddy rice	-	-	7,653	10,269	-	17,922
Sorghum	20,062	3,798	638	384	5,992	30,875
Wheat	1,755	908	-	-	-	2,663
Other cereals	1,869	14	18	-	86	1,988
Cassava	382,835	-	10,244	1,162	7,951	402,192
Sweet Potatoes	448,232	8,997	39,711	3,794	1,933	502,666
Irish Potatoes	190,924	137,983	3,519	95	573	333,094
Yams & Taro	68,452	-	8,070	1,646	402	78,570
Cooking Banana	365,597	-	540	-	11,770	377,908
Dessert banana	96,598	-	-	-	346	96,944
Banana for beer	496,791	-	3,403	-	8,170	508,364
Beans	227,313	4,577	6,248	766	5,713	244,618
Bush beans	134,216	-	5,702	686	5,607	146,211
Climbing beans	93,098	4,577	546	80	106	98,407
Peas	11,430	860	52	1	126	12,470
Groundnuts	5,611	-	139	-	161	5,911
Soya beans	10,804	-	753	47	21	11,625
Vegetables	107,538	742	15,486	2,180	748	126,693
Fruits	33,650	329	2	-	1,441	35,422

Table of uncleaned dataset (only used for analysis)

Variables	Estimate	Lower	Upper	p-value
CEREAL CROP PREDICTION				
Intercept	2005.5	-651.53	4662.5	0.083
Cereal	0.00011482	-0.01161	0.011839	0.970
Cereal^2	-3.1642e-10	-1.7513e-08	1.6881e-08	0.944
Cereal^3	2.5202e-16	-8.1334e-15	8.6375e-15	0.909
<i>P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0</i>				
TUBER CROP PREDICTION				
Intercept	1656.8	-2363.3	5677	0.22
Tuber	0.00035691	-0.0035823	0.0042961	0.73
Tuber^2	-1.1875e-10	-1.3974e-09	1.1599e-09	0.73
Tuber^3	1.3258e-17	-1.243e-16	1.5082e-16	0.72
<i>P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0</i>				
BANANA CROP				
Intercept	-11157	-65836	43523	0.47
Banana	0.021232	-0.066199	0.10866	0.41
Banana^2	-1.1388e-08	-5.7905e-08	3.513e-08	0.40
Banana^3	2.0326e-15	-6.2025e-15	1.0268e-14	0.40
<i>P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0</i>				
LEGUME CROPS				
Intercept	-22079	-40014	-4144.6	0.034
Legumes	0.072062	0.017904	0.12622	0.029
Legumes^2	-7.1679e-08	-1.261e-07	-1.7256e-08	0.030
Legumes^3	2.3719e-14	5.5166e-15	4.1921e-14	0.030
<i>P-values for the null hypothesis of no association, H0: beta = 0</i>				
VEGETABLES AND FRUITS				
Intercept	9472	1826.1	17118	0.033
Vegetables and Fruits	-0.06414	-0.12991	0.0016348	0.052
Vegetables and Fruits ^2	1.8295e-07	-4.7999e-09	3.707e-07	0.052
Vegetables and Fruits ^3	-1.7308e-13	-3.5098e-13	4.829e-15	0.053

Table 7 shows Inzight inference using normal theory: the dependent variable production year and the independent variables cereal, tuber crop, banana, legumes, vegetables and fruits (cubic trend coefficients with 95% confidence intervals)

Rwanda Export Crops	Spearman Rank	Average Correlation Rank
Cereal	1	$\frac{1 + 1 + 0.74 + 0.43 + 0.89}{5} = \underline{4.06}$ $= 0.812$
Tuber	1	
Banana	0.74	
Legumes	0.43	
Vegetables and Fruits	0.89	
The % Impact of PPP on Rwanda's SD		81.2 %

Table 8 predicted Percentage Impact of PPP Calculation on Sustainable Development